

SKASE Journal of Translation and Interpretation

ISSN 1336-7811

VOLUME 19 - 2026 No. 1

DOI: [10.33542/JTI2026-1-0](https://doi.org/10.33542/JTI2026-1-0)

Table of Contents

(Files in PDF format)

1.	Wioleta Karwacka Between Humans and the Rest of the Natural World: A Corpus-Based Study of Popular Science Articles in Translation with a Focus on Human Categories DOI: 10.33542/JTI2026-1-1	2
2.	Sarah Mariam Roy Bridging the Sacred: Communicative Efficacy in Modern Translations of John through Relevance Theory DOI: 10.33542/JTI2026-1-2	20
3.	Volga Yılmaz-Gümüř, Laurence Jay-Rayon Ibrahim Aibo, Cristiano Mazzei Teaching Translation and Interpreting Online: Assessment Strategies from Practical Experience DOI: 10.33542/JTI2026-1-3	39
4.	Melita Lemut Bajec, Klara řumenjak Women Are as Fickle as April Weather – Are They Really? Cross-Cultural Analysis of Anglo-American and Slovenian Proverbs Featuring the Word <i>Woman</i> DOI: 10.33542/JTI2026-1-4	58
5	Ali Sukayna, Marwan Jarrah, Amer Al-Adwan Adapting <i>Ad Hoc</i> Concepts in Screen Productions DOI: 10.33542/JTI2026-1-5	81
	List of Reviewers	

Between Humans and the Rest of the Natural World: A Corpus-Based Study of Popular Science Articles in Translation with a Focus on Human Categories

Wioleta Karwacka, University of Gdańsk

Abstract

This paper presents a corpus-based analysis of popular science articles published in Scientific American and translated into Polish. Its aim is to analyze how lexemes denoting human categories such as “human”, “people” and “person” are translated in popular science texts and to establish whether there are shifts in those categories that may lead to modifying the way of depicting human relationships to other animals or the environment, especially by emphasizing or attenuating anthropocentrism or human exceptionalism expressed in texts. The bilingual corpus used in this study comprises 184 pairs of source and target texts from the English-language version of Scientific American translated into Polish and published between January 2019 and January 2023 in Świat Nauki (the Polish edition of Scientific American). The design for this study included corpus creation and compilation, exploration of word lists, concordance and parallel concordance for the translation of human categories. The findings suggest that human categories are usually sustained in target texts and human relationship to other animals or the environment is also sustained in translation. However, there are also moderately frequent shifts in explicitness, occasionally accompanied by sentence structure change, resulting in changes in the perceived human exceptionalism and anthropocentrism and emphasizing or attenuating human agency in environmental depletion.

Keywords: *corpus, translation, anthropocentrism, human exceptionalism, popularization*

1. Introduction

This paper attempts to address the issues discussed by Cronin (2017), who called for adopting a wider perspective in translation studies and including more ecocentric approaches. It is also a continuation of the discussion on the representation of the voices of nature in translation inspired by Taivalkoski-Shilov (2020). According to Michael Cronin’s (2017) diagnosis of the current state of ecological thought in translation studies, the environmental perspective is, in fact, absent, even though its presence may seem more than justified. Since Cronin’s *Ecotranslation* was published, environmental problems and the representation of nature have received some attention in translation studies, for instance from Sealey (2019), Desblache (2020), Taivalkoski-Shilov (2020), Wang (2023), Dasca & Cerarols Ramírez (2024). However, Michael Cronin’s (2017) observation that there is a gap in research into translation remains relevant today as translation studies almost completely disregard the ecological aspects of translation. Seeking the ecological perspective in translation studies is justified by the reality of the field. After all, translators function and actively participate in a multidimensional ecosystem – translators handle texts about its problems, mediate communication, participate in negotiating the role of technical development, tourism or food production in environmental change (Cronin 2017); yet, translation scholars hardly ever discuss those issues. Translation research rarely touches upon the relationship between humans and our environment. Perhaps one possible answer to these demands is to look critically at the

language used to describe nature, even though, as Cronin (2021: 47) notes, from the point of view of the theoretical or methodological framework, the social factors affecting translation as much as the environment are more important than the intra-textual dynamics. However, linguistic analysis may shed light on the relationship between humans and the rest of the natural world if we take into account that the ecotranslational perspective emphasizes the connection between translation and environment and thus, the focus of research is shifted to translation and language contact that relate human activity to the environment (cf. Dasca & Cerarols Ramírez 2024).

Exploring the ecotranslational perspective involves opposing the assumption that translation is supposed to be unrelated to nature, which is rooted in the nature-culture dichotomy – a far-fetched simplification of people’s relationship with the world around them (Taivalkoski-Shilov 2020). Culture is, in fact, rooted in nature, and translation, among other things, mediates the reciprocal interactions between culture and nature (Desblache 2020). Ironically, nature tends to be conceptualized as completely separate from biological life in cultural contexts and thus becomes reduced to specimens preserved in museums, dusty skeletons or volumes detailing the systematics of various organisms (cf. Desblache 2020).

Translation studies deal exclusively with the translation of human communication while recognizing the diversity of its forms (Cronin 2017: 72–3). It follows that research into translation is anthropocentric. What is more, human and, by extension, humanistic categories also presuppose the existence of a nonhuman element, animate and inanimate entities, so far absent or treated instrumentally in the anthropocentric research and popularization activities, as well as translation (Cronin 2017: 92).

It seems that anthropocentrism and human exceptionalism, which are frequently indicated as responsible for the environmental crisis (Washington et al. 2021; Droz 2022), can be traced in texts discussing environmental problems and their translations. They can become the subject of translation research, if they are present in source and/or target texts. The aim of this paper is to study popular scientific texts which discuss environmental problems, analyze how lexemes denoting human categories such as “human”, “people”, and “person” are translated in popular science texts and establish whether there are shifts in those categories that may lead to modifying the way of depicting human relationships to other animals or the environment, especially by emphasizing or attenuating anthropocentrism or human exceptionalism expressed in texts.

2. Anthropocentrism and human exceptionalism

Anthropocentrism, a view that situates humans as the focal point of interest and the main reference point, assumes that only humans have inherent value, while the value of other beings or organisms, components of the world, depends on their usefulness for human purposes, and is therefore instrumental (Goralnik & Nelson 2012; Kopnina et al. 2018; Washington et al. 2021; Wang 2023). For instance, animals are often described in the context of their relationship to humans and their usefulness (or lack thereof), for example, as resources, sources of food (“products”), companions (“pets”), or “pests” (Cook & Sealey 2018: 312). Some animal names, in fact, denote products made from their meat, for instance “fish” or “chicken” (Cook & Sealey 2017: 312). They are also described as “wild”, “domestic”, “dangerous” – with humans as the point of reference, forming an anthropocentric system (Cook & Sealey 2018: 315).

Nevertheless, essentially, all ethical systems are anthropocentric, since humans are the ones with the cognitive capacity to formulate moral judgments, so the anthropocentric ethical system is the only logical ethical system available to us (Goralnik & Nelson 2012). The origins and roots of anthropocentrism are found in ancient Greek philosophy, Judeo-Christian traditions, Renaissance/Reformation, modernism and postmodernism (Washington et al. 2021).

Even though the term *anthropocentrism* may be ambiguous, it frequently has negative connotations, especially if it appears in the context of ethical considerations about human activity, the essence of humanity, and how we (humans) derive knowledge about the world around us (Droz 2022). The view that anthropocentrism is ethically wrong and responsible for the environmental crisis is quite prominent in environmental discourse (Kopnina et al. 2018). Anthropocentrism is sometimes considered a scapegoat for the environmental crisis (Droz 2022: 24) – it is sometimes accused of belittling the status of the nonhuman world, treating it solely as a resource, which in turn leads to fuelling the ecological crisis and accelerating the extinction of species (Washington et al. 2021). Anthropocentrism is even sometimes considered to be the fundament of ecocide (Washington et al. 2021; Droz 2022). When it occurs in this sense, it is synonymous with, for instance, resourcism, extractivism and also homocentrism, androcentrism, speciesism or species discrimination (see: Cronin 2017; Kopnina et al. 2018; Washington et al. 2021; Droz 2022). Other terms affiliated with anthropocentrism include *human supremacy*, i.e. the belief that humans are “the superior life form of the planet” (Washington et al. 2021: 287), *human chauvinism*, which says that “humans are the only subjects of moral consideration” (Washington et al. 2021: 287) and *human exceptionalism*, according to which humans are essentially different from all other animals (Washington et al. 2021). Some environmental ethicists, however, argue that the criticism of anthropocentrism can be counterproductive and misleading because it tends to overlook the nuances of inequalities between people who differ greatly in their impact on the environment and ignores a simple correlation: Since ecosystems constitute a life support system for humans, anthropocentrism can provide motivation for environmental protection as it is beneficial for humans (Kopnina et al. 2018).

As mentioned above, *human exceptionalism* is affiliated with *anthropocentrism*. Those two terms, however, are not synonymous. *Human exceptionalism* assumes that humans are radically different from any nonhuman beings (Cronin 2017: 68–9). Having said that, we need to state that the differences between humans and other animals are a fact: The most prominent ones include language, cognitive and creative potential (Merleau-Ponty & Séglaard 2003; Toadvine 2007; Kirby 2014; Dean 2021). The fact that one species differs from other species is actually the fundament for biological taxonomy: Giraffes are exceptional and dissimilar from other species, as are penguins and seahorses, etc.:

From the standpoint of contemporary evolutionary biology, it seems that the answer would be negative: human capacities, including those of language and self-consciousness, are just as much a product of evolutionary selection as the traits of other animals. Even if humans have capacities that distinguish us from other species, these are no more or less exceptional than the distinguishing capacities of others. As Mary Midgley puts this point, “We are not the only unique species. Elephants, as much as ourselves, are in many ways unique; so are albatrosses, so are giant pandas.” (Toadvine 2007: 40, cf. Midgley 2005: 152).

In the case of humans, however, the differences are “fetishized” (Cronin 2017: 68) and used as a justification for giving humans a special place in the ecosystem – this is the aspect

that connects human exceptionalism and anthropocentrism. It is worth noting that “recent research suggests that the cognitive gap between humans and other animals is much narrower than has formerly been supposed, with the growing consensus that our differences are a matter of degree rather than kind” (Toadvine 2007: 40). The tendency towards human exceptionalism may be rooted in “our anxieties about the unacceptable parts of our own natures” (Toadvine 2007: 40). Human exceptionalism, much like anthropocentrism, is blamed for animal exploitation and the destruction of the natural environment (Dean 2021). In a sense, one of the effects of climate change and the discussion about it is an increasingly critical assessment of the belief in human exceptionalism (Cronin 2021).

Neither anthropocentrism nor human exceptionalism is a linguistic phenomenon, but the manifestations of both of them can be linguistic. For example, they can be found in dictionary definitions and encyclopaedia entries, which characterize animals in terms of their usefulness as potential human food or as a farm aid, fur donor, subject of laboratory experiments, etc., and emphasize features considered aesthetically appealing by humans – large eyes or the graceful and agile gait of deer (Heuberger 2003).

3. Popularization and nature

Popularization can be seen as a social process involving discursive-semiotic practices that take into account various media, books, the Internet, as well as other genres aimed at disseminating scientific knowledge to lay audiences in an accessible way (Calsamiglia & Van Dijk 2004; Bołtuć 2015). Popularization is characterized not only by certain textual structures but, above all, by the properties of the communicative context: participants and their roles (journalists, readers), their knowledge and attitudes, which are significant factors in the linguistic analysis of the textual structures of such discourse. Popularization involves reformulation and recontextualization of scientific knowledge. Accordingly, the language of popularization publications is expected to be adapted appropriately to the audience, the genre and the requirements of the medium. From the perspective of this study, it is especially important that media actively participate in shaping popular knowledge and opinions about science and scientists, deciding which elements of scientific knowledge to disseminate and how to do so (Calsamiglia & Van Dijk 2004; Bołtuć 2015). That means that they can be a significant element of the tradosphere shaping the attitudes to environmental issues.

The available studies exploring how nature is depicted in popularization include the analysis of modal verbs used in the narrations of nature documentaries. The results indicate that animal behaviour can be depicted as motivated by compulsion or obligation, in a continuum, from circumstantial necessity to the obligation to make an informed choice (Sealey & Oakley 2014). Popular science texts may have anthropocentric overtones and elements of anthropomorphism that may be retained or amplified in translation, as previous studies of Polish translations of English-language popularizations show (Karwacka 2020). In the translation of popularization, shifts can be observed in wording related to social behaviour or attitudes, as emotional and mental states of animals: The social behaviours and attitudes of animals are occasionally conveyed as expressions of emotions or cognitive states. Translations may portray animal behaviour and mindset as slightly more intentional than in the original popularized accounts, indicating an underlying anthropocentric bias in the translation process, whether deliberate or unconscious (Karwacka 2020).

4. Methodology

The focus of this study, i.e. the relationship between humans and the rest of the natural world, is motivated by the eco-translation perspective. Operationalizing concepts such as eco-translation, or human exceptionalism or anthropocentrism for the purposes of translation analysis, however, is a challenge, which is addressed by adopting the approach offered by corpus-based critical translation studies (CbCTS), which explore ideological aspects of translation through analyzing transitivity, nominalization, modality, classification as well as keywords and sensitive words (Hu & Li 2019).

In this study, the focus is on classification, i.e. “designation and description of human beings, objects, and events through lexical means in texts” (Hu & Li 2019: 597). The analysis centers on the classification of humans vs. (other) animals, which may be influenced by the translators’ or editors’ positions and beliefs (Hu & Li 2019). In analyzing translation, classification in the target text may potentially be motivated by the ideology of the author, source text and source culture and also by the translator along with target culture (Hu & Li 2019). Therefore, it seems that exploring human categories may yield observations regarding shifts or manipulations, understood as textual operations (cf. Chesterman 2016: 89), which may affect the way in which humans are depicted in texts about natural environment. The initial assumption was that it would be possible to study the visibility and significance of human agency in environmental changes and the human role in the natural world as well as some linguistic operations which would be related to anthropocentrism or human exceptionalism.

The specific goal is to explore popular science articles about the natural environment with a special focus on lexical units consisting of or containing words which refer to humans and animals – *human, people, man, person* – to see how the humans and their relationship to their environment are depicted in translated texts. The lexemes chosen for this study are related to humans but the fact alone that they are used in a text does not necessarily suggest an anthropocentric or an exceptionalistic approach; however, they may help observe, for instance, potential shifts in conveying the human relationship to the environment. The aim of the study is to trace those potential shifts rather than formulate recommendations on adequate solutions to translation problems.

4.1. Analysis

The tools used in this study include the functionalities available in Sketch Engine: word lists, concordance, annotation and parallel concordance (Kilgarriff et al. 2004; Kilgarriff et al. 2014). The size of the corpus is relatively small (see Section 4.2), therefore the adopted analysis strategy has quantitative elements which inform the qualitative study.

Whenever translation strategies are mentioned, they follow the classification proposed by Chesterman (2016: 91–109):

- Syntactic strategies: literal translation, loan, calque, transposition, unit shift, phrase structure change, clause structure change, sentence structure change, cohesion change, level shift, scheme change.
- Semantic strategies: synonymy, antonymy, hyponymy, converses, abstraction change, distribution change, emphasis change, paraphrase, trope change and other semantic changes.

- Pragmatic strategies: cultural filtering, explicitness change, information change, interpersonal change, illocutionary change, coherence change, partial translation, visibility change, transediting and other pragmatic changes.

The strategies most frequently referred to in this study include the pragmatic strategy of explicitness change, which is defined as a change “either towards more explicitness (explicitation) or more implicitness (implication)” (Chesterman 2016: 105). Whenever explicitness change is detected in the studied material, it is therefore additionally labelled as explicitation or implication as appropriate. Another strategy which is frequently referred to is the semantic strategy of hyponymy, which involves translating a source language (SL) subordinate into a target language (TL) hyponym as well as variants SL hyponym – TL subordinate and SL hyponym – TL hyponym (Chesterman 2016: 100).

At the stage of initial screening of the corpus, the word list of nouns revealed a relatively high frequency of the target *człowiek* (‘human’) (351 occurrences, 8th position on the list). The source *human* occurred 166 times (27th position) producing a significant discrepancy. Most of the discrepancy can be explained when we combine the numbers of occurrences of the sources *human* and *people* (166 and 186 occurrences, 27th and 22nd position in the corpus, respectively). The number, however, is still not equal (351 vs. 352). The fact that the lexemes were relatively frequent in the corpus could signal the anthropocentric perspective.¹ That is why the subsequent steps were planned with the assumption that the study may reveal certain shifts affecting how the nature and the human-nature relationship are conveyed. The next step was to trace how human categories (“human”, “people”, “person”, “man”) were translated to see if there were any shifts that would potentially affect the depicted relationship between humans and the rest of the natural world. The choice was dictated by the assumptions of the study which included analyzing lexical units used as categories. The results of those explorations led to further steps: exploring the translation of “nonhuman” and “including humans”.

4.2. Corpus

Acceptable corpus size remains the subject of debate (Corpas Pastor & Seghiri Domínguez 2010; Condamines & Picton 2022: 231), but the tendency is to compile largest possible corpora, which are heterogeneous in genre and domain (Condamines & Picton 2022: 231). As a general standard, 20–50 occurrences of each expression ensure sufficient representativeness (Condamines & Picton 2022: 231). Collecting and compiling bilingual specialized corpora poses a significant challenge (Condamines & Picton 2022: 232). As a result, corpora in a specialized domain are typically smaller and are characterized by a limited number of occurrences and shared contexts (Bertels 2022: 324). Nevertheless, smaller corpora can be valuable for analyzing text genres in the specialized domain: As Watson (2001: 2) observes, a specific corpus does not have to be extensive if it has “a reasonable number of examples of each target word”. Therefore, with high-frequency words, a corpus of around 50,000 words should produce at least 10 examples of each word. In the case of low-frequency words, the corpus could be expanded up to 200,000 words. Beyond this point, Watson (2001: 2) postulates, “the law of diminishing returns and the size of the file containing the corpus make further expansion not worth the effort” (Watson 2001; cf. Karwacka 2025b, 2025a).

¹ To shed a wider perspective: The word *cat*, which can refer both to the family or species occurs 145 times, is the second most frequently represented within the animal kingdom. On the other hand, the word *animal* – which is used for all animals, including humans, occurs 515 times.

The above factors were taken into consideration – the corpus used in this study (bilingual focus corpus) comprises 180 pairs of source and target texts from the English-language version of *Scientific American* translated into Polish and published between January 2019 and January 2023 in *Świat Nauki* (the Polish edition of *Scientific American*).

Additionally, to compare preferences in Polish non-translations, a reference corpus was used. It is a collection of Polish-language internet texts from 2019, available in Sketch Engine (plTenTen19). The sizes of the sub-corpora are listed below:

- English sub-corpus: 215,613 tokens; 189,500 words
- Polish sub-corpus: 203,388 tokens; 173,184 words
- Reference corpus Polish Web 2019 (plTenTen19): 4,863,900,915 tokens; 3,994,024,317 words
- English Web 2021 (enTenTen21): 61,585,997,113 tokens; 52,268,286,493 words

The material chosen for this study is popular science for a few reasons: Popularizations discuss the relationship between humans and the surrounding world; they influence the degree of environmental education among the lay recipients and even shape their views on environmental issues. In the case of our study material, i.e. *Scientific American* articles, the availability of parallel texts is an important selection criterion.

The names of translators were not indicated by the journal. The texts were chosen with regard to their topic – natural environment, animals, plants, bacteria, funghi (tags: agriculture, animals, biology, climate change, conservation, earth, ecology, environment, evolution, extraterrestrial life, genetics, geology, microbiology, paleontology, plants, pollution, public health, space and physics, vaccines). Texts discussing new technologies, architecture or urban infrastructure and human psychology were excluded because they were unlikely to allow observations of the relationship of humans and the rest of the natural world. The corpus was first processed manually by removing titles – according to the information provided in each issue of *Świat Nauki*, headings are created *de novo* by the Polish editing team. The files were then converted into text-only documents. Next, they were uploaded to Sketch Engine and automatically compiled. The alignment was checked manually, and – where texts were not correctly aligned – the files were checked, cleaned and re-aligned.

5. Results

5.1. People (lemma)

The first step involved searching for the lemma *people* in source and the equivalents in target texts. In the vast majority of cases, synonymy was used (see Table 1), including such solutions as *człowiek/ludzie* (lemma denoting singular ‘human’ and plural ‘people’), *osoba/osoby* (‘person/s’), *homo sapiens*, *ludność* (‘population of people’). The cases of hyponymy involved using more specific categories *mieszkańcy* (‘inhabitants’), *badacze* (‘researchers’), *strażacy* (‘fire-fighters’).

Table 1: Strategies used for translating the lemma *people*

Strategy	Number of occurrences
Synonymy	137
Hyponymy	21
Explicitness change – implicitation	17
Transposition	10
Abstraction change	1
Total	186

There were 17 cases of explicitness change towards implicitation consisting of only implying humans or even omitting them. However, they seem to be motivated by style choices rather than the tendency to conceal human participation in the discussed situations or phenomena:

- (1) ST: The type of lateralization **most familiar to people** is undoubtedly handedness.
 TT: **Najbardziej znanym** przejawem lateralizacji mózgu jest bez wątpienia preferencja w użyciu jednej z rąk.
 ('**The most well-known** manifestation of brain lateralization is undoubtedly the preference for using one hand.')

These shifts can be attributed to a preference for more abstract and impersonal forms, particularly in explanatory contexts, the use of which results in reducing overt references to human participants without altering the propositional content or deliberately manipulating human visibility. One of the ways in which explicitness change can be achieved is through sentence structure change involving the use of the passive voice and impersonal forms, which was found in 4 occurrences. For instance:

- (2) ST: **people widely considered them** to be tall tales
 TT: relacje na ten temat **długo uważano** za wykwit marynarskiej fantazji
 ('the reports on this subject **have long been regarded** as a resurgence of nautical fantasy')

Such changes are not obligatory, i.e. they do not seem to be dictated by pragmalinguistic conventions: The translator could have formulated the sentence with a personal active form (*ludzie uważali*, an equivalent of *people considered*) but chose the impersonal form.

A similar effect of implicitation is achieved through clause structure change involving the use of an impersonal form – the defective verb *można* ('one can') + infinitive in 1 target text:

- (3) ST: extinct florals that **people could smell** while meditating
 TT: wymarłych kwiatów, które **można by wąchać**, medytując
 ('extinct flowers, **which could be smelled** while meditating')

Transposition mainly involved translating *people* into various forms of pronouns like *my* ('we', 4 occurrences) or *ci/tych* ('these'/'those', 4 occurrences). The lexeme *people* occurs 186 times in the corpus, and, as we will see in the sections below, there are more lexemes that are synonymous.

Replacing lexical items that denote *people* with pronouns may potentially affect the visibility of the human element. However, in the occurrences found in the corpus, the equivalent of the first-person plural form *we* is used to denote all humans, explicitly excluding non-human beings, while the equivalent of *they/those* is employed primarily as a strategy to produce concise and natural-sounding sentences in Polish rather than to obscure human reference. See example 4 below.

(4) ST: the **number of people who reach the finish line** has been going down

TT: spada **liczba tych, którzy docierają do mety**
(**'the number of those who reach the finish line is declining'**)

We know that the mere fact of mentioning people does not indicate an anthropocentric perspective. But the fact that people are mentioned much more frequently than any other species can imply centering on the human aspect. Nevertheless, the translation of the lexeme *people* does not point to any shifts in perceived anthropocentrism or human exceptionalism; the use of transposition and implicitation did not alter the anthropocentric effect. It is worth stressing, however, that explicitness changes and transposition may affect the way in which the human–environment relationship is reflected in a translated text. Section 5.2 presents cases in which such translation shifts obscure or emphasize human impact on nature.

5.2. Human (lemma, noun)

Table 2: Strategies used for translating the lemma human – noun

Strategy	Number of occurrences
Synonymy	127
Transposition	20
Explicitness change – implicitation	13
Hyponymy	6
Total	166

In the case of *human*, there were separate queries for *human* as noun and as an adjective. For the noun, the equivalents used included mainly synonyms *człowiek/ludzie* ('human'/'people', 124 occurrences) and single occurrences of *istota ludzka* ('human being') and *homo sapiens*. The transpositions mainly involved using the pronoun *my* ('we') to translate the lexeme *human*. This strategy can help avoid lexical repetition in the target text, but it may also implicitly reinforce a human–animal dichotomy and perpetuate an us–them opposition. See example 5 below.

- (5) ST: the findings hint at the pest-deterrent **services bats may offer humans**.
TT: odkrycia te są wskazówką, że być może i **my moglibyśmy skorzystać z usług nietoperzy**.
(‘the findings are a clue that perhaps **we, too, could benefit from the services of bats.**’)

There were 13 cases of explicitness change (see Table 2) – towards implicitation, for example:

- (6) ST: The findings, published in 2019 and 2020, revealed a clear path for how **humans could enhance the reactions**.
TT: Wyniki tego projektu, opublikowane w latach 2019 i 2020, wskazały jasno, w **jaki sposób można by zwiększyć intensywność reakcji** chemicznych
(‘The results of this project, published in 2019 and 2020, clearly indicated how **the intensity of chemical reactions could be increased.**’)

What is particularly interesting is that, in 4 cases, implicitation is used while discussing the human impact on the environment:

- (7) ST: A cinnamon-breasted sandpiper that is declining rapidly **as humans overharvest** the horseshoe crabs
TT: Liczebność tych pięknie ubarwionych bekasowatych szybko maleje **z powodu odławiania** na masową skalę skrzyploczy
(‘The numbers of these beautifully colored sandpipers are rapidly declining due to the **mass trapping** of horseshoe crabs’)
- (8) ST: conditions along these mammal pathways, including routes through **land used by humans for homes, crops, forestry or livestock**
TT: warunki wzdłuż takich stref tranzytowych są dla zwierząt rzeczywiście korzystne – w tym celu sprawdzano m.in. **lokalizację domów, pól uprawnych, pastwisk czy lasów**
(‘conditions along such transit zones are really favorable for animals – for this purpose, **the location of homes, cultivated fields, pastures forests and other factors were checked**’)
- (9) ST: Historically ignored **because of its paucity of fossil fuels for humans to exploit**
TT: Choć często ignorowane, jako pozbawione paliw kopalnych, **które można by wydobywać**
(‘Although often ignored **as lacking fossil fuels that could be extracted**’)
- (10) ST: the myriad other **stressors generated by humans**
TT: niezliczone **inne czynniki wywołujące stres**
(‘countless **other factors inducing stress**’)

The examples above illustrate the use of an impersonal form with a defective verb (9) and changing from passive into the active gerund form (10). Those changes are not obligatory, i.e. the human agency could be made as explicit as it is indicated in STs. Their effect can be described as blurring anthropogenic factors of environmental depletion: The party responsible for trapping crabs, extracting fossil fuels and inducing environmental stress is not directly identified. Is that indicative of anthropocentrism? It definitely does not point to an ecocentric approach.

In the results of the query for humans, the phrase *we/us humans* occurred 7 times. It is an emphatic phrase signaling that the author stresses that they and the readers belong to the same biological species referred to in articles discussing exceptional human features or the group responsible for environmental changes. The phrase is translated with the equivalent of *we (us) humans (my, ludzie)*, *humans (ludzie)* or *us (nas)*. However, the number of occurrences is too small to make valid comments on the distribution of solutions.

5.3. Człowiek (lemma)

In the reverse search, when the Polish corpus was searched for the lemma *człowiek* ('man', 'human') to identify the source units, it transpired that the target *człowiek* (351 occurrences) corresponded to the sources *human* (191 occurrences), *people* (99 occurrences), *person* (5 occurrences), *man* (5 occurrences) and pronouns (10 occurrences). There were altogether 41 cases of explicitness change towards explicitation, i.e. the human element was just implied in the source and is explicitly referred to in the target texts. Humans are mentioned as ecosystem participants, as in example 11 below, which mentions the coexistence of humans and wild plants and animals. Humans are also occasionally named as the party responsible for environmental depletion (altogether 4 occurrences), see example 12 below, in which the passive construction "its habitat was razed" is translated with the use of an equivalent of "humans significantly reduced their habitat".

- (11) ST: more creative means of **coexisting alongside wild plants and animals**.
TT: bardziej kreatywnego podejścia do kwestii **współegzystencji ludzi oraz dzikich roślin i zwierząt**.
(‘a more creative approach to the **coexistence of humans and wild plants and animals**’)
- (12) ST: even as much of **its habitat was razed** to make room for pineapple plantations
TT: mimo że **ludzie znacznie zredukowali ich siedlisko**, by zrobić miejsce dla plantacji ananasów wydobywających ropę naftową oraz luksusowych osiedli mieszkaniowych.
(‘even though **humans significantly reduced their habitat** to make room for pineapple plantations’)

That means that the corpus shows competing approaches – making human agency more explicit as in example (12) above as opposed to blurring this agency, as shown in the previous section. The use of explicitation could also be interpreted as a form of compensation for implicitation (including 17 cases of implicitation of *people*, and 13 of the noun *human*). However, since it is not known whether the texts were translated by the same translator, this

interpretation remains hypothetical. The tension in translating the relationship between humans and the environment that they shape to suit their needs may be indicative of the potential range of approaches to the man vs. nature dichotomy and its anthropocentric aspect.

5.4. Including humans

An interesting additional observation was made concerning the category of humans while exploring the translations of the phrase *including humans* for instance in “animals, including humans”, “tetrapods including humans”, “creatures, apes, organisms including humans”, which emphasize that people are a part of the animal kingdom. Out of 8 occurrences of *including humans (people)*, 6 were translated as *w tym (także) człowieka/ludzi/ludziom* (‘including [also] human/people’ [2 declension forms]) (see example 13). In one example, the distance between humans and other animals was increased and people were presented as separate from the animal kingdom (see example 15). In one case, the classification of humans within the tetrapod category became less explicit (see example 14). It illustrates a certain tension surrounding references to humans as part of the animal kingdom and the challenges of overcoming human exceptionalism.

- (13) ST: more than 33,800 species of tetrapods alive today, **including humans**.
 TT: ponad 33 800 gatunków, **w tym także u człowieka**.
 (‘over 33,800 species, **(also) including humans.**’)
- (14) ST: we can reconstruct how the basic plan for **the hands of tetrapods, including humans**, originated.
 TT: możemy rekonstruować drogę prowadzącą od płetw mięśniopłetwych **do rąk tetrapodów**.
 (‘we can reconstruct the pathway leading from muscular fins to **tetrapod hands.**’)
- (15) ST: Two other forms of play have only been documented in great apes, **including humans**.
 TT: Dwa inne rodzaje zabaw udało się dotychczas zaobserwować jedynie u wielkich **małp i – oczywiście – także u ludzi**.
 (‘Two other types of play have so far been observed only in great apes and, **of course, in humans as well.**’)

5.5. Human (lemma, adjective)

Table 3: Strategies used for translating the lemma human – adjective

Strategy	Number of occurrences
Synonymy	44
Transposition	90
Explicitness change – implicitation	5
Hyponymy	1
Total	140

There are 140 occurrences of the adjective *human* in the corpus, and they are most frequently translated with the use of the adjective *ludzki*. It is translated by transposition (90 occurrences) with the use of the noun *człowiek* ('human', 58 occurrences) or the personal pronoun *nasz* ('our') in 36 occurrences, for instance, *human brain* – *nasz mózg* ('our brain'). There are 5 cases of implicitation, for instance, *human perception* – *percepcja* ('perception'). There is only one case of hyponymy (see Table 3).

5.6. Nonhuman animals

There were 9 occurrences of *nonhuman* including 1 instance referring to artifacts ("nonhuman artifacts" – "not made by human hands"). The remaining occurrences refer to monkeys, primates, animals, and – broadly – members of communities inhabiting sacred groves ("community members who are not humans", example 17). When *nonhuman* refers to animals other than humans (8 occurrences) that belong to the same groups as humans (apes, primates, animals), the inclusion of humans within other zoological categories is not reflected in 3 target excerpts where *nonhuman animals* is translated as *animals* (see example 16 below). *Nonhuman primates* appears twice: once translated as *primates (naczelnych)*, and once as *primates, excluding humans (naczelnych, poza człowiekiem)*, example 18). There is one instance of translation of *nonhuman animals* as *our animal relatives and cousins (naszych zwierzęcych krewnych i kuzynów)*, and one instance of translating *nonhuman apes* into a less transparent and more technical term *małpy człekokształtne* ('Hominoidea'). It is also worth noting that the superfamily of Hominoidea, the family Hominidae (hominids), includes humans, as well as gorillas and orangutans (Britannica 2026). To sum up, in 4 cases, the *nonhuman* element was completely omitted, thus foregoing the emphasis on humans belonging to the animal kingdom. In other cases, we observe more or less complex strategies to convey the sense of "nonhuman".

(16) ST: Are **nonhuman animals** as good as we are at evaluating rivals?

TT: Czy **zwierzęta** są w tym równie dobre?
Are **animals** equally good at this?

(17) ST: These **nonhuman community members** benefit them in many ways;

TT: Ci **przedstawiciele wspólnoty, którzy nie są ludźmi**, przynoszą nam rozmaite korzyści;
(‘Those **members of the community who are not human** bring us various benefits;’)

(18) ST: we now have archaeological records for three **nonhuman primate lineages**.

TT: dysponujemy zapisem archeologicznym dotyczącym ewolucji technicznej trzech odrębnych **linii naczelnych, poza człowiekiem**.
(‘we have an archaeological record of the technical evolution of three distinct **primate lineages, apart from humans**.’)

Interestingly enough, in the corpus of Polish-language internet texts in Sketch Engine (pITenTen19, 4,253,636,443 words) from 2019, we can find the phrase *zwierzęta pozaludzkie* ('beyond-human animals') – a direct equivalent of *nonhuman animals* – 19 times (in 7 sources). It needs to be noted that, on the one hand, dividing animals into human and nonhuman acknowledges the fact that people are a part of the animal kingdom, and on the other hand, reinforces the human-animal dichotomy.

5.7. *Man, person*

The source units *man* and *person* were also included in the explorations. The noun *man* has 18 occurrences, including 15 denoting human males and only 3 times referring to all the people, and then it is translated as *człowiek/ludzie* ('human'/'people'). The word *mężczyzna* ('man', understood as a human male) is used 10 times. The remaining cases are translated by transposition (pronouns), hyponymy and explicitness change (implication). *Person* occurs 21 times, 9 of which are translated as *osoba* ('person'), 5 as *człowiek/ludzie* ('human'/'people'), and the remaining ones are translated by explicitness change (implication) and hyponymy.

6. Discussion

This study focused on the lexical units used to classify the categories of “human”, “animal” and “nonhuman”. The starting point for the study was an initial screening of the corpus, which showed a relatively high frequency of human-referencing lexemes and suggested a potential anthropocentric perspective. This observation informed the subsequent analytical steps focusing on human categories and possible shifts in the representation of the human-nature relationship. In order to shed light on the potential anthropocentric orientation of the texts in the analyzed corpus, the frequencies of the most prominent human-related lemmas are presented in Table 4. The lemmas *human* (noun) and *people* occur more frequently in the English source texts of the focus corpus than in the English reference corpus (1,632.5 vs. 1,192.29 occurrences per million tokens). Similarly, the lemma *człowiek* (equivalent of *human* and *man*) occurs more frequently in the focus corpus than in the reference corpus. However, these findings only indicate a potential tendency and do not in themselves demonstrate an anthropocentric bias. Rather, they show that references to humans occur more frequently in the focus corpus.

Table 4. Frequency of human-referencing lemmas in the focus corpus and reference corpora

Lemma	Frequency in the focus corpus (per million tokens)	Frequency in the reference corpora (per million tokens)
<i>Human</i> (noun)	769.9	84.18
<i>People</i>	862.6	1,108.11
<i>Człowiek/ludzie</i> (equivalents of <i>human/people</i>)	1725.77	1,080.45

The context of the study is the tension between overcoming and reinforcing anthropocentrism and human exceptionalism in texts about nature. The observations made in this study indicate that when translating human categories, translators usually choose equivalent synonyms, which produce a similar effect with respect to how people are referred to.

In a smaller but still considerable number of cases, the human element is made more or less visible or obvious through explicitness change. This can have a number of consequences. Firstly, humans can be depicted and perceived as the “default” creatures (e.g. *human gut – jelita* [‘intestines’]). Those changes are not related to pragmalinguistic conventions and can be treated as shifts between covert and overt anthropocentrism. What is more, human participation in environmental processes may be obscured. This applies to destructive activities (*other stressors generated by humans – inne czynniki wywołujące stress* [‘other factors inducing stress’]) but it may also serve to acknowledge the simple fact that humans are part of the natural world. As presented in the sections above, in the analyzed corpus, explicitation is used slightly more often than implicitation (41 vs. 38, respectively), which may be considered consistent with the explicitation hypothesis, according to which translators tend to make implicit information in the source text more explicit in the target text (Blum-Kulka 1986). Changes in human visibility can be the result of changing sentence structure into passive. Changes related to transitivity structures may reflect the translator’s communicative intentions and they guide the readers to perceive, in this case, environmental changes from a particular perspective, which can suggest certain ideological implications (Hu and Li 2019). It is worth noting that there are also changes resulting in increased visibility and emphasized responsibility of humans (e.g. *habitat was razed – ludzie zredukowali ich siedlisko* [‘people reduced their habitat’]). With regard to the visibility of the human agency and human impact on the natural environment, the findings are evenly distributed: Human influence is obscured in translation in four cases, and it is emphasized in four cases in the segments containing the studied lexemes. Even though the effect achieved does not necessarily need to result from translators’ personal ideologies, anthropocentric – or, conversely – ecocentric overtones may be added or removed in translation.²

Another noteworthy finding concerns phrases such as *nonhuman animals* or *animals including humans* which are translated either in a way that conveys the fact that the homo sapiens species belongs to the *Animalia* kingdom or in a way that moves humans away from other animals – even though such occurrences were not frequent in the corpus, their presence signals that the relationship between people and other animals can be a translation problem. This problem is also seen in such translations as: *we humans are clearly the odd ape out – ludzie są na tle swoich bliskich biologicznych kuzynów bardzo nietypowymi stworzeniami* [‘humans are very atypical creatures compared to their close biological cousins’], where the explicit reference to humans as apes is replaced by a more general and less taxonomically precise description. On the one hand, this shift obscures the biological continuity between humans and other primates, on the other hand, it still recognizes that a connection exists between those groups.

The study may be deemed anthropocentric in nature since it focuses on human categories, but it seems important to note and raise awareness to the categories that we use when we talk about humans and (other) animals, especially when we refer to them collectively or when we compare humans to other species. This challenge is explained by Ted Toadvine:

² See also Karwacka (2025c) for a discussion of the results of this study and a continuation of research into anthropocentric and ecocentric overtones in translation.

“Since the drawing of the distinction between humans and other animals concerns the constitution of our own identities, it has been acknowledged that the drawing of this distinction is not – nor can it be – an entirely neutral or objective matter” (Toadvine 2007: 40). Nevertheless, it seems to be worth the effort as it may shed light on the language we use to refer to the coexistence of humans and animals in a world essentially dominated by humans (cf. Cronin 2017: 116).

7. Limitations

This study was conducted on a relatively small corpus in one language pair, so its conclusions are limited to this pair only, and should be treated as the findings of a corpus-informed qualitative study. The categories chosen for the analysis, though not yielding revolutionary observations, still offer some understanding of how translators approach the human-nature relationship in popularizations. Acknowledging these limitations, future research could build upon these findings by exploring additional categories or employing different methodologies.

8. Conclusion

This study concerned tracing human exceptionalism in popularization articles devoted to environmental problems and their translations by analyzing source and target lexical units referring to humans and animals. The results show that the way in which a source text conveys human relationship to other animals or the environment is usually also reflected in target texts, but there are also occasional shifts in the perceived human-nature relationship, with infrequent overtones of human exceptionalism, in most cases, resulting from explicitness change occasionally accompanied by sentence structure change. Such shifts may but do not have to be motivated by translators’ personal ideologies. Whether this bias is conscious or not, its presence in the translation process may affect the way in which the problems addressed in the articles are perceived by the readers, as they may, for instance, be less aware of the human impact on the natural world.

References

- Bertels, Ann. 2022. Chapter 14. Terminology and distributional analysis of corpora. In Faber, Pamela & L’Homme, Marie-Claude (eds.), *Terminology and lexicography research and practice*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company. 311–28. doi: 10.1075/tlrp.23.14ber.
- Blum-Kulka, Shoshana. 1986. Shifts of cohesion and coherence in translation. *Interlingual and Intercultural Communication. Discourse and Cognition in Translation and Second Language Acquisition Studies* 17: 35.
- Bołtuć, Marta. 2015. Lost in translation. Popular science genre as a mediation between American and Polish culture – the case study of National Geographic. *Zeszyty Naukowe. Organizacja i Zarządzanie/Politechnika Śląska* 84: 9–26.
- Britannica Editors. 2026. Hominidae. Encyclopedia Britannica. (<https://www.britannica.com/animal/Hominidae>) (Accessed 2026-05-15).

- Calsamiglia, Helena & Van Dijk, Teun A. 2004. Popularization discourse and knowledge about the genome. *Discourse & Society* 15(4): 369–89. doi: 10.1177/0957926504043705.
- Chesterman, Andrew. 2016. *Memes of translation. The spread of ideas in translation history*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company. doi: 10.1075/btl.123.
- Condamines, Anne & Picton, Aurélie. 2022. Chapter 10. Textual terminology. Origins, principles and new challenges. In Faber, Pamela & L’Homme, Marie-Claude (eds.), *Terminology and lexicography research and practice*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins Publishing Company. 219–36. doi: 10.1075/tlrp.23.10con.
- Cook, Guy & Sealey, Alison. 2018. The discursive representation of animals. In *The Routledge handbook of ecolinguistics*. Abingdon/New York: Routledge. 311–24.
- Corpas Pastor, Gloria & Seghiri Domínguez, Míriam. 2010. Size matters. A quantitative approach to corpus representativeness. In Rabadán, Rosa & Fernández López, Marisa & Guzmán González, Trinidad (eds.), *Lengua, traducción, recepción en honor de Julio César Santoyo*. León: Universidad de León Área de Publicaciones. 111–45.
- Cronin, Michael. 2017. *Eco-translation. Translation and ecology in the age of the Anthropocene*. Abingdon/New York: Routledge.
- Dasca, Maria & Cerarols Ramírez, Rosa (eds.). 2024. *Translation studies and ecology. Mapping the possibilities of a new emerging field*. Abingdon/New York: Routledge.
- Dean, Dorothy C. 2021. ‘At home on the earth’. Toward a theology of human non-exceptionalism. *Journal for the Study of Religion, Nature and Culture* 14(4): 480–95. doi: 10.1558/jsrnc.40899.
- Desblache, Lucile. 2020. Translation, natural history and music. Communication beyond the verbal. In Taivalkoski-Shilov, Kristiina & Poncharal, Bruno (eds.), *Traduire Les Voix de La Nature / Translating the Voices of Nature*. Montréal: Éditions québécoises de l’oeuvre. 207–29.
- Droz, Laÿna. 2022. Anthropocentrism as the scapegoat of the environmental crisis. A review. *Ethics in Science and Environmental Politics* 22: 25–49. doi: 10.3354/esepp00200.
- Goralnik, Lissy & Nelson, Michael P. 2012. Anthropocentrism. In Chadwick, Ruth (ed.), *Encyclopedia of applied ethics*. Elsevier. 145–55. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-373932-2.00349-5.
- Heuberger, Reinhard. 2003. Anthropocentrism in monolingual English dictionaries. An ecolinguistic approach to the lexicographic treatment of faunal terminology. *AAA. Arbeiten aus Anglistik und Amerikanistik* 28(1): 93–105.
- Hu, Kaibao & Li, Xiaoqian. 2019. Corpus-based critical translation studies. Research areas and approaches. *Meta* 63(3): 583–603. doi: 10.7202/1060164ar.
- Karwacka, Wioleta. 2020. Assessing shifts in animal intentionality and anthropomorphism in the translation of popular science texts from English into Polish. In Taivalkoski-Shilov, Kristiina & Poncharal, Bruno (eds.), *Traduire Les Voix de La Nature / Translating the Voices of Nature*. Montréal: Éditions québécoises de l’oeuvre. 183–206.
- Karwacka, Wioleta. 2025a. COVID-related terms in translated popular scientific articles. A case study on term variation. *Topics in Linguistics* 26(1): 68–91. doi: 10.17846/topling-2025-0004.
- Karwacka, Wioleta. 2025b. *Greenhouse effect, global warming and climate change* in popular science articles – a corpus-informed study of term variation in translation. *The Translator* 31(3): 290–308. doi: 10.1080/13556509.2025.2505342.

- Karwacka, Wioleta. 2025c. Człowiek środowisko i język: spojrzenie ekolingwistyczne na przekład tekstów popularnonaukowych. Gdańsk: Wydawnictwo Uniwersytetu Gdańskiego.
- Kilgarriff, Adam & Baisa, Vít & Bušta, Jan & Jakubiček, Miloš & Kovář, Vojtěch & Michelfeit, Jan & Rychlý, Pavel & Suchomel, Vít. 2014. The Sketch Engine. Ten years on. *Lexicography* 1: 7–36.
- Kilgarriff, Adam & Rychlý, Pavel & Smrž, Pavel & Tugwell, David. 2004. The Sketch Engine. *Proceedings of the 11th EURALEX International Congress*. 105–16.
- Kirby, Vicki. 2014. Human exceptionalism on the line. *SubStance. A Review of Theory and Literary Criticism* 43(2 [134]): 50–67. doi: 10.1353/sub.2014.0028.
- Kopnina, Helen & Washington, Haydn & Taylor, Bron & Piccolo, John J. 2018. Anthropocentrism. More than just a misunderstood problem. *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics* 31(1): 109–27. doi: 10.1007/s10806-018-9711-1.
- Merleau-Ponty, Maurice & Ségлар, Dominique. 2003. *Nature. Course Notes from the Collège de France*. Evanston: Northwestern University Press.
- Midgley, Mary. 2005. *The myths we live by*. Abingdon/New York: Routledge.
- Sealey, Alison. 2019. Translation. A biosemiotic/more-than-human perspective. *Target. International Journal of Translation Studies* 31(3): 305–27. doi: 10.1075/target.18099.sea.
- Sealey, Alison & Oakley, Lee. 2014. Why did the Canada goose cross the sea? Accounting for the behaviour of wildlife in the documentary series *Life*. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics* 24(1): 19–37. doi: 10.1111/ijal.12007.
- Taivalkoski-Shilov, Kristiina. 2020. Increasing ecological awareness in translation studies. A voice-based perspective. In Taivalkoski-Shilov, Kristiina & Poncharal, Bruno (eds.), *Traduire Les Voix de La Nature / Translating the Voices of Nature*. Montréal: Éditions québécoises de l'oeuvre. 3–24.
- Toadvine, Ted. 2007. How not to be a jellyfish. Human exceptionalism and the ontology of reflection. In Painter, Corinne & Lotz, Christian (eds.), *Phenomenology and the non-human animal*. Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands. 39–55. doi: 10.1007/978-1-4020-6307-7_4.
- Wang, Quan. 2023. Translating nonhuman agency. *New Voices in Translation Studies* 28: 159180. doi: 10.14456/NVTS.2023.8.
- Washington, Haydn & Piccolo, John & Gomez-Baggethun, Erik & Kopnina, Helen & Alberro, Heather. 2021. The trouble with anthropocentric hubris, with examples from conservation. *Conservation* 1(4): 285–98. doi: 10.3390/conservation1040022.
- Watson, Todd, R. 2001. Building and using your own corpus and concordance. *ThaiTESOL Bulletin* 14(2).

Wioleta Karwacka
 Instytut Anglistyki i Amerykanistyki
 Wydział Filologiczny Uniwersytetu Gdańskiego
 ul. Wita Stwosza 51, 80-308 Gdańsk
 Poland
 e-mail: wioleta.karwacka@ug.edu.pl

Bridging the Sacred: Communicative Efficacy in Modern Translations of John through Relevance Theory

Sarah Mariam Roy, Woxsen University

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to explore the communicative efficacy in contemporary translations of the Gospel According to John (Chapters 1–3) using Gutt’s relevance theory, a framework that views translation as interlingual interpretation. By analysing three English translations—the New International Version (NIV), English Standard Version (ESV), and The Message—the study explores each version’s effectiveness in conveying the original text’s intent to modern audiences. Relevance theory, with its focus on cognitive environments and secondary communication, provides a structured approach for comparing how each translation adapts John’s message to diverse reader contexts. This research outlines the evolution of Bible translations from author-focused to audience-centred approaches, revealing how sociocultural relevance drives new interpretations. Through a communicative lens, the analysis contrasts the Greek original with its English counterparts, examining differences in stimulus, cognitive environment, and interpretation. The study illustrates how relevance theory can serve as a cohesive framework for understanding translation philosophy and demonstrates the importance of aligning sacred texts with contemporary linguistic and cultural settings.

Keywords: *Relevance theory, translation studies, communication analysis*

1. Introduction

The Bible has been translated into different languages from the original languages of Hebrew, Aramaic and Greek. Bible translations have a long and complex history shaped by linguistic, cultural, and theological developments. The present study investigates the relevance of communication in the art and practice of translation. Bible translations are perpetually growing with the increasing number of new translations and because of the new words added into language at regular intervals. These translations claim in their prefaces to be more communicative and faithful. There is a lack of standard assessing methodologies, which provides the impetus for this research. Therefore, Ernst-August Gutt’s relevance theory is a communication-based translation theory applied in this research to select translations of the Bible as the primary texts (Gutt 2014: 65). The present paper focuses on comparing, analysing and assessing the three different translations of the Gospel According to John (henceforth John). The three translations used in this study are the *English Standard Version* (2016), the *New International Version* (2011) and *The Message: The Bible in Contemporary Language* (2002) (hereafter referred to as *The Message*).

Translation as a communicative act has to be primarily understood beyond its linguistic aspects alone (Gutt 2014: 68). Each text is produced within a cognitive environment and even more so while producing a translation. The original interpretation can be produced only when the translation process involves the transmission of the contextual information that was a part of the cognitive environment of the original audience: It is pertinent to accept that in translation “texts travel across time, space and different orders of indexicality” and must therefore be

“re-contextualized” (House 2015: 4). The translation of a text is a process of communication of meaning to trace the original tone and intent of a message.

Relevance is the field in which a translator identifies and negotiates the communication struggles concerning form and content. When different translation methodologies are applied, various translations of the same text are born. Susan Bassett (2002: 33) has rightly observed that “if a dozen translators tackle the same poem, they will produce a dozen different versions.”

1.1 The Gospel According to John

The Gospel According to John (Εὐαγγέλιον κατὰ Ἰωάννην) is one of the four canonical gospels in the Bible. It carries a structured account of the ministry of Jesus. The concluding verses set out the purpose of the text, “that you may believe that Jesus is the Christ, the Son of God, and that believing you may have life in his name” (John 20:31). Scholars believe that John reached its final form around AD 90–110, although it contains signs of origins even dating back to AD 70 (Brown 1988: 7). Like the three other gospels, it is anonymous, although it identifies an unnamed “disciple whom Jesus loved” (John 21:7) as the source of its traditions. Scholars such as Tasker consider that a Johannine community existed as the text is closely related to the three Johannine epistles in style and content. It is a stylistic and thematic match for the three Johannine epistles and, along with the Book of Revelation, is treated by most scholars as one body of Johannine literature. (Brown 1988: 78). John has also been studied for its historical and philosophical contributions in different cultures (Kanagaraj & Kemp 2002: 7). In such a context, the Gospel According to John is an appropriate choice. As John is an ancient text dating back to AD 90–110 (Tasker 1960: 5), the different possibilities of translating an ancient text for contemporary readers – whether academic, liturgical, devotional, or general readerships – may be analysed. As a text, John, according to scholars, belongs to different genres with poetic portions, discourse, biographical accounts and first-person narratives (Marshall 2006: 200). Hence, there is ample scope for analysing different aspects of the text in translation. Also, John has different kinds of audiences today, some with aesthetic intention, some on historical scholarship and others for devotional reading (Köstenberger 2003: 350). Even though it belongs to the gospel genre, it is widely claimed to be different from the other three gospels, which are referred to as the Synoptic gospels due to their similarity in content (Tasker 1960: 18). Hence within the Bible itself, John stands out for its peculiar qualities of narration, language diction and vocabulary. These features make the text particularly suitable for analysing how translators negotiate style, symbolism, and key theological terminology. The text is thus selected for its ancient origin, and for its wide readership and subsequently the variety of translations available.

1.2 Literature review

Translation studies has developed through key phases: early linguistic theories (1950s–60s), cultural and functionalist turns (1970s–90s), and cognitive, technological, and sociological approaches in the 21st century. Research on translations generally investigates translated texts on different levels and of different kinds. Linguistic aspects of translation, corpus studies of translation, descriptive-historical studies and analysis of think-aloud protocols are some of the critical areas of research in translation studies. It calls for a re-definition of the theory and understanding of the phenomenon of translation. Translation analysis applies different theoretical frames or approaches such as subjective, hermeneutic, descriptive, postcolonial,

poststructuralist, postmodern, literal and discourse-based approaches on translated texts. Cognitive and corpus-based approaches now play a significant role (Saldanha & O'Brien 2014: 10). Various interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary interpretive perspectives are also applied to translation studies. Translation research takes the form of investigating the process involved and the translator's role from other disciplines ranging from the historical, socio-cultural and descriptive studies of actual translation products. Such studies also consider the synchronic and diachronic temporal dimensions and the inter-cultural context present in translations. Unlike the research on merely linguistic attributes, which lead only to general observations, contemporary research focuses on employing a particular frame in the larger frame of reference. These developments mark a shift from purely linguistic equivalence to functional, cultural, and cognitive models of translation. Such research investigations are systematic and have a self-reflexive nature in future translation research such as embracing the "thoroughly diverse branches of the social sciences and natural sciences, particularly the biological sciences and technical aspects of cognitive science" (Tymoczko 2005: 1089).

Within this historical development, Eugene Nida's work in the 1960s introduced functional and formal equivalence, an important early foundation for Bible translation theory. A range of Bible versions like the Good News Bible (GNB), which follows functional equivalence, and the New American Standard Bible (NASB), which follows formal equivalence, are available. The discussion on their relative merit is more or less a scientific accommodation of a 20th-century revision of the age-old free/literal dichotomy under discussion since ancient translators such as ST. Jerome and Cicero (Gutt 2014: 18)

The paradigm shift (Doty 2007: 6) Gutt brought about in translation studies was by applying relevance theory (originally forwarded by Sperber and Wilson in human communication) to translation theory (Sperber & Wilson 1986: 15). Relevance theory is based on the inferential model of communication and forwarded by H. P. Grice (1991: 13), and the focus is on translation as an interlingual interpretive use (Gutt 2014: 105). It originated in the 1980s (Sperber & Wilson 1986) and later entered Bible translation discussions through Gutt. It consciously differed from dynamic equivalence translation by reproducing not the meaning but the conditions for original interpretation – the stimulus, the cognitive environment and the communicative principle of relevance theory (Gutt 2014: 105). The identification and addressing of cognitive processes have led to inference-led interpretation. Gutt considers this a pre-requisite in the task of translation. Research in such a dimension results in the formulation of successful communication in translation. It also results in building a communicative paradigm for analysis.

In the relevance theory approach, the same stimulus can elicit a range of contextual assumptions which are more or less accessible, and the same cognitive effects can be more or less easily derived. In such a situation, the translator faces a conflict, i.e. the greater the effort of inference called for, the less rewarding the input will be to process. On the other hand, the less processing effort required, the more input processed and the greater the positive cognitive benefits derived from processing an input, the more relevant the input is to the individual. Relevance is, therefore, a comparative notion which cannot be quantified (Gutt 2014: 31).

Relevance theory considers translation an intentional act of communication. This model provides a sufficient framework for understanding the cognitive process in translation. The analysis of expectations and inferences in the formation of interpretation is also addressed. Relevance is assessed according to the cognitive and communicative principle of relevance. This is done by identifying the processing effort, the contextual implications, the strength of implicatures and the resultant interpretations. Research in translation must analyse the

possibilities of cognitive processes in order to influence future translation processes. This is rightly pointed out by Van Der Henst & Sperber (2004: 239):

The human tendency to maximise relevance makes it possible not only to predict some of the other people's cognitive processes but also to try to influence them—how indeed could you aim at influencing people if you had no way to predict how your behaviour would affect their thought?

Kevin Gary Smith (2000: 95–96) has proposed a practical and critical study of Gutt's approach of direct and indirect translation while addressing specific translation issues of figurative language, implicit information, ambiguity and gender-biased language. He discusses how supplementary material may assist readers, bridge the contextual gap between the source context and the receptor context by providing illustrations/footnotes in a direct translation or by explicating implicit information in an indirect translation.

On a different note, Harriet Hill (2006: 12) has applied relevance theory in a comparative study in which three versions of selected Bible passages were tested in the Adioukrou language of Ivory Coast. The first translation was only the text without footnotes or any background information. The second translation had extensive footnotes providing background information needed to understand the passages. The third was a translation with footnotes in which all the background information in the footnotes was woven into the text. These translations were then given to the local community. In the study conducted, the readers were asked to answer the questions about each of the three translations. The results implied that the footnoted version and the adaptation were more communicative than the first translation. Thus, context plays a vital role in communication using footnotes. It was concluded in the study that with proper awareness, unsophisticated readers could also obtain information from footnotes.

Stephen Doty, in his research, designed a test to examine how clear and intelligible translations are to an average Thai reader. These included a literal translation, a functional equivalence translation and a meaning-based translation. Three different stories from the Bible were tested using multiple choice questions. The questions were objective and allowed statistical evaluation and comparison of the three types of translations. The research findings provide considerable evidence about the limitations of not providing contextual information to its readers. The results reveal the effectiveness of a meaning-based translation to be higher than that of a literal translation. Thus, it emphasizes the need for additional material with each translation. According to Doty (2007: 85), “the need for supplementary materials to assist new Bible readers to understand the message is apparent.”

Hill and Doty have used different types of translations in order to assess the comprehension of the readers. The focus was on the response of the audience to different translations. The relevance of supplementary material was underlined by Doty (2007: 85). Hill (2006: 103) contends that such supplementary material supported by footnotes, when incorporated into the text, leads the reader to understand better the context. As observed earlier, Smith (2000: 178–89) used the theoretical construct of direct and indirect translation proposed by Gutt as a framework for practical application.

Similarly, Sang Zhonggang has researched translating implicit information using relevance theory. In literary translation, the translator is confronted with a large volume of implicit information whose features (graded communicability, context-dependence, the relation between the implicit information, text and context, etc.) (Zhonggang 2006: 45) limit

the communicability of literary texts in another context, so the translator of literary texts faces more difficulties in the translation. Zhonggang took Gutt's theory as an approach for translating the implicit information in literary texts and experiments with constructing an explanatory framework for translating the implicit information in literary texts. The framework of Zhonggang (2006: 45) is based on the notion that translation is a "clues-based interpretive use of language across language boundaries." He agrees with Gutt's theory that the central concern for a translator is to achieve successful communication. In such a context, even when it is difficult to achieve complete interpretive resemblance to the source text, the translator needs to search for adequate relevance to maintain successful communication. The relevance of the source text to the target audience may be weakened due to the contextual and linguistic differences. In these instances, the translator should aim to interpretively make the textual properties of the target text as similar as possible to those of the source text, adjusting the similarity of each set of text structures. Hence, any layer of the literary text that could impede the principle of relevance may be adjusted to achieve the resemblance of textual properties. Zhonggang's explanatory framework for translating the implicit information in a literary text is practically presented as an effective strategy. There are studies elucidating how readers interact with onomatopoeia in digital manga and how the relevance of these expressions influences their reading behaviour (Rohan et al. 2021: 71)

Recent developments in translation studies emphasize that meaning-making in translation is shaped by multiple constraints operating simultaneously. As Marais (2023: 117) notes, communicative intent emerges within a semiotic environment, and the translator must select and constrain available resources in ways that maximize the likelihood of successful communication. Relevance theory contributes to this understanding by offering a cognitive explanation of how translators and readers manage inferencing, processing effort and contextual effects. However, contemporary scholarship positions such cognitive constraints within a broader functionalist framework. As Nord (2023: 172) argues, the *skopos* – the intended function of the translation in its target context – determines translational decisions and provides the primary criterion for assessing coherence, adequacy, and communicative appropriateness. In functionalist approaches, relevance and communicative adequacy are operationalized through the translation brief, which defines the purpose, audience, and pragmatic needs of the target community (Meylaerts & Marais 2023: 2).

Accordingly, relevance theory in this study is not treated as a competing grand theory of translation but as a complementary explanatory model that illuminates the cognitive processes underlying interpretive use, inferencing and contextualization within the functional constraints established by *skopos* and brief. This aligns with current trajectories in translation theory, where cognitive and functional approaches are understood as mutually supportive rather than mutually exclusive. The present analysis therefore uses relevance theory to examine how readers process translational stimuli and derive contextual effects, while acknowledging that the ultimate evaluative framework for translation choices remains the functionalist notions of *skopos*, coherence, and communicative adequacy.

In this sense, relevance theory is employed here not to determine translational norms but to refine the understanding of how a translation's intended effects are cognitively achieved. Functional adequacy determines *what* a translation must accomplish for its audience; relevance theory helps explain *how* the audience processes the translational stimuli in order to achieve those effects. This dual-level conceptualization is consistent with recent integrative approaches in translation studies, where cognitive accounts of inferencing and effort–effect balance are

used to support, rather than replace, functionalist principles governing translation production and evaluation.

Assessment in translation studies considers both functional adequacy and the relationship between the original text and its translation. It also evaluates the relationship between the original text, its reception, the author's voice and the translator's role. It may deal with the external aspects of a translation which are macro-contextual or internal aspects which are micro-contextual (House 2015: 5). The external aspects have a social perspective, and the internal aspects deal with the cognitive processes involved in doing a translation. There are studies dealing with variability in metaphorical motion expression in original vs. translated texts across multiple levels of analysis (target domain, source domain, metaphorical mapping) and typological contrasts (Lewandowski & Özçalışkan 2024: 25).

Relevance theory and its assessment consider the cognitive processes in translation together with its socio-cultural context. It also evaluates linguistic, pragmatic, and functional dimensions of the translation. In such a context, research on building a communicative paradigm stands relevant. The present study focuses on the contemporary English translations of the Bible and its process of communication. Gutt's relevance theory calls for a translation to be self-sufficient in providing the readers with the context, stimulus and its interaction for an interpretation.

1.3 Research on Bible translation

Research on Bible translation is generally a discourse on the theory and practice of different approaches worldwide. The Bible translation scenario until the middle of the 20th century was inclined to literal translations and “[n]obody had studied the task of Bible translation worldwide from the perspective of the receptor languages in an attempt to find solutions to the translators' dilemma” (Smalley 1955: 61). In the traditional translation model, missionaries were the primary translators, and the locals served a secondary role as “language helpers” (Ciampa 2010: 60). Earlier translation work was done by missionaries who learned the vernacular language and translated the Bible. Many of the pioneering tasks were making dictionaries and even scripts of many languages (Verghese 2014). Their concern was to develop literacy in the community. The degree of involvement of the local community in translation projects later increased significantly. This change throws light on the increasing role of the local communities in current Bible translation projects. The earlier dependency on a foreign translator is now seen as “marginalisation” (Ciampa 2010: 61) and subsequently, this has led to new translations and revisions being conducted. In recent times, the academic discussion has developed to the broader analysis of the translated text using social, cultural, linguistic, audience-related, and technological advancements.

The development of translation theories led to a phase where new translations and revisions of the Bible were undertaken. Additionally, the changing nature of languages and the need to be more communicative with the contemporary audience also motivate newer translations. Being communicative with the contemporary audience is a significant reason for multiple translations of the Bible. All translations seek to communicate the content of the text. The large variety of translations has produced a more comprehensive range of options for communicating with different readers. This provision of many translations leads to debates and discussions on communication. In such a context, a communicative paradigm for analysing translations is necessary. The objectives and application of communication are restricted to the discussions and debates in translation studies. Relevance theory is one of the

communication-based approaches to translation by Gutt. The study analyses the three English translations: NIV, ESV and The Message using the communicative paradigm on two levels: first is the cognition of the reader (Gutt 2014: 237) and second is the communication of the text (Gutt 2014: 238). Subsequently, the concept of communication is analysed in the contemporary translations of John 1–3.

Bible translation has become a global phenomenon, characterized by various methodologies that have led to numerous English translations. These translations fall into three main categories: literal, mediating, and paraphrastic – each with different degrees of adherence to their respective methods. No translation is perfect; all aim to communicate effectively with different audiences (Bell 2005: 45). Literal translations, such as the King James Version (KJV), New American Standard Bible (NASB), and English Standard Version (ESV), aim to be as close as possible to the original texts. Mediating translations, like the New International Version (NIV), balance literal accuracy with modern readability. Paraphrastic translations, including The Living Bible and The Message, adapt the text to contemporary language and idioms, making it more dynamic and accessible. The Good News Bible, for example, addresses the needs of those with lower levels of formal education, making standard translations more understandable (Bratcher 1971). This variety in translation philosophies highlights the ongoing effort to make the Bible accessible and meaningful across diverse audiences and cultures.

1.3.1. *Word-for-word approach: ESV in focus*

There was a general tendency to consider God’s word with reverence and so to consider each word as a container of meaning (Ryken 2003: 32). In such an understanding, the meaning may be altered or miscommunicated if not translated correctly in the target language. Such translations give importance to the form of the original language. Hence, as far as possible, the translators restrict the translation of the words in the same order, yet in a comprehensible manner. There are plenty of such translations already available in the domain. Word-for-word translation is also called literal translation and is considered the most accurate. There is a general assumption in such translations of providing the best accuracy possible. There are many Bible translations which are word-for-word. The NASB, the King James Version (KJV), the English Standard Version (ESV), and the New English Translation (NET) are all examples of word-for-word translations. One of the most common reasons why such translations are in high demand is because of the general understanding that the literal translation leaves no room for misunderstanding (Ryken 2003: 35). The claim is to preserve the meaning of the original text even in translation. Of the several literal translations, ESV is selected for the present study. It is also significant as it falls in the lineage of the KJV, which is widely accepted as representing the literal translation approach.

The ESV is a revision of the Revised Standard Version (RSV). It belongs to the literal translations with its claim of translating using the “essentially literal” (ESV 2016: ii) approach. It was originally published in 2001. It is written in contemporary English, yet readers still find that it reminds them of the KJV and RSV. It seeks to be true to the original words in order to be accurate. It seeks to avoid interpreting the original text by translating the words of the text instead of providing a mere summary or its sense. The translation is suitable for public reading and preaching. Scholars and laymen use it for both academic and devotional study. The problem with literal translations is that the original language may have words with different layers of meaning. Such a word may not be available in the target language and hence it leads to gaps in communication. The different meanings available to the translators are not available to the readers. Similarly, literal translation focuses on the words and not on the context in which

these were spoken. While translating the words carefully, the texts may not be fully comprehended without context.

1.3.2. *Thought-for-thought approach: NIV in focus*

There was the general assumption that when translated word-for-word, the text was not easily comprehensible. Some of the translations are thought-for-thought where the sense or the thought is given importance and not the words. Hence the translator tries to rephrase the thoughts of the author. In this approach, the meaning is sought to be reproduced. In such cases, it is convenient for the reader but requires effort on the part of the translator. There is also an element of the translator providing their meaning of the text, so this kind of translation is deemed as less accurate (Poythress 2005: 114). The focus in this approach is on the reader's understanding. All obstacles that the reader would generally face in terms of vocabulary and sentence structure are carefully eliminated from this translation.

The NIV published first in 1978 belongs to such a translation where the thought is communicated to the readers. The focus is on "broad modern English" (Preface ii) which is understandable to the entire international audience. It does not carry difficult words for the reader to be confused. It did not seek to be literal in word order, but to communicate in broadly understood English. Hence the focus is on the understanding of the people with a policy to update the translation regularly. The problem with thought-for-thought translations is that the process involves an element of interpreting for the reader. In order to increase the level of understanding, contemporary vocabulary is used. In such cases, the translation may result in losing the meaning of the original text. The translator's focus is on the reader; therefore, the text is only sought to be explained. While increasing the level of understanding, the text does not provide significant context which would have helped in complete understanding.

1.3.3. *Paraphrastic translation: The Message in focus*

The third approach is that of a paraphrase where the idea is retold for the sake of understanding. In this approach, there is freedom to summarize based on what is understood by the translator. There may be additions and deletions for the sake of communicating as well. In such translations, words are of secondary importance, the prime focus is for understanding the text. Such translations are easier to read and understand and do not require much effort from the reader.

A paraphrase translation of the Bible seeks to make the meaning of the text understandable to the reader. It may elaborate more on the context in a way designed to help the reader understand the passage better (Wilt 2014: 35). It can also be an adaptation to a culture or to a period. Therefore, a paraphrase is a restatement of a text or passage in other words that convey the meaning and may employ many more words to attempt to more completely describe the meaning of the words from the original language, thus enabling readers to readily detect further nuances of meaning they may otherwise find difficult to discern in a regular translation. This helps readers to easily perceive additional shades of meaning they might otherwise struggle to see in a standard translation. The focus of the translation is on easy comprehension and easily connects with the contemporary reader. The text is summarized, and in the process, additions and deletions are obvious to various degrees. The text is recontextualized for the reader. Hence the meanings differ when the original context is not provided.

The Message is one such paraphrastic translation of the Bible in English by Peterson from the original languages. It uses contemporary idioms to keep the language of the text “current and fresh and understandable” (The Message 2018: 1). Its publisher Navpress claims that Peterson’s work was later reviewed by prolific Old and New Testament scholars to ensure that it is accurate and faithful to the original languages. The translation was a response to make the text more interesting to old and new readers. The problem with this highly idiomatic translation is that the text is recontextualized for the contemporary reader. The idioms which are used are easily understandable for the contemporary audience but may not exactly convey the intention of the original. This can lead to the addition of information and interpretation. The text is immensely popular and has replaced literal and thought-for-thought translation for its easy understanding and the clarity it provides.

There are differing opinions among scholars and laymen. Scholars who are familiar with the original languages and who know the historical background find the literal translation approach more accurate as it does not summarize the translator’s opinion. Audiences which do not want to wait to dig for the meaning prefer a thought-for-thought approach, so that they can comprehend easily instead of trying to collect the background. Many times, the translator has to interpret the text for the convenience of the reader. This can possibly lead to limited understanding of the different meanings possible otherwise. Similarly, it may also be misunderstood by the translators. These options were seen as multiple ways for better communication. Each of the translations have sprawling claims to better communicate the text. The question remains as to which constitutes a better translation approach. In such a context, it is necessary to analyse these translations with respect to the criterion of communication. To this purpose, one translation from each of the approaches – namely, the ESV, NIV and The Message – is considered in the present study for analysis using relevance theory.

2. Comparative analysis

Effective communication depends on the cognitive effects produced when new textual information interacts with this environment, either by strengthening, modifying, or generating new assumptions. At the same time, the reader naturally seeks to minimize processing effort, and any translation that demands unnecessary mental work reduces communicative efficacy. The present study focuses on the three translations and their processes based on linguistic differences, cognitive effects, and processing costs. The analysis includes assessing the differences in the original audience, the secondary audience and the impact of these differences in interpretations. Identifying the background of the community in which the text is written is necessary for its interpretation (Gutt 2014: 105). In relevance theory, the mutual cognitive environment of the author and the audience forms the context in which interpretation occurs. This context may be traced in the language, culture and social system that the author and the audience had shared. Unless the context is provided, translation may even be interpreted differently (Gutt 2014: 106). Such a possible threat may be avoided by providing appropriate communicative clues and contextual effects. The struggle for understanding, guided by these cues, leads to the proper interpretation of the text. By systematically applying these relevance-theoretic concepts, the analysis evaluates the communicative efficacy of the selected verse through the lens of relevance theory. All Greek citations in this study are taken from the *Novum Testamentum Graece* (NA28) (Aland et al. 2012).

2.1. γεννηθῆ ἄνωθεν *gennethe anōthen* (John 3.3)

ἀπεκρίθη Ἰησοῦς καὶ εἶπεν αὐτῷ, Ἀμὴν ἀμὴν λέγω σοι, ἐὰν μὴ τις γεννηθῆ ἄνωθεν, οὐ δύναται ἰδεῖν τὴν βασιλείαν τοῦ θεοῦ.

- ESV: Jesus answered him, “Truly, truly, I say to you, unless one is born again, he cannot see the kingdom of God.”
- NIV: Jesus replied, “Very truly I tell you, no one can see the kingdom of God unless they are born again.”
- The Message: Jesus said, “You’re absolutely right. Take it from me: Unless a person is born from above, it’s not possible to see what I’m pointing to—to God’s kingdom.”

The word γεννηθῆ ἄνωθεν (*gennēthē anōthen*) has meaning at three levels in Greek. The first meaning is ‘from above’ or ‘from heaven’, second ‘from the beginning’ and third ‘born again’. Jesus uses this phrase to convey to Nicodemus that merely practicing the Law is not enough (as he is a Pharisee). John, the author, presents Nicodemus as confused. In this context, Jesus explains the new birth, i.e. birth in the spirit. Given the range of inferences, Nicodemus initially understands it as being born again in the womb. Natural birth refers to a world of sin and that all men are sinners (Rom. 3.23). The compound ἀναγεννάω (*anagennaō*) has the meaning of “cause to be born again” (Ringwald 1975: 176). There is an Old Testament connection as “I will surely tell of the decree of the LORD: He said to Me, ‘You are My Son, Today I have begotten You’” (Ps. 2.7). The new origin is in God through Jesus Christ, which is different from the physical birth in 1.13. Being born in the Spirit is an exchange. It is similar to other phrases such as “born from above” (3.7) and “born of God” (John 3.9). This notion cannot be fully comprehended by the human mind and hence it is therefore difficult for Nicodemus to understand.

Born again is a concept in the translation in John 3.3. Semiotically, the term works on three levels: first, ‘from above’, i.e. from heaven, implying that earthly things are perishable; second, ‘from the beginning’, implying that the past needs to be wiped out and a new life is created; and third, ‘born again’ indicating a distinction between physical birth and spiritual birth. By merely translating as *born again* in ESV and NIV (with the footnote as *born from above*), these three interpretations are not possible. The Message translation, *born from above*, is confusing as *above* is a highly vague term and may cause confusion and mythical allusions. The author presents the conversation between Nicodemus and Jesus for better comprehension. The ESV, NIV and The Message translations need to communicate the entire contextual information and consider processing costs, and ideally should carry a footnote explaining the meaning to the original audience

2.2. Ἀμὴν Amen (1.51)

καὶ λέγει αὐτῷ, Ἀμὴν ἀμὴν λέγω ὑμῖν, ὄψεσθε τὸν οὐρανὸν ἀνεφρότα καὶ τοὺς ἀγγέλους τοῦ θεοῦ ἀναβαίνοντας καὶ καταβαίνοντας ἐπὶ τὸν υἱὸν τοῦ ἀνθρώπου.

ESV: And he said to him, “Truly, truly, I say to you, you will see heaven opened, and the angels of God ascending and descending on the Son of Man.”

NIV: He then added, “Very truly I tell you, you will see ‘heaven open, and the angels of God ascending and descending on’ the Son of Man.”

The Message: You haven’t seen anything yet! Before this is over you’re going to see heaven open and God’s angels descending to the Son of Man and ascending again.”

Ἀμὴν (*amēn*) is used twenty-five times in John (Kanagaraj & Kemp 2002: 92). It comes from the Hebrew word *Amen* which means ‘to confirm’, ‘make sure to support’. Jesus uses it for solemn assurance. It is the climax of the introductory passage to the entire gospel. *Ἀμὴν* is usually translated as *Amen* and sometimes as *verily*, *of a truth*, *most assuredly*, and *so let it be*. It also serves as an “emphasis marker” and introduces a statement of pivotal importance. They are essential in interpreting the entire passage. This repetition of the word *ἀμὴν ἀμὴν* (*Amēn amēn*) has the force of a “superlative, most assuredly” (Strong 1996: 657).

In the present study, Nathaniel, who was earlier sceptical, suddenly recognises the Messiah and praises Him. The use of *Amēn amēn* points to this particular context and invites the direct attention of the readers. The text also implies that the Hebrew word *Amen* was common in the Old Testament (Num. 5.22 and Neh. 8.6). Hence, it implies the heralding of an important statement will be understood by the disciple later when they reread their life events with Christ, such as the gospel writers. It is used in John to add solemnity and this technique of emphasizing his words marks the uniqueness of Jesus (Tasker 1960: 70).

Truly has the etymology in *treowlice* (Klein 1971: 347) and has been defined as “in agreement with fact” (OED 2005: 1644). The usage implies solemn assurance. The NIV, ESV and The Message translations need to communicate the entire context. The translation as *very truly* in NIV calls for an emphasis on the truth of the promise that Jesus offers to Nathaniel. The ESV translation, *truly* (1.51), implies an assurance repeated for emphasis and certainty. The Message translation, *You haven’t seen anything yet!*, addresses the context of Nathaniel’s surprise and invites to a future revelation of greater expectation. Though the tone of a promise is lacking, the emphasis is more on surprise and anticipation in The Message. More than the truth or certainty or promise factor, it is the pattern of giving solemn assurance for greater truth. This pattern needs to be explained for the present-day audience for original interpretation as it was shared contextual information. It may be translated along with footnotes carrying the cognitive environment implicature of the original text.

2.3. *υἰὸν τοῦ ἀνθρώπου. Huion tou anthropou (1.51)*

καὶ λέγει αὐτῷ, Ἀμὴν ἀμὴν λέγω ὑμῖν, ὄψεσθε τὸν οὐρανὸν ἀνεφρότα καὶ τοὺς ἀγγέλους τοῦ θεοῦ ἀναβαίνοντας καὶ καταβαίνοντας ἐπὶ τὸν υἰὸν τοῦ ἀνθρώπου.

- ESV: And he said to him, “Truly, truly, I say to you, you will see heaven opened and the angels of God ascending and descending on the Son of Man.”
- NIV: He then added, “Very truly I tell you, you will see ‘heaven open, and the angels of God ascending and descending on’ the Son of Man.”
- The Message: You haven’t seen anything yet! Before this is over you’re going to see heaven open and God’s angels descending to the Son of Man and ascending again.”

The phrase *Son of Man* is an expression used thirteen times in the gospel. Jesus used this phrase to refer to himself. The *υἰὸν τοῦ ἀνθρώπου (huion tou anthropou)* is an “unveiling of divine attributes in the divine form” (Howard 1952: 490). The “Son of Man” was predicted by Jesus to be betrayed; delivered up; lifted up; suffer and die and hence gave his life as a ransom for many. The primary audience of John was enlightened in this regard and hence its inclusion in John.

According to Jewish law, a lamb was sacrificed for the sins of a man. In such a context, Jesus became a sacrifice for humankind. He was an undefiled lamb for the entire human race. This claim, as Son of Man, shows the identity of Jesus as a humble and obedient servant. All four gospels use this title, and scholars consider it to have derived from Daniel’s prophetic books where *Son of Man* refers to one who represented God and his people. Ezekiel, the prophet was also addressed by God as *Son of Man*. Similarly, it also alludes Jacob’s dream (Genesis 28:12), refers to the imagery of angels ascending and descending. In such a context, Jesus takes the position of God’s prophet to a people in captivity (Kanagaraj & Kemp 2002: 93).

John speaks of Jesus being lifted up from the earth in his narrative, implying crucifixion and glory. The act of the serpent being lifted up in the wilderness (Num. 21:9) was a part of the cognitive environment of the primary audience and hence required low processing costs. A similar expectation is given in the concept of *the Son of Man*. His uplifting in his death would be the means of drawing all unto himself (12.32). The Son of Man is to ascend to heaven and descend from heaven. It has Jewish roots (Ladd 1974: 281) and *Man* implies the human race; of which Jesus belongs in the narrative.

The *Son of Man* is a socio-cultural word, and modern translations need footnotes to explain implicit meanings. Its translation requires processing effort and needs to be relevant. The extended meaning of the concept needs to be explicated for the secondary audience. Hence, the translations – ESV, NIV and The Message – cannot be communicative by merely translating the words and not the implicit information. The appropriate information needs to be available for a secondary audience in a footnote or the background material of the translation.

2.4. σημείων *semeion* (2.11)

Ταύτην ἐποίησεν ἀρχὴν τῶν σημείων ὁ Ἰησοῦς ἐν Κανὰ τῆς Γαλιλαίας καὶ ἐφάνερωσεν τὴν δόξαν αὐτοῦ, καὶ ἐπίστευσαν εἰς αὐτὸν οἱ μαθηταὶ αὐτοῦ

ESV: This, the first of his signs, Jesus did at Cana in Galilee, and manifested his glory. And his disciples believed in him.

NIV: What Jesus did here in Cana of Galilee was the first of the signs through which he revealed his glory; and his disciples believed in him.

The Message: This act in Cana of Galilee was the first sign Jesus gave, the first glimpse of his glory. And his disciples believed in him.

The Greek word *σημείων* (*semeion*) can be translated in English with the word *sign* and is defined as “a mighty work wrought by Jesus that represents the revelatory and redemptive event happening in him” (Guthrie 1990: 273). Signs were miracles which had the primary purpose of demonstrating something more than the sign itself. Their value was more on confirming the power of the one who would do the sign as evidence that he was something out of the ordinary. In John, a sign was to mean that Jesus was extraordinary with the emphasis on the person Jesus and not the sign itself (Ladd 1974: 38). Hence signs were designed to lead to faith in Jesus. They must also be seen as a revelation of the identity of Jesus and his oneness with the Father.

Signs were used in the Old Testament in prophet Jonah and connected with the Exodus event of Israelites in the book of Genesis. Signs functioned as pointers seeking to reveal something outside of the event. The sign had the function of pointing to the authority of what was proclaimed. In the Old Testament, a miracle assures people of God’s presence and power, such as in Exodus 4.1–9. Thus, signs in John function two ways: first, the meeting of physical needs of man and second, to meet the spiritual needs. Signs cause the masses or the individual receiving it to produce faith and stand as a witness. John, the Baptist bears witness to Jesus (John 1:15–27). After seeing the water turn into wine, the disciples witness Jesus’ power (John 2:1–11). The Samaritan woman bears witness to Jesus (John 4:1–42). The Father bears witness to Jesus. Hence, the signs are intimately linked with belief and the role of witness (Ladd 1974: 343). This forms the cognitive environment of the primary audience.

Signs in 2.11 etymologically originates from *signe* and means ‘a sign’ or ‘a mark’ (Browne 2018: 225). A sign is defined as “a motion or gesture by which a thought is expressed” (OED 2005: 1419). Signs are consciously introduced in the text to produce faith. Hence, they are present to confirm a larger pattern of implied meanings. They are not merely symbols or signals. The primary audience was well aware of its interpretation in the miracles done by prophets to convey that they are from God. Miracles focused on the aspect of power, while signs focused on the aspect of producing belief. This contextual information will require a certain level of processing efforts from the secondary audience. It may be provided as extra-textual material explaining signs as revelatory actions, and not mere symbols.

2.5. ἠγάπησεν *egapesen* (3.16)

Οὕτως γὰρ ἠγάπησεν ὁ θεὸς τὸν κόσμον, ὥστε τὸν υἱὸν τὸν μονογενῆ ἔδωκεν, ἵνα πᾶς ὁ πιστεύων εἰς αὐτὸν μὴ ἀπόληται ἀλλ' ἔχη ζωὴν αἰώνιον.

ESV: For God so loved the world, that he gave his only Son, that whoever believes in him should not perish but have eternal life.

NIV: For God so loved the world that he gave his one and only Son, that whoever believes in him shall not perish but have eternal life.

The Message: “This is how much God loved the world: He gave his Son, his one and only Son. And this is why: so that no one need be destroyed; by believing in him, anyone can have a whole and lasting life.

John uses *ἀγάπη* (*agape*) to mean ‘to love’ thirty-six times, while *agape love* occurs seven times (Ladd 1974: 34). This unfathomable depth of the love is stressed by this *agape* which is unconditional love and forms the cognitive environment for the selected text. The love that the Father has for the Son is considered “the archetype of all love”. This fact is made visible in the sending and self-sacrifice of the Son in John 3.16 (Gunther & Link 1976: 543). It has a firm base in the Old Testament but is more a dominant theme in the New Testament. God goes beyond the limit to give up his one and only Son. Here, we have the cognitive environment of Abraham giving up Isaac in the Pentateuch (Gen. 22). This framework of his forefather reflects in the sacrifice his one and only son in obedience to the will of God (Gen. 22). It is this great love that God had for the world. The human understanding of tenderness, forgiveness, and love in the relationship of a father to an only child provides an appropriate picture of the sacrifice and its depth. The depth of love was measured in the Old Testament by means of gifts. God’s gift to humankind was his precious son Jesus. It has thus been said that the most significant feature in God loving the world is that “he loved so comprehensively” (Guthrie 1990: 104).

Love comes etymologically from *lufu* and has a wide range of meanings which includes ‘the feeling of love’, ‘romantic attraction’, ‘affection’, ‘friendliness’ and ‘the love of God’ (Klein 1971: 466).) In John 3:16, the translation in The Message makes the extent of God’s love explicit (“this is how much”), whereas the NIV and ESV preserve the more conventional wording “For God so loved.”. The Message translation makes explicit, through its construction, the implied destruction that awaits those who do not believe. Jesus as the *only Son* (ESV) and *one and only Son* (NIV) is made explicit to understand the proportion of God’s love and sacrifice. The Message also makes it explicit by focusing on the “Son” aspect and also on the “one and only” factor by repetition. The characteristic of *agape love* is that it is of divine nature (Howard 1952: 702). It is unconditional in reaching out of the sinful world, and this is to be emphasised for communication. It can be translated as *unconditional love*. This love of God goes beyond the limit to give up his one and only Son. Abraham’s parallel of giving up Isaac needs to be supplied in the translation as supplementary information for complete understanding. This will lead to cognitive benefit for the processing cost involved.

2.6. μονογενῆ *monogene* (3:16)

Οὕτως γὰρ ἠγάπησεν ὁ θεὸς τὸν κόσμον, ὥστε τὸν υἱὸν τὸν μονογενῆ ἔδωκεν, ἵνα πᾶς ὁ πιστεύων εἰς αὐτὸν μὴ ἀπόληται ἀλλ ἔχη ζωὴν αἰώνιον.

ESV: “For God so loved the world, that he gave his only Son, that whoever believes in him should not perish but have eternal life.

NIV: For God so loved the world that he gave his one and only Son, that whoever believes in him shall not perish but have eternal life.

The Message: “This is how much God loved the world: He gave his Son, his one and only Son. And this is why: so that no one need be destroyed; by believing in him, anyone can have a whole and lasting life.

Monogene is a compound word of *mono* (‘only’) and *gene* (‘begotten’). The literal translation is *only begotten* and fits the context. There are different meanings from ‘unique,’ to ‘single of its kind’ and ‘only child of parents’ (Strong 1996: 36). In the context of the verse, it refers to Christ as the only Son of God. The word *monos* is frequently used for God’s uniqueness, and the context here serves to explain that God’s stage of sacrifice to His only begotten Son reveals the depth of his sacrifice. In a broader frame, the meaning is that the Son is the only offspring of the parent, not the only existing person of his kind. It is not to be misunderstood as “one of a kind,” because the parent is also of the same kind (Bartels 2003: 723). The differentiation is implied that Jesus is “begotten, not made” (Noll 2012: 58). In John, the Son is not “one of a kind” but shares the very nature of the Father and hence is the “only begotten Son” of the Father. This ‘only begotten son’ becomes the firstborn after fulfilling the promise (John 1:12).

The ESV, NIV and The Message translations need to communicate the entire contextual information. The word *μονογενῆ* (*monogenes*) in John 3.16 has been translated as *one and only Son* in NIV and The Message and as *only Son* in ESV. The meaning of the nature of Christ in relation to God as begotten is reduced to the human understanding of ‘only child’. The translation is rendered to be easily understood, but the original context is not supplied. The translation must retain ‘only begotten Son’ and supplement the context of the original cognitive environment. In John, the Son is not “one of a kind” but share the very nature of the Father and hence is the “only begotten Son” of the Father (Howard 1952: 69). The cognitive environment needs to be supplemented in footnotes.

3. Conclusion

Translation takes place from one context to another context, which is the source context of the text to the receiver’s context. This gap in context needs to be bridged without distorting the original meaning of the text. In relevance theory, the original interpretation can be formed only in the original context. Hence, if John interacts with the contemporary audience of a different worldview/culture, a different interpretation from that of the original is formed. Such translations that focus on introducing changes and adapting them to the audience’s

culture/worldview can lead to a different interpretation. All translations, as well as other texts, have the problem of deriving the intention of the author. In the communicative framework of relevance theory, the basic assumption is that translation is for communication between the author and the reader. Therefore, the context, as in human communication, supplies the rest of the information for the interpretation of the text. There are studies which refer to communication models as inadequate (Bonard 2024: 145) and suggest modifying the inferential model to include non-intentional behaviours as a solution (Wharton et al. 2021: 259). By drawing on addition, supplementation, cognitive environment, and processing cost, the study achieves higher interpretive relevance in explaining translation decisions in the Gospel of John.

Every translated text needs to be assessed in the cognitive environment of the primary and secondary audience. The interpretation process is both communicative and needs the cognition of the reader. By comparing the Greek concepts in translation, the need for a paradigm in assessment is identified. In translation, the original interpretation, ostensive-inferential communication, communicative clues, contextual effects, processing cost, and the cognitive environment are the communicative paradigms of relevance theory. ESV, NIV and The Message are three translations focusing on the contemporary audience but limit the cognitive environment of the text and the reader. The concept of communication is analysed in the contemporary translations of John 1–3. The study has dealt with identifying and investigating translations in order to build a communicative paradigm for assessment. The analysis is based on the two principles of relevance. The first principle, cognitive principle, deals with the cognitive process of the reader (Sperber & Wilson: 1986: 7). The analysis considered the stimuli, context and interpretation in this regard. Such an analysis helps analyse the presence/absence of provisions needed for the cognitive process based on relevance. The second principle, communicative principle, deals with the communication with the contemporary reader (Sperber & Wilson: 1986: 9).

The struggle in communicating a text is well represented in the history of Bible translation. The application of relevance theory in translation as secondary communication has led to a “paradigm shift” (Doty 2007: 20) in the theoretical studies produced thus far in translation studies. The importance of contextual information to arrive at the original interpretation struggles to come up with the original meaning. It is possible by using pictures in sketches, diagrams and footnotes. The cognition of the reader and the communication of the source text are equally dealt with in relevance theory. As discussed, its application can be used on a larger scale for different types of text, audiences and translation genres. It is instrumental in translating literature – local into global, ancient into contemporary, from genre to multiple genres.

References

- Aland, Barbara & Aland, Kurt & Nestle, Eberhard & Strutwolf, Holger. 2012. *Novum Testamentum Graece* (NA28). Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft. doi: 10.30965/25890468-02901024.
- Bartels, Karl-Heinz. 2003. Only Begotten. In Brown, Colin. (ed.), *The new international dictionary of New Testament theology*. Grand Rapids/Nashville: Zondervan. 723–25. doi: 10.1177/0142064x8100401205.
- Bassnett, Susan. 2002. *Translation studies* (3rd ed.). Abingdon/New York: Routledge. doi: 10.4324/9780203427460.
- Bell, David B. 2005. A comparative analysis of formal shifts in English Bible translations. Alicante: University of Alicante. (Doctoral dissertation.)
- Bonard, Constant. 2024. Underdeterminacy without ostension. A blind spot in the prevailing models of communication. *Mind and Language* 39(2): 142–61. doi: 10.1111/mila.12481.
- Bratcher, Robert G. 1971. The nature and purpose of the New Testament in today's English version. *The Bible Translator* 22(3): 97–107. doi: 10.1177/000608447102200301.
- Browne, Daniel Jay. 2018. *The etymological encyclopaedia of technical words and phrases used in the arts and sciences, and of many words in common use*. London: Forgotten Books.
- Brown, Raymond E. 1988. *The gospel and epistles of John. A concise commentary*. Collegeville: The Liturgical Press.
- Ciampa, Roy E. 2010. Contemporary approaches to Bible translation. Origins, characteristics and issues. In Cavaco, Timóteo & Daniel, Simão (eds.), *A Bíblia: Suas edições em língua portuguesa*. Odivelas: Sociedade Bíblica de Portugal. 59–101.
- Doty, Stephen H. 2007. *The paradigm shift in Bible translation in the modern era, with special focus on Thai*. Auckland: University of Auckland. (Doctoral dissertation.)
- Grice, H. Paul. 1991. *Studies in the way of words*. Cambridge/London: Harvard University Press.
- Gunther, Walther & Link, Hans-George. 1976. Love. In Brown, Colin. (ed.), *The new international dictionary of New Testament theology*. Grand Rapids/Nashville: Zondervan. 538–47.
- Guthrie, Donald. 1990. *New Testament introduction* (4th ed.). Lisle: Inter-Varsity Press.
- Gutt, Ernst-August. 2014. *Translation and relevance. Cognition and context* (2nd ed.). Abingdon/New York: Routledge. doi: 10.4324/9781315760018.
- Hill, Harriett. 2006. *The Bible at cultural crossroads. From translation to communication*. Abingdon/New York: Routledge. doi: 10.4324/9781315759883.
- House, Juliane. 2015. *Translation quality assessment. Past and present*. Abingdon/New York: Routledge. doi: 10.4324/9781315752839.
- Howard, Wilbert F. 1952. The Gospel According to John. Exegesis. In Buttrick, George Arthur & Bowie, Walter Russell & Scherer, Paul & Knox, John & Terrien, Samuel & Harmon, Nolan B. (eds.), *The interpreter's Bible* (vol. VIII). New York/Nashville: Abingdon-Cokesbury Press. 463–811.
- Kanagaraj, Jey J. & Kemp, Ian. 2002. *The Gospel According to John*. Quezon City: Asia Theological Association.

- Klein, Ernest. 1971. *A comprehensive etymological dictionary of the English language*. Amsterdam/London: Elsevier Publishing Company.
- Köstenberger, Andreas J. 2003. Translating John's Gospel. Challenges and opportunities. In Scorgie, Glen G. & Strauss, Mark L. & Voth, Steven M. (eds.), *The challenge of Bible translation*. Grand Rapids/Nashville: Zondervan. 347–64.
- Ladd, George Eldon. 1974. *A theology of the New Testament*. Grand Rapids: Eerdmans.
- Lewandowski, Wojciech & Özçalışkan, Şeyda. 2024. Metaphorical events in translation. Does language type matter? *Lingua* 298: 103654. doi: 10.1016/j.lingua.2023.103654.
- Marais, Kobus. 2023. *Trajectories of translation*. London: Routledge. doi: 10.4324/9781003379713.
- Marshall, Howard. 2006. Gospels. In Johnston, Philip (ed.), *IVP introduction to the bible. Story, themes and interpretation*. Lisle: Inter-Varsity Press. 185–206.
- Meylaerts, Reine & Marais, Kobus. 2023. Introduction. In Meylaerts, Reine & Marais, Kobus (eds.), *The Routledge handbook of translation theory and concepts*. London: Routledge. 1–8. doi: 10.4324/9781003161448.
- Noll, Mark A. 2012. *Turning points. Decisive moments in the history of Christianity*. Grand Rapids: Baker Academic.
- Nord, Christiane. 2023. Functionalist approaches. In Meylaerts, Reine & Marais, Kobus (eds.), *The Routledge handbook of translation theory and concepts*. London: Routledge. 170–78. doi: 10.4324/9781003161448-13.
- Oxford English Dictionary*. 2005. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Poythress, Vern S. 2005. Fullness versus reductionist semantics in biblical interpretation. In Grudem, Wayne & Ryken, Leland & Collins, C. John & Poythress, Vern S. & Winter, Bruce (eds.), *Translating truth. The case for essentially literal translations*. Wheaton: Crossway. 113–35.
- Ringwald, Karl Heinrich. 1975. Gennao. In Brown, Colin (ed.), *The new international dictionary of New Testament theology* (vol. 1). Grand Rapids: Zondervan. 176–80.
- Rohan, Olivia & Sasamoto, Ryoko & O'Brien, Sharon. 2021. Onomatopoeia. A relevance-based eye-tracking study of digital manga. *Journal of pragmatics* 186: 60–72. Doi: 10.1016/j.pragma.2021.09.018
- Ryken, Leland. 2003. The bible as literature. In Comfort, Philip Wesley (ed.), *The origin of the bible*. Wheaton: Tyndale. 111–54.
- Saldanha, Gabriela & O'Brien, Sharon. 2014. *Research methodologies in translation*. London: Routledge. doi: 10.4324/9781315760100.
- Smalley, William A. 1955. Language and culture in the development of bible society translation theory and practice. *International Bulletin of Missionary Research* 9(2): 61–77. doi: 10.1177/239693939501900203.
- Smith, Kevin G. 2000. *Bible translation and relevance theory. The translation of Titus*. Stellenbosch: University of Stellenbosch. (Doctoral dissertation.)
- Sperber, Dan & Wilson, Deirdre. 1986. *Relevance. Communication and cognition*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Strong, James. 1996. *The Strong's complete dictionary of Bible words*. Nashville: Thomas Nelson Publishers.

- Tasker, R. V. G. 1960. *Tyndale New Testament commentaries. The Gospel According to John*. Lisle: Inter-Varsity Press.
- The Bible. English Standard Version. 2016. Wheaton: Crossway.
- The Bible. New International Version. 2011. Grand Rapids: Zondervan.
- The Message. The Bible in contemporary language. 2018. Colorado Springs: NavPress.
- Tymoczko, Maria. 2005. Trajectories of research in translation studies. *Meta* 50(4): 1082–97. doi: 10.7202/012062ar.
- Van Der Henst, Jean-Baptiste & Sperber, Dan. 2004. Testing the cognitive and communicative principles of relevance. In Noveck, Ira & Sperber, Dan (eds.), *Experimental pragmatics*. London: Palgrave. 229–79. doi: 10.1057/9780230524125_7.
- Verghese, B. K. 2014. *Let there be India. Impact of the Bible on nation building*. New Delhi: WOC.
- Westcott, Brooke F. & Hort, Fenton J. A. 1998. *Greek-English interlinear New Testament*. Grand Rapids: Zondervan.
- Wharton, Tim & Bonard, Claude & Dukes, Daniel & Sander, David & Oswald, Steve. 2021. Relevance and emotion. *Journal of Pragmatics* 181: 259–69. doi: 10.1016/j.pragma.2021.06.001.
- Wilt, Timothy. 2014. *Bible translation. Frames of reference*. London: Routledge. doi: 10.4324/9781315759913.
- Zhonggang, Sang. 2006. A relevance theory perspective in translating the implicit information in literary texts. *Journal of Translation* 2(2): 43–60. doi: 10.54395/jot-xdhen.

Sarah Mariam Roy

Department of Humanities, School of Technology, Woxsen University

Kamkole Village, Sadasivpet, Sangareddy District

Hyderabad, India

e-mail: sarah.mariam@woxsen.edu.in OR sarahroy123@gmail.com

Teaching Translation and Interpreting Online: Assessment Strategies from Practical Experience

Volga Yılmaz-Gümüş, Anadolu University
Laurence Jay-Rayon Ibrahim Aibo, University of Massachusetts Amherst
Cristiano Mazzei, University of Massachusetts Amherst

Abstract

Higher education has undergone significant transformations, with learner needs and expectations changing and diversifying due to modern life demands and extensive use of technologies. Moreover, the global COVID-19 pandemic has led us to rethink and extend our knowledge of teaching practices, with increased focus on online education. As a result, teaching and learning in this remote environment now need to be researched probably more than ever. This study aims to provide an overview of assessment tools used in online translation and interpreting teaching and to propose strategies for effective assessment. It does so by examining a specific online translation and interpreting course offered as part of a certificate program in the United States. This case study offers a comprehensive analysis of assessment methods in the given course, examining the course materials in view of Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives, and the Community of Inquiry framework (social, cognitive, and teaching presence in assessment). Predicated on hands-on experience, the assessment practices outlined in this paper provide simple and practical assessment guidelines adaptable to different settings of translation and interpreting teaching.

Keywords: *assessment, online education, translator training, translation teaching, Community of Inquiry*

1. Assessment in online translation and interpreting teaching: an uncharted territory

The COVID-19 pandemic has had considerable effects on all aspects of our lives, including teaching and learning. With the global lockdown that started in March 2020, remote teaching was the only option for several months. The assertion is that online education is here to stay and will keep growing in a post-pandemic world, thus, calling for it to be researched probably more than ever. There was a handful of research papers on teaching translation and interpreting online before the pandemic, most of which were theoretical discussions (see for example Bartrina 2009; Duranton & Mason 2012; Ko 2012; Alshehab 2013; Medadian & Ketabi 2014; Hartono 2015; Leone 2015; Gavrilenko 2018; Gorozhanov et al. 2018; Lee & Huh 2018; Yılmaz-Gümüş 2018; Ismail et al. 2019; Bilić 2020).

Research on online translation and interpreting teaching then grew tremendously in 2021. Collective volumes (e.g. *The Journal of Specialised Translation*, vol. 36b 2021; Seresi et al. 2021) were published, as well as a monograph by Mazzei & Jay-Rayon Ibrahim Aibo (2022) fully dedicated to teaching translation and interpreting online. The majority of related papers published after the outbreak of the pandemic explored instructors' and/or students' perceptions of online teaching and learning experiences during the pandemic in a wide range of geographical settings (see for example Afolabi & Oyetoyan 2021;

Alwazna 2021; Almahasees & Qassem 2022 Bordet 2021; Kasperè & Motiejūnienė 2021; Libberos Cortez & Schrijver 2021; Su et al. 2021; Wu & Wei 2021).

Hubscher-Davidson & Devaux (2021: 187) noted that there is a difference between well-organized online courses and emergency ones offered in response to a crisis. Research on both types provides the opportunity to think about and enhance our knowledge of the remote education experience. The Online Certificate in Professional Translation & Interpreting (OCPTI) offered at the University of Massachusetts (UMass) Amherst, the setting of the present research, was launched in 2018, namely before the start of the pandemic.

Against this background, the present study focuses on a specific aspect of online translation and interpreting teaching: assessment. Assessment design is an essential part of both face-to-face and online teaching. Assessments need to be planned and implemented in such a way as to respond to the needs of all stakeholders, including learners, teachers, the institution, and the market. Adopting a non-empirical approach, this case study examines assessment practices in one of the courses within an online translation and interpreting program. The article provides an overview of these practices and explores how the course content aligns with Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives and the Community of Inquiry (CoI) model. Taking the course *LLC501 Translation and Interpreting Ethics and Standards* offered at OCPTI as a case study, our paper provides an overview of assessment practices used in online translation teaching. The objective of the paper is to show how the contents of the course align with Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives and the Community of Inquiry (CoI) model.

For the sake of transparency, the authors would like to define their respective roles in this study. Volga Yılmaz-Gümüş was an invited scholar during the 2022 academic year and observed *LLC501* during the spring 2022 semester, taught by Laurence Jay Rayon Ibrahim Aibo. Cristiano Mazzei is the Director of the Online Certificate in Professional Translation & Interpreting, where *LLC501* is taught.

2. Theoretical framework

Course designers and instructors can address the challenges of assessment in online teaching by designing and using a variety of assessment tools and strategies that align with the learning objectives and promote higher-order thinking skills (Bloom's taxonomy), and by reinforcing the social and the instructor presence (CoI model). Assessment is an ongoing process that happens before (diagnostic), during (formative), and after (summative) the learning. In this respect, Bloom's taxonomy chart provides a framework for aligning various types of assessments with learning objectives. The scheme, developed by Bloom and his colleagues in 1956, is a classification of the different objectives and skills that course designers and instructors set for their learners. The classification has been revised many times over the years, and the level categories in the currently used version of the taxonomy were defined by Anderson & Krathwohl in 2001 (for an overview of the revision, see Krathwohl 2002). The six levels and action verbs used to define cognitive processes are as follows: remembering (recall, recognize, identify), understanding (summarize, compare, explain, interpret, classify), applying (apply, use, implement), analysing (analyse, differentiate, organize), evaluating (evaluate, check, assess), and creating (create, generate, produce, design). As learning objectives move from lower to higher-order skills, the assessments also develop accordingly. For example, if a learning objective is to enable learners to identify or list basic facts about the subject matter, then a multiple-choice quiz is appropriate. However, if a learning objective is

to enable learners to analyse the subject matter in depth and to support the analysis, then presentations, projects, and essays are more appropriate. Ideally, instructors should provide learners with a variety of assessment methods that allow them to demonstrate their mastery of new skills and knowledge. Considering that assessment activities need to be aligned with learning objectives, this study takes Bloom's taxonomy as a reference to demonstrate how such coordination has been achieved in the course being studied.

The CoI model, first developed by Garrison et al. (2000), is another point of reference for reviewing assessment procedures in online teaching. The CoI, defined as "a process of creating a deep and meaningful (collaborative-constructivist) learning experience through the development of three interdependent elements" (Garrison 2011: 22), provides a comprehensive and well-organized framework for designing online courses and a useful theoretical basis for researching online learning. The three key elements that need to interact for a successful higher education experience are cognitive presence, defined as "the extent to which the participants in any particular configuration of a community of inquiry are able to construct meaning through sustained communication", social presence, defined as "the ability of participants in the Community of Inquiry to project their personal characteristics into the community, thereby presenting themselves to the other participants as "real people", and teaching presence, related with the design of educational experience and facilitation, the former being the teachers' instructors' responsibility of "the selection, organization, and primary presentation of course content, as well as the design and development of learning activities and assessment", and the latter being a shared responsibility of the teacher/instructor and learners (Garrison et al. 2000: 88–90). This study seeks to understand how these types of presences are used particularly in assessment practices in online translation and interpreting teaching.

3. Research setting and method

The OCPTI is a short undergraduate program that is multilingual, i.e., not language-specific. Applicants must provide evidence of high proficiency in English and at least one spoken Language Other Than English (LOTE). To apply for the program, they need to provide detailed information regarding their language proficiency and educational background. Students are required to take at least 15 credits (5 courses or more) and must pass with a minimum grade of C to complete the program successfully and earn the certificate. Following the guidelines of US universities, students are expected to dedicate approximately ten hours per week to each 3-credit course. The classes are asynchronous, but not self-paced, which means that students are required to meet weekly assignment deadlines. Readings, discussions, papers, presentations, quizzes, and other course-related content are in English. Students do translation and interpreting assignments in their language pairs. Some of those assignments are sent out to language reviewers (professional translators and/or interpreters) who work in the same language pair as the student.

LLC501 Translation and Interpreting Ethics and Standards is a 3-credit course, which was selected as our case study to examine how assessment is conducted in online translation and interpreting teaching. Although it represents only one component of the OCPTI curriculum, the course was considered particularly suitable for the purpose of this paper because it brings together multiple dimensions of the field, including translation and interpreting practice, theoretical frameworks, technologies, and the profession. As a core course taken by students from different language pairs, it also reflects several pedagogical and

assessment practices used in the program, which offers a range of courses covering various aspects of translation and interpreting.

With the goal of recommending effective assessment tools and practices for online teaching based on data collected from the course offered in the OCPTI in spring 2022 and in the context of the framework presented in Section 2, our paper aims to address the following questions:

- At which levels of Bloom's taxonomy does the course assess learner performance?
- Do the course assessments call upon cognitive presence, social presence, and teaching presence?

This paper reports on the results of document-analysis-based qualitative research that examined course materials used in the class. Course syllabus, as well as assessment descriptions and rubrics, were the sources that provided data for these analyses. Blackboard was the learning management system (LMS) used in this course, and all documents were available to students on the LMS.

Document analysis, the research procedure adopted in this study, is "a systematic procedure for reviewing and evaluating documents" that "have been recorded without a researcher's intervention" (Bowen 2009: 27). As noted by Schensul (2008: 232), documents are the basis for most qualitative research. This paper first presents which diagnostic, formative and assessment tools were used, and then looks for the alignment of assessment tools or activities with the course objectives (see Section 4.1). Secondly, examples of assessment tools are provided to show which levels of Bloom's taxonomy were aimed at in the online course (Section 4.2). The CoI framework is then used to explore cognitive, social, and teaching presence in online assessment (Section 4.3).

4. Assessment strategies for online translation and interpreting teaching

4.1. Types of assessment in the course

Assessment is not only a way of evaluating student performance and learning but also an integral part of knowledge construction. A variety of assessments are used in online courses to allow students to demonstrate what they have learned in the courses and what they can do in professional settings. Table 1 provides the distribution of diagnostic, formative, and summative assessments and grade breakdown in the course being investigated.

Short syllabus quizzes are given to help both instructor and learners save time by reducing further email correspondence and to set course expectations in terms of content, time commitment, materials, course work, etc. These are lower-stake tools that help students engage with the syllabus closely before the learning process starts through questions on learning objectives, types of assignments, grade breakdown, deadlines, or digital literacy.

In the OCPTI, a wide array of formative assessment activities and tools have been used to evaluate learners' performance. Written, audio, or video discussions are an essential part of online learning, and different modes of media used for discussions respond to the needs of different types of learners. Other formative assessments include translation and interpreting assignments, quizzes, essays/reaction papers/analytic papers, and reflections on translation and interpreting.

Table 1: Diagnostic, formative, and summative assessments

Diagnostic assessments	Formative assessments	Summative assessments
Short syllabus quiz	VoiceThread discussions on Blackboard 30%	Final project presentation 30%
Short quiz on “Introduction and Overview”	Assignments (quizzes, translation assignments, interpreting assignments) 20%	
	Reflections 20% <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 short reaction paper - 1 recorded presentation 	

The summative assessment in *LLC501* was based on a final project that required both individual and collaborative work. Learners were asked to create a podcast episode where they identified and discussed complex dilemmas pertaining to translation or interpreting. They had the flexibility to express their knowledge and skill mastery creatively in this podcast. In line with course objectives, they had the chance to show research, problem-solving and collaboration skills they were expected to acquire in the class. A detailed assignment description provided course participants with information on the various steps of the project and its timeline, illustrations of complex dilemmas, lower-stake dilemmas and non-dilemmas, recommendations about the importance of communication and negotiation with group members, specific guidelines about what they were expected to do in this project, and deliverables to be submitted to the LMS. Furthermore, a detailed rubric was given as a checklist for students to self-evaluate their work before submitting and presenting their team podcast in a live presentation session. The assignment was designed in a way to provide the opportunity for learners to show synthesized skills and explore broader concepts.

4.2. Bloom’s taxonomy in assessment

The learning objectives defined for *LLC501*, examples of formative and summative assessments designed to achieve these objectives, and how they are aligned with Bloom’s taxonomy levels are presented in Table 2.

As indicated in the table, various assessments were designed to address each learning objective of the course. Written, audio, or video discussions enable learners to show their understanding of specific course components, including course readings (Understand). Assignments such as translating or creating a project require them to use the knowledge and skills they acquire in the course for a specific purpose (Apply). Reflection assignments that are very common in the OCPTI courses encourage learners to think particularly about their translation and interpreting decisions and justify their decisions by drawing upon what they have already learned in the course (Analyse and Evaluate). The Final Podcast project enabled them to showcase what they have learned throughout the course in a project they created collaboratively (Create).

Table 2: Bloom's taxonomy levels in assessment

Learning objectives	Formative assessments (examples)	Summative assessments (examples)	Bloom's taxonomy (formative/summative)
1. Discuss professional ethics as it applies to the work of translators and interpreters	VoiceThread discussion: Go to Course Materials and watch Cuban movie <i>Un Traductor</i> (English subtitles are provided) and read Fricklin and Jones's article, titled "Deciphering 'Voice' from 'Words': Interpreting Translation Practices in the Field." Comment on the reading based on the prompts given.	Final Podcast project in groups Reflection	Understand/ Create
2. Describe professional interpreting and translation codes of ethics and standards of practice	Essay quiz: - Read Julie McDonough-Dolmaya's article thoroughly and annotate it. - Answer each question in 4 to 5 full sentences. - Use your own words and do not use quotes from the article. The purpose of this essay quiz is to showcase your critical thinking skills.	Final Podcast project in groups Reflection	Understand, Analyse/ Create
3. Explain accountability as it relates to the work of translators and interpreters	Translation: Translate into your LOTE a church pamphlet about firearms and reflect on the impact of this translation on the target audience and culture. Translation assignment + reflection	Final Podcast project in groups Reflection	Understand, Apply, Analyse/ Create
4. Identify ethical issues in case studies	Reaction paper: Select a dilemma from one of our readings or from another source (newspaper article or real-life dilemma). Discuss the dilemma referring to specific tenets of specific codes of ethics and standards of practice.	Final Podcast project in groups Reflection	Apply, Analyse/ Create
5. Discuss strategies to address ethical dilemmas	Interpreting assignment: Interpret into your LOTE the white nationalist speech by Richard Spencer. You will share a reflection in a separate VoiceThread discussion this time, so as to discuss ethical implications with your peers. Interpreting assignment + reflection	Final Podcast project in groups Reflection	Understand, Apply, Analyse/ Create

4.3. CoI in assessment

The CoI is used here as a framework to seek evidence for teaching, social, and cognitive presence in online assessment in the OCPTI. In this scheme, teaching presence consists of the following dimensions: Design and organization, facilitation, and direct instruction. Social presence is associated with affective expression, open communication, and group cohesion. Finally, cognitive presence comprises the subdimensions of triggering event, exploration, integration, and resolution. What is written in a syllabus or any material available does not always warrant actual learning. However, they certainly provide evidence for an instructor's intention to promote learning, perception of best practices, and willingness to communicate with students. The content of relevant documents, therefore, offers some essential data to examine the three CoI elements in a learning environment.

4.3.1. Teaching presence

The focus on design and organization translates as clear communication of course topics, goals, and important time frames, and specification of how to participate in learning activities. Explaining these aspects very clearly at the very beginning of the course is more important in online teaching, given that students may not have the chance to receive instant clarification from their instructor. Furthermore, individual requests for clarification certainly and unnecessarily increase instructors' workloads.

The backbone of an online course is a detailed syllabus that explicitly communicates what the instructor expects from students and what students should expect from the course. The course syllabus provides a brief introduction to the course and course objectives. Then, a week-by-week description of the course clearly indicates topics, readings, and assessments that students should expect to cover each week (see Table 3).

Furthermore, schedules and important dates (e.g. assignment due dates) are announced at the beginning of the semester on the LMS. The grading policy and breakdown of grades are communicated clearly in the syllabus.

Table 3: Weekly course description from the syllabus

Week #	Dates	Topics, Readings, and Assignments
WEEK 5	Feb 23–March 1	What to read and watch:
Professional Codes and Standards		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Watch 12 min documentary <i>Justice in Translation</i>, published in the <i>New York Times</i> • Hale, Sandra. "Analyzing the Interpreter's Code of Ethics." In <i>Community Interpreting</i>. 2007. <p>Assignment: Reaction Paper: Select a dilemma from one of our readings or from another source (newspaper article or real-life dilemma). Using the code of ethics and standards, write about ways of addressing the dilemma.</p>

The second subdimension of teaching presence is facilitation. Facilitation is mainly associated with keeping learners informed, engaged, and motivated. In *LLC501*, the instructor uses a wide range of tools for course facilitation. A syllabus quiz and synchronous introductory meeting in Week 1 allow learners to get more familiar with the essentials of the course and discuss and clarify course requirements with the instructor. Videos uploaded by the instructor and occasional synchronous meetings with the instructor not only keep learners engaged but also reinforce the presence of the instructor. It is essential to highlight that, as all the OCPTI courses are asynchronous, synchronous meetings are fully optional, recorded and made available to learners who are not able to attend. The instructor further motivates learners to get engaged in productive dialogue by starting and adding comments to online VoiceThread discussions. Detailed assignment descriptions are provided to enable learners to complete their assignments easily. As seen in Table 4, for a reaction paper assignment, the instructor starts with providing resources that learners are expected to use to complete the assignment. She explains what learners are expected to do for this assignment (points 1 and 2), informs learners about formatting and style requirements (point 3), provides a link to the assignment rubric (point 3), offers an online resource for students needing help with academic writing and reminds academic honesty principles (point 4), and finally defines how to name and submit their assignment files.

Table 4: Assignment description

Week 5

Reaction Paper 1

Attached Files:

- [ATA Code of ethics With Commentary.pdf](#)
- [NAJITCodeofEthicsFINAL.pdf](#)
- [NCIHC National Code of Ethics.pdf](#)

For this first reaction paper, you will write a **3–4 p. essay** on dilemmas.

1. Select a dilemma from one of our readings or from another source (newspaper article or real-life dilemma).

Here is a list of sample case studies for dilemmas: [List of dilemmas.pptx](#)

You may also refer to the “Ethics in the News” folder to get started and find ideas.

Your dilemma should be complex. Easy-to-solve dilemmas do not provide sufficient ground to ponder over.

2. Referring to the various different codes of ethics and standards covered in our course, write about ways of addressing the dilemma you have selected.

What you need to do is a back-and-forth movement (like a bee!) between specific ethical principles (i.e. accuracy, impartiality, advocacy, etc.) in specified/clearly identified codes (you may work with more than one Code to add depth to your reflection; Dolmaya’s article you worked on last week is a great source of additional Codes of Ethics) and your dilemma. You may point out the limitations of what said principles offer in terms of guidance, or conflicts between different principles.

3. Formatting, style, and rubric:

- Here is the grading rubric for all written papers.
- Please note that all your papers should be written following a basic essay structure (introduction, thesis, analysis with examples, and conclusion). They should be written in 12-point font and double-spaced lines. Give a title to all your papers (example: “Reaction1_FirstName_LastName”).
- Include a list of works cited at the end, in addition to making the appropriate citations. Copying and pasting from the Internet constitutes a form of plagiarism. Make sure you cite your sources at all times. Include page numbers and use the MLA formatting style.

4. Help with writing and academic honesty:

- Our university offers a great online resource for those who need help with their writing skills: (...)
- Reminder: Academic honesty is required of all students at the university. For more information about what constitutes academic dishonesty, please see the Dean of Students’ website: (...)

5. Name your reaction paper according to the Course Syllabus guidelines and submit it here as a **Word.doc** file here.

Make sure your paper is somewhere between 3 and 4 pages.

Well-argued and well-supported three-page papers are preferable to longer papers with a weaker structure.

Direct instruction, the third subdimension of teaching presence, mainly relates to instructor involvement in discussions and to instructors’ feedback. As mentioned earlier, the instructor takes an active part in discussions by starting them and commenting on learners’ posts. The instructor provides general feedback that may be helpful to all learners in the course, as well as individual feedback for each assignment.

In the OCPTI courses, external language reviewers are asked to provide language-specific feedback because the courses are multilingual and instructors do not speak all the languages used by learners in their translation or interpretation assignments. Receiving direct feedback from LOTE expert reviewers may be considered a factor that fosters teaching presence in the courses. Grading being reserved for course instructors, external reviewers are asked to encourage learners to find solutions themselves by doing particularly the following (Mazzei & Jay-Rayon Ibrahim Aibo 2022: 78):

- Point out similar subject-matter materials written in their target language, including relevant URLs and highlighting a relevant expression or passage, explain why the resource is a reliable one, and encourage the student to identify similarly reliable resources in their next assignment.
- Point out interferences within their language pair.
- Identify extra-linguistic references to help them solve a problem.
- Refer them to a more reliable or more specialized dictionary in their target language.
- Encourage them to use a spellchecker or editing software and suggest one (if available in their target language).
- Encourage them to take higher-level writing classes in their target language.

To sum up, indicators of teaching presence in the course include providing a learner-oriented course design, a detailed syllabus with weekly descriptions of course content and deadlines with detailed assignment descriptions, playing an active role in discussions, and providing general and individual feedback, both from the course instructor and language reviewers (for translations and interpretations into their LOTE). In another study (Yılmaz-Gümüş & Mazzei 2024), the authors used the CoI survey, as well as several open-ended questions, to examine learners' perceptions of their online learning and assessment experiences in the OCPTI. The findings further corroborated the effectiveness of the teaching-presence practices described above (Yılmaz-Gümüş & Mazzei 2024: 18):

Well-designed syllabi and assignment descriptions helped the adult learners plan the time they allocated to the OCPTI tasks and guided them to complete the assignments properly. Active instructor roles in the discussions and the synchronous Zoom meetings were the course components that fostered learner engagement by increasing their interaction with the instructor. Furthermore, the instructor's active participation in written or video discussions made the learners feel comfortable in joining discussions. Finally, feedback from the course instructor and language reviewers played a significant role in evaluating and improving learner performance.

4.3.2. *Social presence*

As education is built upon a sense of community, it is of particular importance to establish a strong social presence in educational settings. The subdimensions of social presence are affective expression, open communication, and group cohesion. The primary questions are thus how instructors and learners present themselves as humans, as real people, how they open themselves up to learning together, or how they connect with each other in online settings. In online courses of the OCPTI, affective communication generally starts with an introduction video on VoiceThread from the instructor, followed by course participants' video introductions posted on a dedicated VoiceThread space to start a dialogue among learners. Another practice for facilitating connection is the inclusion of personal information about instructors in the syllabus.

Table 5: Information about the instructor on the LMS

A little more about me as a human being

I fell in love with languages and cultures in middle school in my home town in Northeastern France, and more specifically at age 13 during my first exchange program in Germany, (...). (...) I now have over 30 years of cumulative experience as a translation and interpreting practitioner and instructor in the Americas, Europe, and East Africa. My experience living in an African country with four working languages and highly different social and economic statuses, and establishing a multicultural family are central to who I am and how I approach communicating with different audiences, something I greatly enjoy sharing with my students and clients.

Some self-disclosure is likely to foster a sense of belonging – an element that becomes more important in an online learning environment. Sharing a personal story may encourage learners “to model that self-examination and go deeper in their learning” as a result of which “learning becomes relevant, has value beyond the classroom, and new meaning is constructed in the process” (Brantmeier 2013: 97). Thus, a personal story that follows background

information on education and professional experience may humanize the instructor and encourage learners to ponder what they can bring to and take away from the course (see Table 5).

The backbone of social presence is communication. This mostly starts with instructors' announcements about preferred communication methods/channels, availability, and response time. This is particularly important in online teaching settings where in-person communication with the instructor is limited.

LMS announcements (for example about office hours, weekly wrap-up, general feedback on assignments) from the instructors constitute unidirectional types of communication. Instructors or learners (individually or sometimes as a group) may sometimes need one-on-one communication via email, LMS messaging or Zoom meetings. In addition to unidirectional and one-on-one communication, instructors and learners get engaged in collective communication via written or video discussion forums.

The use of inclusive and welcoming language in the syllabus is a way of ensuring that learners feel comfortable participating in online discussions and interacting with the instructor and peers. It is important that learners feel comfortable contributing to discussion forums so that they can develop critical thinking building upon others' ideas, get engaged in a stimulating dialogue that keeps their attention and furthers their learning, and get to know each other as real people. Thus, it is of particular importance to mention explicitly that open communication is encouraged and that each and every idea is valuable.

While in online education environments, syllabi, assignment descriptions and rubrics are formal written (or sometimes video) tools for describing what is expected from students for assessment purposes in a course, they may include informal notes that imitate the instructor's more casual face-to-face voice to connect unostentatiously with learners and make expectations more explicit. An excerpt from the final project description below includes advice and tips about how learners can communicate, distribute roles, and solve problems in the group (see Table 6).

Table 6: Informal notes in the assignment description

PROCESS

1. Start VERY EARLY (wait, did I mention that before?).
 2. Communicate, communicate, communicate! You can use Google Docs, email, chat, WhatsApp or text messages to discuss. Exchanging phone numbers might be a good idea. Sometimes phone conversations or audio messages are a lot more efficient or adequate than emails sent back and forth. Make it SIMPLE FOR ALL. Tech nerds should refrain from suggesting new tools that require a learning curve. Simplicity and frequent communication are key.
 3. Set a realistic, concrete schedule with your partners at the beginning of the project so that you can stay on top of it and deliver on time with the least amount of stress. I expect you to work independently and solve issues within your team. However, please email me if you have concerns before they become problems!
 4. Be realistic about your own strengths. If you think you're good at something specific, then offer to do that in your team. If you think you're good at managing the whole process, offer some of that help as well. If you think you are research-oriented, then you might want to be the person researching the case study/dilemma, etc.
-

Group cohesion, the third subdimension of social presence, is generally embedded in collaborative learning activities. As a part of the assessment, learners are encouraged to comment on their peers' posts on discussion boards, which is an effective way to promote interactions among learners. Furthermore, peer feedback on assignments is encouraged. Final projects are group projects in which learners are required to pick roles and complete an authentic project as a team. Reflections on teamwork, as an integral part of the final project, allow students to evaluate their collaborative learning experience.

All these considered, the indicators of social presence in the course include the use of introduction videos and/or a synchronous first session, the inclusion of personal information in the syllabus about the instructor(s), self-disclosure when required, a clear indication of communication channels, the use of an inclusive and welcoming language, and promoting collaborative learning.

4.3.3. Cognitive presence

Boston et al. (2009: 5) provide a brief and clear definition of cognitive presence and its subdimensions:

Cognitive presence is the extent to which learners are able to construct and confirm meaning through reflection and discourse and is defined as a four stage process of practical inquiry. First is a triggering event, where an issue or problem is identified for further inquiry. Next is exploration, where students explore the issue both individually and as a community, through reflection and discourse. The third stage is integration, where learners construct meaning from ideas developed during exploration. Finally, the process culminates in resolution, where learners apply the new knowledge.

As the majority of learners in the OCPTI are career-focused, it is relevant to design authentic tasks, i.e., assignments that “assess the student’s ability to efficiently and effectively use a repertoire of knowledge and skill to negotiate a complex task”, and “allow appropriate opportunities to rehearse, practice, consult resources”, and “get feedback on and refine performances and products” (Wiggins 1998: 24). For the final project of the course, students must collaborate to identify and resolve an ethical dilemma in translation or interpreting practice. The instructor explains in a detailed way the issue (in this case, an ethical dilemma) that learners need to identify and solve in this assignment. The issue to be solved must be a complex one that professionals will likely encounter in their work lives (see Table 7).

Table 7: Assignment description: Triggering event

STEP 1: Decide on roles in your team

- Start early! Start early! Start early! Start early! (This is not a formatting issue.)
- For instance, one role could be researching the case study/dilemma. Another role could be identifying the various codes of ethics to refer to (think outside the box, look at different codes from around the world, in different languages). A third role could be creating the script for recording the podcast, etc.
- Team communication and negotiation skills are a must during this process.

STEP 2: Identify the dilemma/case study you will discuss

Your case studies need to illustrate:

- Hard-to-solve dilemmas
 - Complex issues
-

Below is an example of an easy-to-solve case from Week 5 PowerPoint list of dilemmas, which would NOT be appropriate for your final project:

“A child is scheduled for surgery, and you are interpreting for them (as in him/her/they). You have interpreted for that child and their parent before and you know that the child has a heart condition. The parents, however, forgot to disclose it to the healthcare staff.”

Your case studies need to provide ground for:

- Elaborate discussions
- Subtle pros and cons

Your case studies need to be supported by:

- Important concepts from our course readings

What your case study cannot be:

- A case study already analyzed in one of the course readings
 - A case study already analyzed in one of Week 5 reaction papers
-

Learners are required to explore the issue as a group, using helpful resources – in this case, a selection of international codes of ethics (see Table 8). They need to work individually and as a group to brainstorm and find relevant information to deal with the issue.

Table 8: Assignment description: Exploration

STEP 3: Identify the codes of ethics you will refer to

- Make a list of the codes of ethics you have selected.
 - Identify the principles you will refer to.
 - Contrast potentially differing principles across these codes
-

The third stage, integration, is a process where learners are required to combine information they acquire as a further step to resolve the issue. They apply the code of ethics and standards to the ethical dilemma they identified to construct solutions. To complete this stage of the assignment, learners need to discuss the ethical dilemma with group members, using fundamental course content and new information they get for the purpose of this assignment.

In this specific example of assessment, in the final stage (namely resolution), learners are required to create a 10-minute podcast episode (a scripted audio discussion between team members) in which they “do a critical analysis of a case study presenting an ethical dilemma”, showcasing their synthesis skills. A time-constrained podcast episode is an opportunity to show how learners can synthesize and transfer knowledge acquired in the course to real-life issues.

This is an example of an authentic task, fulfilling the key criteria defined by Wiggins (1998: 22–24) for authentic assessment: to be realistic (finding a hard-to-solve dilemma that professionals are likely to encounter in real life), to apply judgment and innovation, asking students to “pick” the subject (identifying a real-life case), to replicate or simulate the contexts in which adults are “tested” in the workplace (using a variety of sources to deal with a highly complex real-life issue). In turn, the instructor assesses the students’ abilities to tap into a repertoire of knowledge and skills to negotiate a complex task (identifying principles that apply to the case and working as a group to delineate the ethical issue), allowing them to get feedback on and refine performances and products (creating a podcast episode as an end product of group work, research, and problem-solving).

Reflective practice is another essential component of online learning to foster cognitive presence. Learners are also encouraged to reflect on the process of translating with specific reference to problems and challenges so that they develop a deeper understanding of translating: “Encouraging students to reflect on their process of tackling translation and interpreting challenges, applying research strategies, identifying and using terminology tools, etc. lends itself very well to multilingual online course [...]” (Mazzei & Jay-Rayon Ibrahim Aibo 2022: 34). By doing so, learners have solid evidence of what they have learned from the experience.

The course instructor also provides a rubric for written translation reflection or self-assessment. This rubric is a guideline for learners to reflect on the translation process (e.g. Which strategy did you use to solve a translation unit/challenge?), the product (e.g. Did you proofread your target text after you finished?), and performance (Were you satisfied with the result?) (see Table 9).

Table 9: Rubric for written translation reflection/self-assessment

Translation process:

- How did you find the translation for the most difficult word/term/phrase?
- How do you know your translation of the most difficult word/term/phrase is correct?
- Did you think about the audience as you were translating?

Translation tools and resources:

- Which tools did you use to help you in your translations (dictionaries, glossaries, online searches)? Please be specific and name your sources.
- Did you ask someone/expert for help? Please be specific.
- Did you post a question to a translators’ forum or group on FB or listservs?

Translation unit/challenge:

- Which word or term was the most difficult word/term/phrase (took you the longest) to translate? Why? Is it technical? Be specific and please provide a back translation into English if focusing on a LOTE term.
- Is the word/term/phrase culturally specific?

Translation strategies:

- Which strategy did you use to solve a translation unit/challenge? Reformulation? Explication? Reduction? Footnote? Cultural Substitution? Etc.

Translation quality:

- Did you proofread your target text after you finished?
- Did you use Spell Check in Office Word or another spelling tool?

Time spent on translation:

- How long did it take you to translate this text?
 - Do you feel your linguistic skills in the source and target languages played a role in how long it took?
-

Translation discovery:

- What new thing did you learn while you were working on this translation?
- How did you feel when you were done?
- Were you satisfied with the result?

Improvement plans:

- Do you need to take more high-level classes in LOTE or English to improve your linguistic performance?
 - Do you need to take high-level writing courses?
 - Should you improve your general knowledge?
-

Generally designed for instructor assessment of student assignments, rubrics may serve as a checklist for learners to evaluate their assignment and, hence, performance. Thus, well-designed rubrics now hold a legitimate place in online teaching for instructor assessment and self-assessment. Rubrics are made available to course participants right after they receive the final project description. Just like reflective practice, rubrics may be useful tools for fostering cognitive presence as they “encourage students to think critically about their own learning and motivate them to continue practicing and learning” (Mazzei & Jay-Rayon Ibrahim Aibo 2022: 89).

To sum it up, indicators of cognitive presence include designing assignments that require exploration, research and problem-solving skills, authentic tasks, reflective practice, and questions guiding learners for self-assessment, and rubrics for self-assessment.

5. Conclusion: recommendations for assessment in teaching translation and interpreting online

Educators will increasingly need new research and tools to deliver the best experience possible to learners as online education continues to expand. This article hopes to fill a gap in online translation and interpreting teaching by presenting practicable assessment strategies based on the analysis of course materials in a specific online class. Even though the recommendations emerge from a specific course with distinct characteristics, including the fact that it is taught to multilingual students, instructors might benefit from incorporating some of the general frameworks below into their assessment practices. A later survey conducted in the same program (Yılmaz-Gümüş & Mazzei 2024) provided empirical support for many of these recommendations from the learners’ perspective:

- Design of assessment activities should be aligned with learning objectives, as defined by Bloom’s taxonomy;
- Different learner needs should be addressed through constant communication, collaboration, and flexibility;
- A wide array of assessment activities (especially formative assessments scaffolded from low- to high-stake) should be designed, using various media that provide learners with the opportunity to demonstrate learning (e.g. multiple-choice questions, essays, videos, or podcast episodes);

- A detailed syllabus with clear information about assessment (e.g. assignments, submission dates, grading policy, and breakdown) should be provided at the very beginning of the course, discussing information in the syllabus with learners to avoid ambiguity and misunderstandings;
- Courses should include detailed assignment descriptions, presenting information about what learners are required to do, resources they can use, formatting and style requirements, assessment criteria (rubric), academic honesty, and how to submit the assignment;
- Rubrics and exemplars of good work (e.g. a sample reflection on translation; examples of excellent, good, fair, and incomplete comments in a discussion thread) should be provided as self-assessment tools;
- Reflective practice should be used especially in translation assignments to encourage learners to justify translation decisions with specific reference to problems and challenges so that they develop a deeper understanding of translating;
- Summative assessments should include authentic tasks simulating real-life work conditions of translators and interpreters (e.g. carrying out a translation and interpreting project as a team, using a CAT/CAI tool);
- Activities that promote collaborative learning should be designed (e.g. translation and interpreting projects where each member assumes a different role);
- Software that allows flexibility for learners (e.g. written, video and audio options in VoiceThread) should be used and learners should be informed about available technical support;
- Timely and constructive feedback should be given, and learners should be invited to give peer feedback;
- In some cases, personal anecdotes can be included in feedback to encourage interaction, such as examples from the instructor's experience in improving specific translation and interpreting skills;
- Instructor presence in the virtual class should be fostered to promote learners' online engagement in assessment activities (e.g. by starting dialogues and commenting on learners' input in discussion boards);
- Learning and assessment experience should be humanized by adding a personal touch to course materials and designing activities that allow learners to feel that they interact with their instructor and peers;
- Inclusive and welcoming language should be used in the syllabus and other communications with learners so that they feel comfortable participating in online discussions, which is a part of assessment, and working with peers in group projects.

Translation scholars will continue to research teaching translation and interpreting online and look for best practices of teaching and assessment practices for different educational and cultural settings. Empirical and evidence-based studies will improve the quality of online translator and interpreter training and the status of the translation and interpreting profession at the national and global levels. Considering the increasing demand for online translation and interpreting programs for bilingual adult learners and the need for further research on teaching translation and interpreting online, the authors of this paper believe that the proposed list of practices presented herein can serve as a point of departure for evaluating existing curricula and launching new programs in translation and interpreting.

Acknowledgment

This work was conducted during Volga Yılmaz-Gümüş's visit to the University of Massachusetts Amherst as a researcher, sponsored by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (grant no. 1059B191900270) under the 2219-International Postdoctoral Research Fellowship Program.

References

- Afolabi, Segun & Oyetoyan, Oludamilola I. 2021. Charting a new course for translator and interpreter training in Africa. Lessons from the COVID-19 experience in selected countries. *The Journal of Specialised Translation* 36(b): 327–50. doi: [10.26034/cm.jostrans.2021.047](https://doi.org/10.26034/cm.jostrans.2021.047).
- Almahasees, Zakaryia & Qassem, Mutahar. 2022. Faculty perception of teaching translation courses online during Covid-19. *PSU Research Review* 6(3): 205–19. doi: [10.1108/PRR-12-2020-0044](https://doi.org/10.1108/PRR-12-2020-0044).
- Alshehab, Mohammad. 2013. The impact of e-learning in students' ability in translation. *Journal of Education and Practice* 4(14): 123–33.
- Alwazna, Rafat Y. 2021. Teaching translation during COVID-19 outbreak. Challenges and discoveries. *Arab World English Journal* 12(4): 86–102. doi: [10.24093/awej/vol12no4.6](https://doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol12no4.6).
- Anderson, Lorin W. & Krathwohl, David (eds.). 2001. *A taxonomy for learning, teaching, and assessing. A revision of Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives*. New York, NY: Longman.
- Bartrina, Francesca. 2009. Teaching subtitling in a virtual environment. In Diaz-Cintas, Jorge & M. Anderman, Gunilla (eds.), *Audiovisual translation. Language transfer on screen*. London: Palgrave Macmillan. 229–39.
- Bilić, Viktorija. 2020. The online computer-assisted translation classroom. *The International Journal for Translation & Interpreting* 12(1): 127–41. doi: [10.12807/ti.112201.2020.a08](https://doi.org/10.12807/ti.112201.2020.a08).
- Bordet, Geneviève. 2021. Teaching online in translation studies. A teacher-researcher's feedback from France. In Radić, Nebojša & Atabekova, Anastasia & Freddi, Maria & Schmied, Josef (eds.), *The world universities' response to COVID-19. Remote online language teaching*. Research-publishing.net. 235–48. doi: [10.14705/rpnet.2021.52.1275](https://doi.org/10.14705/rpnet.2021.52.1275).
- Boston, Wally & Diaz, Sebastian R. & Gibson, Angela M. & Ice, Phil & Richardson, Jennifer & Swan, Karen. 2009. An exploration of the relationship between indicators of the Community of Inquiry framework and retention in online programs. *Journal of Asynchronous Learning Network* 14(1): 3–19. doi: [10.24059/olj.v13i3.1657](https://doi.org/10.24059/olj.v13i3.1657).
- Bowen, Glenn A. 2009. Document analysis as a qualitative research method. *Qualitative Research Journal* 9(2): 27–40. doi: [10.3316/QRJ0902027](https://doi.org/10.3316/QRJ0902027).
- Brantmeier, Edward J. 2013. Pedagogy of vulnerability. Definitions, assumptions, and applications. In Lin, Jing & Oxford, Rebecca L. & Brantmeier, Edward J. (eds.), *Re-envisioning higher education. Embodied pathways to wisdom and social transformation*. Charlotte, NC: Information Age Publishing. 95–106.

- Duranton, Hélène & Mason, Adrienne. 2012. The loneliness of the long-distance learner. Social networking and student support. A case study of the distance-learning MA in Translation at Bristol University. *Open Learning* 27(1): 81–87. doi: [10.1080/02680513.2012.640790](https://doi.org/10.1080/02680513.2012.640790).
- Garrison, D. Randy & Anderson, Terry & Archer, Walter. 2000. Critical inquiry in a text-based environment. Computer conferencing in higher education. *The Internet and Higher Education* 2(2–3): 87–105. doi: [10.1016/S1096-7516\(00\)00016-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1096-7516(00)00016-6).
- Garrison, D. Randy. 2011. *Thinking collaboratively. Learning in a Community of Inquiry*. New York: Routledge.
- Gavrilenko, Nataliya. 2018. Online model for teaching and learning the specialized translation. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education* 14(6): 2711–17. doi: [10.29333/ejmste/85421](https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/85421).
- Gorozhanov, Alexey I. & Kosichenko, Elena F. & Guseynova, Innara A. 2018. Teaching written translation online. Theoretical model, software development, interim results. *SHS Web of Conferences* 50: 1–6. doi: [10.1051/shsconf/20185001062](https://doi.org/10.1051/shsconf/20185001062).
- Hartono, Rudi. 2015. Teaching translation through the interactive web. *Language Circle: Journal of Language and Literature* 9(2): 129–40. doi: [10.15294/lc.v9i2.3703](https://doi.org/10.15294/lc.v9i2.3703).
- Hubscher-Davidson, Séverine & Devaux, Jérôme. 2021. Teaching translation and interpreting in virtual environments. *The Journal of Specialised Translation* 36(b): 184–92. doi: [10.26034/cm.jostrans.2021.040](https://doi.org/10.26034/cm.jostrans.2021.040).
- Ismail, Sayed & Alsager, Haroon N. & Omar, Abdulfattah. 2019. The implications of online translation courses on instructors' philosophy of teaching. *Arab World English Journal* 5: 176–89. doi: [10.24093/awej/call5.13](https://doi.org/10.24093/awej/call5.13).
- Kasperė, Ramunė & Motiejūnienė, Jurgita. 2021. Impacts of global pandemic on translator's career and translator training. *Current Trends in Translation Teaching and Learning E* 8: 154–95. doi: [10.51287/cttle.20215](https://doi.org/10.51287/cttle.20215).
- Krathwohl, David R. 2002. A revision of Bloom's taxonomy. An overview. *Theory into Practice* 41(4): 212–18. doi: [10.1207/s15430421tip4104_2](https://doi.org/10.1207/s15430421tip4104_2).
- Ko, Leong. 2012. Teaching translation online. A reflective study. *Translation Quarterly* 63: 1–26.
- Lee, Jieun & Huh, Jiun. 2018. Why not go online? A case study of blended mode business interpreting and translation certificate program. *The Interpreter and Translator Trainer* 12(4): 444–66. doi: [10.1080/1750399X.2018.1540227](https://doi.org/10.1080/1750399X.2018.1540227).
- Leone, Leah. 2015. The online literary translation workshop. *Translation Review* 92(1): 86–98. doi: [10.1080/07374836.2015.1094434](https://doi.org/10.1080/07374836.2015.1094434).
- Libreros Cortez, Héctor & Schrijver, Iris. 2021. Advantages and challenges of online translation teaching and learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. A Mexican case study. *Иновације у настави* 34(4): 1–12. doi: [10.5937/inovacije2104001L](https://doi.org/10.5937/inovacije2104001L).
- Mazzei, Cristiano, & Jay-Rayon Ibrahim Aibo, Laurence. 2022. *The Routledge guide to teaching translation and interpreting online*. Oxon: Routledge.
- Medadian, Gholamreza & Ketabi, Saeed. 2014. Educating autonomous translators in distance learning. A neglected area in the 'map' of translation studies. *Kalbu Studijos/Studies about Languages* 24: 36–47. doi: [10.5755/j01.sal.0.24.5935](https://doi.org/10.5755/j01.sal.0.24.5935).

- Schensul, Jean J. 2008. Documents. In Given, Lisa M. (ed.), *The Sage encyclopedia of qualitative research methods*. Los Angeles, CA: Sage. 232.
- Seresi, Márta & Eszenyi, Reka & Robin, Edina. 2021. *Distance education in translator and interpreter training*. Budapest, Hungary: ELTE.
- Su, Wenchao & Li, Defeng & Zhao, Xiaoxing & Li, Ruilin. 2021. Exploring the effectiveness of fully online translation learning during COVID-19. In Pang, Chaoyi & Gao, Yunjun & Chen, Guanliang & Popescu, Elvira & Chen, Lu & Hao, Tianyong & Zhang, Bailing & Baldiris Navarro, Silvia Margarita & Li, Qing (eds.), *Learning technologies and systems. 19th International Conference on Web-Based Learning, ICWL 2020, and 5th International Symposium on Emerging Technologies for Education, SETE 2020, Ningbo, China, October 22–24, 2020, Proceedings*. Berlin/Heidelberg: Springer. 344–56.
- Wiggins, Grant. 1998. *Educative assessment. Designing assessments to inform and improve student performance*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass Publishers.
- Wu, Di & Wei, Lan. 2021. Online teaching as the new normal. Understanding translator trainers' self-efficacy beliefs. *The Journal of Specialised Translation* 36(b): 301–26. doi: [10.26034/cm.jostrans.2021.046](https://doi.org/10.26034/cm.jostrans.2021.046).
- Yılmaz-Gümüş, Volga. 2018. Designing language-specific online translation courses: A proposal. *Hacettepe University Journal of Translation Studies* 25. 109–128. doi: [10.37599/ceviri.519315](https://doi.org/10.37599/ceviri.519315).
- Yılmaz-Gümüş, Volga & Mazzei, Cristiano. 2024. Teaching translation online. A Community of Inquiry study. *Current Trends in Translation Teaching and Learning E* 11: 1–30. doi: [10.51287/ctt120242](https://doi.org/10.51287/ctt120242).

Volga Yılmaz-Gümüş
Department of Translation and Interpreting
Anadolu University
e-mail: vygumus@anadolu.edu.tr

Laurence Jay-Rayon Ibrahim Aibo
The Online Certificate in Professional Translation and Interpreting
University of Massachusetts Amherst
e-mail: ljayrayonibr@umass.edu

Cristiano Mazzei
The Online Certificate in Professional Translation and Interpreting
University of Massachusetts Amherst
e-mail: cmazzei@umas.edu

Women Are as Fickle as April Weather – Are They Really? Cross-Cultural Analysis of Anglo-American and Slovenian Proverbs Featuring the Word *Woman*

Melita Lemut Bajec, University of Ljubljana
Klara Šumenjak, University of Primorska

Abstract

This study represents the first cross-linguistic comparison of Anglo-American and Slovenian proverbs featuring the word woman. First, dictionary definitions were analysed to assess portrayals of women and their societal roles in the selected reference works. Next, a bilingual corpus featuring the word woman was compiled, with 211 Anglo-American and 72 Slovenian proverbs to investigate the extent of shared proverbial culture. Lastly, a selection of seven equivalent proverbs in both languages was compiled to explore the cultural elements embedded in these proverbs. The study found that Anglo-American dictionary entries are more inclusive than Slovenian ones, which largely reinforce patriarchal values. The research also revealed a rich shared proverbial tradition. While the analysis of cross-linguistically equivalent proverbs did not uncover many culturally specific elements, it highlighted the universality of human thought and the pervasive influence of patriarchal values, portraying women as subordinate, emotionally unstable, and morally questionable. Nonetheless, the research also identified proverbs that acknowledge women's strength and independence. Lastly, the study emphasises that proverb translation cannot be reduced to a purely lexical process but involves varying degrees of adaptation to convey culturally embedded meanings.

Keywords: *proverbs, woman, Anglo-American, Slovenian, dictionary definitions, shared proverbial tradition, translation studies*

1. Introduction

Proverbs, the world's smallest literary genre (Kochman-Haładyj 2020: 73), reflect the way of life and values of the people of a particular language (Petrova 2014: 256). Being passed down from generation to generation (Kržišnik 2008: 38; Mieder 2015: 297), they encapsulate a collection of folk wisdom, truths, societal norms, and guidelines, and thus steer individuals and communities towards a moral and dignified life (Syzdykov 2014: 319). As part of formal and informal spoken and written language discourse (cf. Nippold et al. 1988; Mieder 1997), proverbs typically convey general rather than absolute truths, which often leads to varying interpretations, particularly when considered in light of different personal and contextual factors (Brown & Wright-Harp 2011: 27). Proficiency in proverb comprehension improves throughout life and correlates with the development of linguistic and analogical skills (Nippold et al. 1988: 20).

Proverbs as dynamic lingua-cultural items are constantly emerging and flourishing but also withering as new ones appear and enter common use (Mieder 2004: xi). According to Mieder (2004, 2015), European proverbs primarily originate from four main sources: Greek and Roman antiquity, the Bible, Medieval Latin and its loan translations, and mass media (songs, films, and advertising slogans). While proverbs may fade in some contexts, anti-proverbs – allusive distortions, parodies, misapplications, or unexpected

contextualisations of recognised proverbs – continue to thrive. Although not a modern invention, anti-proverbs have become increasingly prevalent in contemporary times, reflecting a cultural shift towards playful variations of traditional expressions. Today, anti-proverbs are ubiquitous in digital spaces, particularly in advertising slogans, often eliciting comic, humorous, or satirical effects through the incongruity between the original and the modified forms (Litovkina 2018: 3–24).

Proverbs referring to women are integral to the proverbial discourse and underscore the presence of a culture, profoundly marked by male dominance on the one hand and female subordination on the other (cf. Petrova 2002; Schipper & Schipper 2003). Extensive research has examined such proverbs across a range of cultural contexts (cf. Kochman-Haľadyj 2012, 2020, 2022; Schipper & Schipper 2003), as well as within individual traditions, such as Turkish (cf. Kara 2021), Japanese (cf. Storm 1992), Moroccan (cf. Webster 1982), African (cf. Hussein 2005), and American (cf. Kerschen 1998, Litovkina 2018). In addition, studies have explored women in anti-proverbs (cf. Litovkina 2011, 2014) and cross-cultural comparison, e.g. English and Polish (cf. Kochman-Haľadyj 2015) and English and Urdu (cf. Rasul 2015). On the other hand, the Slovenian context remains comparatively underexplored, with only limited contributions (cf. Babič 2021, 2020).

To date, there has been no systematic cross-linguistic research comparing Anglo-American and Slovenian proverbs featuring the word *woman* (hereafter referred to as women proverbs). This study aims to address this gap by (1) examining how the word *woman* is defined in Anglo-American and how its Slovenian equivalent *ženska* is defined in Slovenian dictionaries, (2) compiling and analysing a corpus of women proverbs in both languages to assess shared proverbial culture and representation of women, and (3) comparing a selection of equivalent proverbs in both languages to uncover cultural influences on their meaning, transmission, and interpretation. Therefore, the following research questions were posed:

- RQ 1: How is the word *woman* defined in Anglo-American dictionary definitions and how its Slovenian equivalent *ženska* is defined in Slovenian dictionary definitions, and do these definitions reflect the diverse roles women play, or do they reinforce stereotypical expectations?
- RQ 2: To what extent do Anglo-American and Slovenian women proverbs in the compiled corpus reflect a shared proverbial tradition, and how do they represent women?
- RQ 3: What do the historical development and cultural features of a selected sample of cross-linguistically equivalent proverbs reveal about representations of women?

2. Proverbs

Originating from the ancient Greek roots of *paroimia* ('proverb') and *logia* ('science'), paremiology encompasses the study of proverbs and other related linguistic phenomena such as proverbial expressions, proverbial comparisons, proverbial interrogatives, twin formulas, riddles, wellerisms, parables, apothegms, sententious remarks, literary quotations, maxims, slogans, adages, aphorisms, weather lore, graffiti (Mieder 2004: xii; Babič 2011: 27) but also modified versions of traditional proverbs known as anti-, quasi- and twisted proverbs, oftentimes satirizing the original sayings through hyperbole, irony, humour, and parody,

while still retaining core proverbial features like being concise, memorable, and insightful (cf. Mieder 1993; Mieder & Litovkina 1999; Mandziuk 2016). More specifically, paremiology investigates proverbs' origins, structures, and functions (Toporišič 1974).

While it is difficult to formulate a fully comprehensive definition of a proverb, as already noted by the early proverb scholar Archer Taylor (1985), its essence is often best captured through its communicative function as proverbs operate as conventionalised speech acts that enable speakers to convey culturally shared knowledge, express evaluations, and influence interlocutors in a concise and rhetorically effective manner; they may serve to offer advice, justify arguments or reinforce social norms, often by invoking collective authority rather than individual opinion. In this sense, proverbs constitute pragmatic tools embedded in discourse, whose meaning and function depend on context and communicative intent (Norrick 1985: 11–30; Mieder 2004: 132, 140).

Proverbs tend to exhibit certain consistent features, such as relative stability across lexico-semantic, morphological, syntactic, and pragmatic structures of at least two lexemes that typically remain unchanged or allow for minimal variation (Arora 1984; Kerschen 1998; Shtoltsel 2018: 11; Muradullayevna 2022: 892–93). Apart from the relative structural and semantic stability, other universally observed markers of proverbiality include a proverb's metaphorical nature and the presence of poetic devices (Keber 2011; Muradullayevna 2022: 892–93). Further, discerning proverbs from other phraseological units is often intricate and shaped by diverse folkloristic and linguistic traditions (Meterc 2014; Masimova 2018: 13), consequently resulting in a range of different terminologies (cf. Taylor 1931; Mieder 2015; Norrick 2015). Despite diverse traditions, a common emphasis is placed on the inherent meaning of proverbs, which transcends the literal interpretation of individual words. Instead, proverbs encapsulate distinct ideas or evoke imagery (Keber 2011; Espinal & Mateu 2019; Harmon 2021: 127), carrying figurative and/or emotional connotations (Masimova 2018: 12).

Proverbs typically refer to all aspects of human life, with individuals being described as archetypal representatives of humankind (Babič 2021: 80). On the one hand, they illustrate the distinct characteristics and customs of different societies; on the other, they also unveil a shared adherence to fundamental cognitive principles and patterns, thus underscoring their universality (Dobrovol'skij 1992; Madmarova et al. 2021: 444). Proverbs are not created by the folk but rather by an individual (Taylor 1985) as a response to a certain event that translates into a mental image and later into a linguistic item that functions as an interpretation of life, a perception of reality, and a socialisation tool, and further receives a more collective acceptance by the people at large (Mieder 2015; Madmarova et al. 2021: 446). A command of the fundamental paremiological units is a prerequisite for navigating effectively within a given communicative milieu (cf. Meterc 2014: 17). To fully understand a proverb and its emotional impact, it is therefore important to consider the cultural context in which it was created; if the cultural context is lost, proverbs may still be recognised, but their deeper significance can be obscured (Lewandowska & Antos 2015: 163). Proverbs are thereby context-dependent, where their full meaning can be understood and appropriately applied (Brunvand 1996; Mieder 1997).

3. Gender-related proverbs within the proverbial cohort

Proverbs as carriers of cultural beliefs reinforce gender stereotypes by depicting typical gender roles, behaviours, and traits associated with males and females, thereby functioning as agents of societal expectations shaping individuals' roles and identities (Martin & Dinella 2001). They encapsulate gender ideology, which is influenced by religious and societal principles dictating distinct rights, responsibilities, and rewards for each gender (Hussein 2005: 60). Although they vary across cultures, scholars working on gender representations in proverb corpora from different linguistic and cultural contexts (cf. Ronesi 2000; Petrova 2002; Schipper & Schipper 2003; Mieder 2004; Kochman-Haładyj 2020, 2022) have observed that various gender-related traits tend to dominate, shaping societal expectations.

In the English and broader European traditions represented in these studies, there is a recurring theme of inferiority, restricting women to domestic roles, and advocating obedience, even to the extent where physical violence against women is presented as rightly justified; additionally, women are portrayed as weak, fragile, stubborn, mysterious, nosy, talkative, and quarrelsome (Kochman-Haładyj 2020: 77–79). Further adding to the body of negative portrayals, Schipper & Schipper (2003) provide a global comparative collection, where women are also perceived as mischievous, cunning, vain, treacherous, tearful, untrustworthy, ill-natured, witch-like, and obsessively vengeful. Additionally, categories emphasising a woman's ability to give birth, possess beauty, and sexual appeal dominate over other, also positive feminine characteristics, such as being kind, caring, patient, economical, resourceful, and ingenious in overcoming obstacles – all qualities deemed essential for their roles as mothers, wives, and household maintainers (Schipper & Schipper 2003; Kochman-Haładyj 2020). The issue of female beauty is complex, acting simultaneously as an attraction for the opposite sex and a potential source of trouble. Consequently, numerous proverbs emphasise the benefits of a hideous woman. Additionally, beauty is often contrasted with intelligence, a trait typically associated with men (Ronesi 2000; Petrova 2002).

Anglo-American proverbs about women have been found to reflect patterns similar to those identified in cross-cultural and world proverb studies (cf. Schipper & Schipper 2003; Kochman-Haładyj 2020). Regardless of the roles women occupy – whether as daughters, mothers, widows, spinsters, wives, lovers, or mothers-in-law – they are often depicted in highly pejorative ways that perpetuate devaluation, discrimination, and the perception of women as second-class citizens (Litovkina 2011, 2018). Additionally, women appear to be among the most frequent themes in Anglo-American anti-proverbs. On the one hand, these expressions are typically antifeminist and demeaning to women, depicting them as demanding, nagging, complaining, critical, pushy, ill-natured, nosy, quarrelsome, never satisfied, revengeful, greedy, vain, and materialistic, etc. (Litovkina 2018: 5–9). On the other hand, influenced by women's liberation movements, numerous anti-proverbs have been coined, reflecting women's resistance to outdated stereotypes and their efforts to redefine their place in society, thereby creating space for a more equitable and balanced portrayal of both genders (Kochman-Haładyj 2020: 80–81). These proverbs may indicate that men are losing their traditional dominance in various areas of life, while women are increasingly taking on central roles and challenging long-standing gender norms (cf. Litovkina 2018).

Similarly, although research on proverbs related to women in the Slovenian context is limited, the articles by Babič (2020, 2021), based on a qualitative and interpretative folkloristic analysis of selected Slovenian proverbial expressions, sayings, and humorous folklore, identify

recurring stereotypical representations of women as talkative, less intelligent, submissive, and primarily associated with domestic roles, as well as negatively evaluated in relation to age. Babič (2020: 2–4, 2021: 84–88) also notes that, despite societal progress and improvements in women’s status, modern riddles and contemporary humorous expressions, particularly those targeting blondes and mothers-in-law, continue to reproduce and in some cases intensify traditional gender stereotypes. This suggests that modern Slovenian folklore not only preserves these deep-rooted representations but also recontextualises them within modern humorous discourse. This, in turn, supports the view that folklore is not neutral entertainment, but a carrier of social and gender ideology, where such representations are embedded and perpetuated.

4. Methodology

This study adopts a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative and quantitative data. The research is based on document analysis, which involves the systematic examination of publicly available sources and allows for broad and contextually grounded data coverage (Bowen 2009: 27). The qualitative component of the study was conducted through inductive coding and categorisation, whereby the dataset was first segmented into lower-order semantic units and subsequently organised into higher-order categories (Kordeš & Smrdu 2015; Vogrinc 2008). The quantitative component, consisting of frequency-based analysis of semantic categories, was used to support and complement the qualitative findings. The integration of qualitative and quantitative data enhanced the robustness of the study by enabling complementarity, corroboration, and a more complete understanding of the phenomenon under investigation (Creswell & Plano Clark 2017). The study was conducted in four steps (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Overview of the research procedure

First, we analysed dictionary definitions of the word *woman* in English and Slovenian, respectively. For English, we consulted two online dictionaries: *Merriam-Webster* (n.d.) and *Oxford Learner’s Dictionaries* (n.d.). These were selected because they are widely used and authoritative reference works that reflect different lexicographic traditions associated with American and British English, respectively, allowing for comparison across the two standard varieties of English.

For the Slovenian language, we relied on the *eSSKJ – Slovar slovenskega knjižnega jezika* (2016–), available on the Fran portal, which represents the central and most comprehensive monolingual explanatory dictionary of contemporary Slovenian. The choice of this source was motivated by its up-to-date, continuously expanding nature and its role as the primary reference work for general lexical meanings in Slovenian.

Second, to compile the bilingual proverb collections, we identified all proverbs containing the word *woman* in English and *ženska*, *žena* in Slovenian, as well as possessive forms *woman's* and *ženski*. However, since the primary meaning of *žena* is relational and denotes a married woman, i.e. *wife*, occurrences reflecting this specific sense were excluded from the analysis. Only instances in which *žena* was used more generally, in the sense of *ženska*, were considered. The analysis, therefore, focused primarily on *ženska* as the general and semantically neutral equivalent of the English *woman*. Also, knowing that proverbs often appear in multiple forms (Taylor 1985), we treated variation of the same proverb as a single entry (e.g. *Hell hath no fury like a woman scorned*; *Hell knows no wrath like a woman scorned*).

To build a comprehensive list of Anglo-American women proverbs, we consulted four sources: *A Dictionary of American Proverbs* (Mieder et al. 1992), *The Oxford Dictionary of Proverbs* (Speake 2008), *A Proverb A Day Keeps Boredom Away* (Litovkina & Dobrovolskij 2000), and *The Dictionary of Modern Proverbs* (Doyle et al. 2012). These works were chosen because they represent authoritative and complementary collections of proverbs, encompassing traditional, contemporary, and contextually documented material from American and British traditions. They also draw on a range of sources, from oral traditions to literary texts and contemporary usage, and provide contextual and chronological references. While Litovkina's 2018 book *Women Through Anti-Proverbs* was also referenced, our focus remained on well-established proverbs. Therefore, we largely excluded newly coined anti-proverbs, though some well-known ones, such as *Women and elephants never forget*, were included when documented in one of the above-listed dictionaries. However, we did not include modern anti-proverbs as this falls outside the scope of this research. Overall, the final compilation now consists of 211 proverbs.

Regarding the Slovenian language, there is currently no single, systematically organised compilation of Slovenian proverbs specifically focused on gender, let alone on the proverbs with the word *woman*. Although both an ongoing online dictionary and a printed dictionary are available (Meterc 2020–, 2023), the number of entries under the headwords *ženska/žena* remains limited. As a result, these sources do not provide a sufficiently extensive and systematically structured corpus for this study. Therefore, we relied on two sources: Šašelj's (1936) article "Kaj pripovedujejo slovenski pregovori o ženskah" ('What Slovenian proverbs say about women') and Babič's (2021) article "Stereotipna podoba ženske v slovenskih folklorih" ('Stereotypical image of women in Slovenian folklore forms') (titles translated by the authors). In total, this resulted in a dataset of 72 proverbs.

It should be noted that the datasets need to be understood as non-exhaustive. Consequently, the analysis is based on representative samples rather than complete corpora. While every effort was made to compile as comprehensive a dataset as possible, this was constrained by the absence of systematic and exhaustive collections, particularly for Slovenian proverbial material. This also explains the reliance on multiple sources in the compilation of the Anglo-American corpus in order to ensure breadth and coverage.

After that, we proceeded with the analysis of semantic fields. We classified categories based on the identifiable semantic affinities they share (cf. Finegan 2008). An inductive taxonomy was developed by grouping proverbs according to their core meaning or underlying conceptual content, whereby items expressing similar ideas were clustered into the same semantic field. In cases where proverbs exhibited semantic overlap and could plausibly be assigned to more than one semantic field, a consistent coding principle was applied. Each

proverb was assigned to a single semantic field based on its dominant and overarching meaning, rather than being counted multiple times. This decision was guided by the primary conceptual message conveyed by the proverb in context. As a point of departure for our corpus-driven analysis, existing classificatory models (cf. Litovkina 2011, 2018) were consulted, providing an initial comparative framework. However, as the two proverb corpora revealed additional semantic nuances and/or culturally specific extensions, existing classificatory models required redefinition and/or expansion. Overall, the final taxonomy ensures comparability with prior research and maintains sensitivity to cross-linguistic variation. Next, based on these semantic categories, we performed a basic quantitative analysis to determine the extent of a shared proverbial tradition.

Finally, we investigated the bilingual corpus and selected seven cross-linguistically equivalent proverbs, which we identified as near/direct equivalents. Near equivalent proverbs were defined as those that express similar underlying semantic content or pragmatic function but differ in their lexical realisation, imagery, or metaphorical structure. Direct equivalents refer to proverbs that correspond in meaning and lexical-semantic structure, often approximating a near-literal translation between the two languages. This distinction was adopted to align with translation studies approaches to equivalence, which understand meaning as multi-layered and focus on communicative purpose and context-sensitive translation decisions (cf. Baker 2018; Nord 2018). The culturally embedded nature of proverb translation further resonates with perspectives that view translation as a form of cultural rewriting and ideological mediation (cf. Tymoczko 2007; Bassnett 2014; Venuti 2018). In addition, this perspective can be related to Chesterman's (2016) concept of translation as the cross-cultural dissemination of ideas, whereby stable units of meaning may circulate across linguistic systems while undergoing formal and metaphorical adaptation. Lastly, the analysis is grounded in the understanding that the transfer and diffusion of proverbs are facilitated by sustained cultural contact between linguistic communities (Taylor 1985).

5. Findings

The findings are organised into three sections. The first section (5.1) examines how the term *woman* is defined in Anglo-American dictionaries and how the word *ženska* is defined in Slovenian dictionaries, exploring whether these definitions profoundly differ in reflecting the diverse roles women occupy. The second section (5.2) investigates the extent of shared proverbial culture and assesses how closely the two proverb collections align in reinforcing traditional societal norms. The third section (5.3) analyses a selected sample of cross-linguistically equivalent proverbs and examines their historical and cultural features to explore how these shape their meaning and representation of women.

5.1. *The differences in the dictionary definitions between English and Slovenian*

Based on Merriam-Webster (n.d.) and Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary (n.d.), the noun *woman* primarily denotes "an adult female person" (e.g. *a 54-year-old woman; an interesting young woman*). This core biological sense is extended to refer to women as members of specific social or occupational categories, typically in compounds such as *businesswoman*, *councilwoman*, or *Englishwoman* (Merriam-Webster n.d.; Oxford Learner's Dictionaries n.d.). Both dictionaries also include references to women in relation to labour or work roles,

particularly in domestic or manual contexts (e.g. *We used to have a woman do the cleaning*) (Merriam-Webster n.d.; Oxford Learner's Dictionaries n.d.). A further set of meanings describes relational identities, including wife, girlfriend, or female partner (e.g. *He's got a new woman in his life*) (Merriam-Webster n.d.; Oxford Learner's Dictionaries n.d.). In addition, both dictionaries record marked usages. These include archaic or offensive forms of address (e.g. *Be quiet, woman!*) (Oxford Learner's Dictionaries n.d.) as well as informal or evaluative uses referring to emotional or personal devotion (e.g. *a chocolate woman through and through*) (Merriam-Webster n.d.). Finally, idiomatic expressions illustrate culturally embedded uses of the term, such as *be your own man/woman*, *a woman of leisure*, or *hell hath no fury like a woman scorned* (Merriam-Webster n.d.; Oxford Learner's Dictionaries n.d.). Overall, these senses form a structured lexical-semantic network ranging from biological reference to socially, relationally, and pragmatically extended meanings.

The Slovenian dictionary definitions of the word *ženska* ('woman') in the eSSKJ (2016–) also stress biological distinctions, but tend to be more strongly associated with stereotypical representations, primarily expressed through physical descriptors (e.g. *majhna* 'small', *mlada* 'young', *modrooka* 'blue-eyed', *vitka* 'slim', *mirna* 'calm', *prijazna* 'kind', *noseča* 'pregnant', *poročena* 'married', *ženska srednjih let* 'middle-aged'). Further, the entry presents a woman in terms of physical development from girlhood to womanhood (e.g. *kar v nekaj mesecih se je iz dekleta razvila v žensko* 'in just a few months she developed from a girl into a woman') and associates womanhood with socially and behaviourally framed expectations based on gendered assumptions (e.g. *ga bo že preprosila, saj je ženska* 'she will persuade him, as she is a woman'; *v njej je premalo ženske, da bi to razumela* 'there is not enough of a woman in her to understand this'). Importantly, while the core definition itself remains largely neutral, stereotypical and evaluative representations emerge primarily in the usage examples and phraseological units rather than at the definitional level. Further, women are portrayed in phraseological examples as emotionally volatile (e.g. *ženska je kakor aprilsko vreme* 'a woman is like April weather') and cunning (e.g. *kjer vrag ne zmore, ženska pripomore* 'where the devil fails, a woman prevails'). These elements can be interpreted as reflecting evaluative and stereotypical views of women within the broader lexicographic treatment of the entry.

To conclude, the comparison of dictionary definitions of the word *woman* in English and Slovenian suggests differences in the types of semantic features emphasised in each entry. While definitions in both languages begin with neutral biological reference to an adult female human, the English dictionaries extend the meaning primarily through references to social roles, relational identities, and idiomatic usage, reflecting a broad functional and contextual range of meanings. On the other hand, the Slovenian dictionary entry includes a greater proportion of evaluative and descriptive attributes related to physical appearance, personality traits, and stereotypical characterisations. In summary, it can be concluded that the observed differences indicate variation in lexical framing and semantic emphasis across the two lexicographic traditions.

5.2. *The extent of shared proverbial tradition*

The two collections contain 283 proverbs, comprising 211 (75%) Anglo-American proverbs and 72 (25%) Slovenian ones. They were classified into four categories (see Table 2): *Subservient* with 63 proverbs (22%), *Expectations* with 60 proverbs (21%), *Character* with 151 proverbs (53%), and *Opposites* with 9 proverbs (3%). This distribution shows a clear

predominance of the *Character* category, which alone accounts for more than half of the dataset, indicating that women proverbs most frequently describe inherent personal traits.

These four categories were subsequently subdivided into 12 uniform semantic fields (see Table 2). A closer look reveals that the *Character* category (53%) is dominated by strongly evaluative and predominantly negative traits, such as *Troublesome* (17%), *Manipulative* (8.8%), and *Gossipy* (7.4%), although it also includes more ambivalent attributes like *Powerful* (11.3%) and *Mysterious* (8.5%). In contrast, the *Expectations* category (21.5%) is primarily associated with external and socially constructed attributes, particularly *Looks* (9.5%), *Age* (6%), and *Moral qualities* (5.7%), reflecting societal norms imposed on women rather than inherent characteristics. Similarly, the *Subservient* category (22.5%) is largely defined by explicitly hierarchical and negative semantic fields, especially *Domestic* and *Inferior* (both 9.9%), alongside *Misogyny* (2.5%), which directly encodes unequal gender relations. The *Opposites* category (3.2%), although marginal in size, indicates the presence of contradictory or paradoxical representations, which may point to inconsistencies in how women are conceptualised across proverbs.

In summary, the overall representation of women in the combined corpus is mixed, although leaning toward the negative, with relatively limited emphasis on positive or empowering characteristics. It should also be noted that the inclusion of such proverbs in established collections (e.g. dictionaries, proverb collections, etc.) does not itself constitute endorsement; instead, it reflects the linguistic and social realities in which these expressions have circulated but may, in turn, contribute to the continued visibility and potential legitimisation.

Table 2: Overview of the four main semantic fields and the 12 sub-semantic fields

Character			Expectations			Subservient			Opposites		
Semantic field	No.	%	Semantic field	No.	%	Semantic field	No.	%	Semantic field	No.	%
Troublesome	49	17	Looks	27	9.5	Domestic	28	9.9	Opposites	9	3.2
Powerful	32	11.3	Age	17	6	Inferior	28	9.9			
Manipulative	25	8.8	Moral	16	5.7	Misogyny	7	2.5			
Mysterious	24	8.5									
Gossipy	21	7.4									
Total	151	53	Total	60	21.5	Total	63	22.5	Total	9	3.2
Total	283 proverbs, 100%										

A closer comparison between the English and Slovenian datasets (see Table 3) reveals several important differences. The Slovenian dataset exhibits a stronger tendency toward negative evaluations, particularly in the case of *Troublesome*, which is considerably more frequent than in the English dataset (22.2% vs. 15.6%), and *Inferior* (13.8% vs. 8.5%). In contrast, the semantic field *Powerful* is almost three times more frequent in English proverbs

(13.3%) than in Slovenian ones (5.6%), suggesting that English proverbs may be more inclined to attribute agency or authority, whereas Slovenian ones tend to downplay it. Similarly, the semantic field *Domestic* appears much more frequently in the Slovenian dataset (15.4%) than in English ones (8%), pointing to a stronger association with traditional or role-based expectations. For categories such as *Manipulative* (8.8% vs. 9.7%) and *Mysterious* (9% vs. 6.9%) the differences are less pronounced.

Certain semantic fields are also notably absent or marginal in the Slovenian dataset. For instance, *Age* appears in the English dataset at 8 % but is entirely absent in the Slovenian dataset (0%). Conversely, *Misogyny* is slightly more present in the Slovenian dataset (4.2%) than in the English ones (2%), although it remains a relatively minor semantic field in both datasets.

Overall, it can be deduced that English proverbs are more evenly distributed across the semantic fields, thus reflecting a more nuanced and diversified perception, whereas the Slovenian dataset is more concentrated around a few semantic fields, particularly *Troublesome*, *Domestic*, and *Inferior*, indicating a more rigid, stereotype-driven, and role-oriented framing.

Table 3: Distribution of proverbs by semantic fields and language

	English			Slovenian		
		No	%		No	%
Troublesome	Troublesome	33	15,6	Troublesome	16	22.2
Powerful	Powerful	28	13,3	Domestic	11	15.4
Inferior	Looks	20	9,5	Inferior	10	13.8
Domestic	Mysterious	19	9	Manipulative	7	9.7
Looks	Manipulative	18	8.8	Looks	7	9.7
Manipulative	Inferior	18	8,5	Gossipy	6	8.3
Mysterious	Domestic	17	8	Mysterious	5	6.9
Gossipy	Age	17	8	Powerful	4	5.6
Age	Gossipy	15	7,1	Misogyny	3	4.2
Moral	Moral	14	6.5	Moral	2	2.8
Opposites	Opposites	8	3.7	Opposites	1	1.4
Misogyny	Misogyny	4	2	Age	0	0
Total	Total	211	100%		72	100%

Overall, despite some proportional differences, the presence of most shared semantic fields across both corpora suggests a considerable degree of overlap in proverbial themes. This indicates that, while emphases may differ, there is a meaningful shared proverbial foundation between the two traditions.

In the following analysis, we demonstrate this by presenting the four categories and the 12 semantic fields within them, supported by proverbs from each language. However, it needs to be emphasised that drawing clear lines between semantic fields can be challenging as many proverbs reflect different nuances on one level, yet share common ideas on another, more general level (Lauhakangas 2001: 24).

The first category, *Subservient*, constitutes three semantic fields:

- The semantic field *Inferior* presents women as subordinate, with little autonomy (*Žena nikomur ne sme dajati daril, ne da bi mož znal za to* ‘A wife must not give gifts to anyone without her husband’s knowledge’), or decision-making power (*What a woman has to say above her whisper isn’t worth listening to*). Women are likened to

prey (*Man is a hunter, woman is his game*), and their value is reduced to domesticity and reproduction (*A woman should be kept barefoot and pregnant and in the kitchen*)¹. These portrayals reinforce the idea of women as possessions rather than individuals, expected to be obedient, silent, and controlled by men.

- The semantic field *Misogyny* promotes mistreatment of women as a form of education (*A dog, a woman and a walnut tree: the more they are beat, the better they are*) and reinforces submission and fear as a woman's rightful place (*Psa drži na verigi, konja na povodcu, žensko v strahu* 'A dog on a chain, a horse on a lead, a woman in fear').
- The proverbs grouped under the semantic field *Domestic* emphasise women's roles and duties within the household. A woman is restricted to her home (*Woman's place is in her home/the house*) where her presence is indispensable, upholding warmth, stability, and functionality (*Hiša ne stoji na zemlji, ampak na ženi* 'The house does not stand on the land, but on the wife'). Women are the backbone of the household (*Pridna žena tri vogle hiše podpira, pa še četrtega pomaga možu nositi* 'A hard-working wife supports three corners of the house and helps her husband carry the fourth').

The second category, *Expectations*, constitutes three semantic fields:

- The semantic field entitled *looks* underscores the emphasis on women's physical appearance, often framing beauty as crucial to success (*A man without ambition is like a woman without looks/beauty*). At the same time, this creates unrealistic expectations to which women are expected to conform (*Inside every fat woman, there is a thin woman trying to get out*), even to the point of prioritising appearance over intellect (*Women are wacky, women are vain: they'd rather be pretty than have a good brain*). On the other hand, certain physical traits are framed negatively. Being tall is seen as a burden in the household (*Bel konj in velika ženska sta dve nesreči pri hiši* 'A white horse and a large woman are two misfortunes at the house'), while being too thin is associated with impracticality (*A skinny woman is like a racehorse: fast and fun but no good for work*). At the same time, a lack of beauty may be seen as protective (*Plain women are as safe as churches*), and ultimately a woman's beauty is enhanced by her husband (*Pava lepša perje, ženo mož* 'A peacock is adorned by its feathers, a woman by her husband').
- The semantic field entitled *Age* reflects societal pressures surrounding the aging process, especially for women. While aging is respected in men, it is presented as a more delicate topic with women (*Age is venerable in a man and would be in a woman if she ever became old*), best avoided in conversation (*A diplomat is a man who always remembers a woman's birthday but never her age*). It should be noted that no corresponding Slovenian proverbs were identified in this semantic field, which may indicate a cultural asymmetry in the proverbial encoding of age-related norms.
- The semantic field entitled *Moral* emphasises a woman's virtue. Her moral character is the most valuable asset in a home (*The best furniture in the house is a virtuous woman*),

¹ Although this proverb could also be associated with the *Domestic* category, it was ultimately classified under *Inferior* due to its dominant semantic focus on power asymmetry, subordination, and lack of female agency. In line with the coding principle adopted in this study, each proverb was assigned to the category reflecting its overarching conceptual meaning rather than secondary thematic associations.

and her actions can either honour or disgrace her husband (*A virtuous woman is a source of honour to her husband, a vicious one causes him a disgrace*). Virtuous women are rare and therefore highly sought after (*Dobre kose ni lahko dobiti, kakor ne dobre žene* 'A good scythe is hard to find, just as a good woman').

The third category, *Character*, constitutes five semantic fields:

- The semantic field *Powerful* portrays women as influential figures in society (*Denar in žene — vladarji zemlje* 'Money and women – the rulers of the earth') and within the household (*Mož pleše, kakor mu žena žvižga* 'The husband dances as his woman whistles'). Their influence is undeniable (*Never underestimate the power of a woman*) as their power shapes the success of those around them (*Behind every great man, there's a great woman*). In more contemporary expressions, women are depicted as independent and self-sufficient, no longer defined by their relationships with men (*A woman without a man is like a fish without a bicycle*).
- Within the semantic field *Troublesome*, we included proverbs that highlight women as instigators of conflict (*Skoraj ni prepira, ki od žene ne izvira* 'There is hardly a quarrel that doesn't originate from a woman'), a constant source of trouble (*Never quarrel with a woman*). A few even compare their nature to that of animals (*Women and dogs cause too much strife*) or malevolent forces (*A woman knows a bit more than Satan*). A woman's anger and her vengeance are extreme (*There is no fury like a woman's fury*). When a woman takes on an authoritative role within the home, it is often framed as an inversion of natural order (*Kjer žena hlače nosi, si mož kruha prosi* 'Where the woman wears the pants, the man begs for bread'). Proverbs also emphasise the troubles when women need to cooperate (*Dve ženski v kuhinji je huje ko sodni dan* 'Two women in the kitchen is worse than Judgement Day').
- *Manipulative* is another semantic field that permeates negativity as it portrays women as guileful (*To je pribita resnica, ženske so bolj zvite ko lisica* 'It's a truth, women are more cunning than a fox'). Their actions are calculated and self-serving (*Women are saints in the church, angels in the street, devils in the kitchen, and apes in bed*), adapting their behaviour to gain control or influence (*A woman is in pain, a woman's in a woe, a woman's ill when she likes to be so*).
- The semantic field entitled *Mysterious* portrays women as enigmatic and paradoxical (*A woman is the greatest contradiction of all*), elusive in their communication (*You can never pin a woman down to an answer*), fickle (*Vsaka ženska ima svojo čud* 'Every woman has her own character') and exasperating (*Women: you can't live with them and you can't live without them*).
- The proverbs in the semantic field *Gossipy* portray women as overly chatty (*Dve ženski – trg, tri – semenj* 'Two women – market, three – fair'), quick to spread information (*There are three types of communication: telephone, telegraph and tell a woman*), sometimes to the point of indiscretion (*Če se moškemu kaj pove, gre pri enem ušesu notri, pri drugem pa ven; če ženski, gre pri obeh ušesih noter, pri ustih pa ven* 'If a man is told something, it goes in at one ear and out at the other; if a woman, it goes in at both ears and out at the mouth').

The fourth category, *Opposites*, constitutes one semantic field, highlighting the idea that men and women are fundamentally different, each in their own distinct nature and behaviours (*Men are from Mars, women are from Venus*), implying that these differences are difficult to reconcile.

5.3. Cross-linguistically equivalent proverbs and their specifics

This part of the analysis focuses on seven cross-linguistically equivalent proverbs that appear in both languages and convey the same underlying message, even if they differ in metaphors or phrasing. It should be noted that the selection of the seven proverbs presented below is not exhaustive but the result of a deliberate sampling choice. As establishing such cross-linguistic equivalence proved challenging, only the most transparent and analytically robust cases are included. Other potential correspondences were excluded for (1) reasons of scope and (2) where equivalence was less direct, context-dependent, or open to interpretation.

Further, in order to explore the cultural elements embedded in these proverbs, we decided to examine them through a historical lens. Specifically, tracing their earliest recorded attestations was used as a means of situating the proverbs within broader patterns of transmission and potential origin. This diachronic perspective then served as a basis for considering whether culturally specific elements were preserved, adapted, or reinterpreted in the respective linguistic contexts. It should be noted, however, that a deeper investigation of Slovenian proverbs in this section did not yield a comparable range of historically traceable or well-documented examples as in the Anglo-American case, which inevitably affects the depth of diachronic and source-based comparison. All Slovenian proverbs in this section are attested in Šašelj's (1936) collection, except for proverb 5, which is documented in Babič (2021). Apart from their attestation in these two sources, no further information regarding their earlier origins or transmission history seems to be available, and their dating is limited to the time of their inclusion in the respective compilations. This limitation is therefore addressed here in order to avoid repetition across the analysis of the seven examples.

The seven cross-linguistically equivalent proverbs are:

(1) *A good woman is hard to find/Dobre kose ni lahko dobiti, kakor ne dobre žene*

This anti-proverb reworks an established proverb *A good man is hard to find*, popularised by Flannery O'Connor's 1953 widely anthologised short story of the same name, which itself drew on a 1917 song by Eddie Green (Doyle 2007). The Slovenian variant introduces a rural metaphor, comparing a good woman to a good scythe, referencing Slovenia's agrarian past, as noted by literary figure Fran Levstik in his travelogue *A Journey from Litija to Čatež* (Levstik 2012). It is also a fine example of how culture, as the carrier of identity, values, thoughts, concepts, and beliefs, is manifested through language (Kutukdjian & Corbett 2009; Furlong & Bernaus 2017: 37).

(2) *A man without a woman is like a ship without a sail/Človek brez žene kakor soba brez stene*

The proverb draws on the phrase *a ship without a sail* written in 1859 in an article "What is a bachelor" by Launcelot Gossensberry in *Hutchings' Illustrated California Magazine*, which included various analogies for bachelorhood. Later, the proverb as we know it was used in 1909 in *Wilson's Photographic Magazine*, where W. F. Oliver refers to it as the opening line

of an old song titled “A Man without a Woman”. This proverb was later adjusted to suit a feminist movement of the 1970s as an anti-proverb *A man without a woman is like a fish without a bicycle* (Doyle et al. 2012: 159). The Slovenian variant introduces the comparison *like a room without walls* and echoes the nation’s deep cultural attachment to homeownership as the ultimate goal for Slovenian families, symbolising stability, security, and personal identity within one’s living environment (Sendi 2017: 136, 141).

(3) *Women are the devil’s net/Žena je vražja mreža*

The proverb draws on one of the greatest and most influential Spanish works, the play *La Celestina*, written by Fernando de Rojas in 1499. The phrase was first used in English around 1520 (Mieder et al. 1992), most likely referring to Celestina, who represents a subversive element in society, meddling with sexual desire and magical powers, being manipulative, cunning, and morally ambiguous (Newton 1974; Brocato 1996). The Slovenian variant is a direct equivalent of the English version.

(4) *Women are as fickle as April weather/Ženska je kakor aprilsko vreme*

The proverb can be traced back to King Francis I of France, a famous seducer who, after being deceived by one of his many mistresses, is said to have engraved the words “A woman often changes, but he who trusts her is a fool” on the windowpane of his room at the Château de Chambord. This phrase was later popularised by Victor Hugo in his 1832 play *Le Roi s’amuse*, emphasizing the theme of female inconsistency. Lastly, it was Giuseppe Verdi who adopted Hugo’s play into the opera *Rigoletto* in 1851, featuring the aria “La donna è mobile” sung by the Duke of Mantua, which echoes the same sentiment (Classic FM n.d). The Slovenian version compares women to April weather but excludes the word fickle.

(5) *There was never a conflict without a woman/Skoraj ni prepira, ki od žene ne izvira.*

The Anglo-American proverb was, according to Mieder et al. (1992), first recorded in Clarke’s *Paremiologia Anglo-Latina* in 1639, a notable early collection of proverbs. The Slovenian variant is a direct equivalent of the English version.

(6) *No house was ever big enough for two women/Dve ženski v kuhinji je huje ko sodni dan.*

The proverb reflects a long-standing cultural notion of inevitable conflict between equals sharing the same domestic space. According to Mieder et al. (1992), the Anglo-American proverb can be traced back to around 1450 and was later recorded in a compilation of ancient manuscripts entitled *Reliquiae* and edited by Wright and Halliwell in 1845. However, Taylor (1957) argues for an even earlier origin, identifying a related idea in a medieval Latin source quoted by Richard de Bury in *Philobiblon* (1344). At the same time, Archer Taylor emphasises that although this is a relatively old proverb, it has been cited only infrequently and seems to be characteristically English in circulation. More broadly, he situates it within a larger family of traditional expressions, found across Europe, and even in Far East traditions, that convey the idea that two of a kind in close proximity are prone to rivalry or disagreement, often expressed through metaphor rather than literal meaning. Slovenian variant compares the presence of two women in the kitchen to being worse than the doom’s day.

(7) *Two things govern the world—women and gold/Denar in žene — vladarji zemlje*

The proverb highlights the perception of women and wealth as powerful forces that influence or control the world. The Anglo-American version is relatively recent, first recorded in *A Dictionary of American Proverbs* (Mieder et al. 1992), which attributes its distribution to the district of Oregon, based on fieldwork across North America between the 1940s and 1970s. Slovenian variant is a direct equivalent of the English version.

The analysis suggests that, out of seven proverbs identified as close equivalents, only the Slovenian proverbs 1 and 2 contain references to culturally specific elements, namely Slovenia's agrarian past and its strong cultural attachment to homeownership, respectively. No explicit cultural references tied to the Anglo-American context could be identified in the Anglo-American proverbs, nor in the Slovenian proverbs 3, 4, 5, and 6. Rather, they all can be interpreted as reflecting more universal patterns of gender representations, particularly those associated with historically dominant patriarchal ideologies, except for proverb 7 that departs from predominantly negative evaluative patterns by presenting women as influential and attributing agency and power to them.

Although the dataset is limited, the analysis suggests that both the Anglo-American and Slovenian proverbs demonstrate how language and folklore can perpetuate stereotypes across time and language.

6. Discussion

The analysis of dictionary definitions of the term *woman* in English and *ženska* in Slovenian reveals that both Anglo-American and Slovenian dictionary definitions begin with a neutral, biological description, but diverge in their broader semantic framing. Anglo-American dictionary entries tend to offer a more inclusive and nuanced understanding of womanhood, acknowledging both traditional and modern identities. Some outdated or stereotypical expressions persist; however, they are typically marked as old-fashioned, humorous, or offensive, signalling an awareness of their problematic nature. In contrast, Slovenian entries, when they extend beyond the biological definition, embed numerous characterisations that associate women with specific physical attributes, emotional instability, and stereotypical behavioural traits, which largely reinforce stereotypes that appear to normalise such representations rather than distance from them. This very issue has also been addressed in a linguistic debate in Slovenia on the language consulting platform *Jezikovna svetovalnica* (Jezikovna svetovalnica n.d.), where the question was raised whether the term *woman* could be defined more equitably in relation to a man. The question titled *Je ženska – človek ali oseba* ('Is a woman a human being or a person?') ("Je ženska – človek ali oseba" n.d.) advocates for more gender-neutral and inclusive language in the representation of both sexes. The dilemma lies in the fact that the word *man* is defined as a person, a somebody, while *woman* is described merely as a human being. Such seemingly small lexical choices, when implemented in reference works, may have far-reaching effects as they help perpetuate traditional views of gender and influence everyday perceptions.

Further, the research revealed the presence of shared semantic fields across both corpora, indicating a rich shared proverbial tradition. The presence of all four overarching categories and a substantial overlap in the 12 identified semantic fields points to a broadly shared conceptualisation of womanhood across the two traditions. Highly frequent fields

(i.e. *Troublesome*, *Inferior*, *Manipulative*, *Domestic*, and *Gossipy*) appear in both corpora, suggesting that negative and stereotypical representations of women may not be culturally specific but form part of a wider, transnational proverbial repertoire. This observation aligns with authors who pointed out that human cognition is not only socially, culturally, linguistically, and contextually dependent, but primarily tends to be universal and symbolic (cf. Dobrovol'skij 1992; Lauhakangas 2001; Brown & Wright-Harp 2011; Cruse 2011). At the same time, it is important to recognise that the meaning of a proverb is shaped by the prevailing values of its time and may change accordingly; proverbs are therefore subject to shifting interpretations based on evolving values, tastes, and attitudes (Taylor 1985). Importantly, Babič (2021: 88) argues that despite certain societal shifts in perceptions of gender roles, core gender stereotypes remain remarkably stable across discourse genres or are even reinforced. Such examples highlight the persistence of gendered stereotypes in society and the role of folkloristic forms as carriers of these representations, concluding that proverbs, in particular, function as enduring vehicles of cultural transmission, preserving and reproducing patterns of thought that may originate in earlier stages of social development but continue to shape contemporary discourse.

Next, the analysis focused on seven cross-linguistically equivalent proverbs, indicating the same underlying message despite formal or metaphorical differences. Of these, only two Slovenian proverbs contain clearly identifiable culturally specific elements. The rest show no culturally specific adaptations and rather reflect broadly shared themes, particularly the portrayal of women as troublesome, manipulative, or socially disruptive. This underscores the enduring influence of patriarchal thought. A brief look at history reveals persistent misogyny, as pointed out by Ramšak (2004): The Greeks were openly hostile to women, while the Romans, though more permissive, remained ambivalent; the Middle Ages were especially harsh, portraying women as sinful and in need of punishment. Medieval literature often depicted them as passionate, gossipy, hypocritical, and incapable of keeping secrets. The enduring trope of the talkative, untrustworthy woman, often punished to be controlled, appeared across religious, literary, and oral traditions, typically voiced by men but sometimes passed on by women themselves (Ramšak 2004: 122). This sentiment, which eventually found its way into proverbs, was widely endorsed by those who authored the moral and ideological narratives of their age (Račić 2023: 113–14). One such figure was the influential and leading theologian Thomas Aquinas of the 13th century, who argued that women were inherently inferior due to their passive souls and weaker intellect, describing them as accidents of nature whose primary purpose was childbearing and supporting men (McCluskey 2007: 2; Petri 2016: 277; Early 2024: 5). This also aligns with Litovkina (2018), who noted that proverbs have preserved discriminatory attitudes toward women for centuries, reinforcing cultural norms that devalue and marginalise them, helping to perpetuate traditional gender roles with deeply ingrained patriarchal structures. Further, this is also in line with Mieder (2004: 146–48) and Burger et al. (2012: 224–72), who contend that proverbs serve to uphold established systems and norms, often presented as teachings of moral values and social skills, and are firmly embedded in child-rearing practices within families and educational settings.

7. Conclusion

The research represents the first cross-linguistic comparison of Anglo-American and Slovenian proverbs featuring the word *woman*; it integrates semantic field analysis with cultural and historical contextualisation. It demonstrates that cultural values, societal experiences, and underlying ideologies are not only embedded in proverbs but can be found even in dictionary definitions, as seen in the Slovenian word entry for *ženska*, which perpetuates traditional and stereotypical representations to a much greater extent than the more inclusive and multifaceted portrayals found in Anglo-American dictionary entries. Additionally, the research uncovered a number of shared semantic fields across both corpora, pointing to a rich shared proverbial tradition. While the analysis of cross-linguistically equivalent proverbs did not uncover many culturally specific elements, it did highlight the universality of human thought and the pervasive influence of patriarchal values, portraying women as subordinate, emotionally unstable, or morally questionable. However, the research also identified proverbs that acknowledge women's strength and independence; particularly more recent Anglo-American creations, shaped by feminist thought and the women's liberation movement, signal a shift toward more equitable gender representations.

A limitation inherent in this study, which requires caution when generalising beyond the current sample, is that the two corpora, despite very thorough research, may not be exhaustive – an insurmountable challenge in proverb studies. Additionally, when providing translations of the Slovenian proverbs, it must be acknowledged that certain semantic and cultural nuances may be partially lost or modified. In this sense, the findings highlight that proverb translation cannot be reduced to a purely lexical process but involves varying degrees of adaptation to convey culturally embedded meanings. This is particularly evident in cases where equivalent proverbs differ in imagery or metaphorical structure across the two languages. As argued in translation studies, translation entails processes of selection and recontextualization rather than neutral transfer. In this respect, the translation of proverbs may contribute to the maintenance or modification of culturally embedded representations, particularly those related to gender and social relations.

In the future, given the notable lack of research on Slovenian proverbs that reference women, more extensive and systematic studies are needed. In particular, attention should be given to women's anti-proverbs in Slovenian context, an area where research is currently non-existent. Exploring this would provide valuable insights into whether traditional gender roles are being challenged or subverted in contemporary language use. Additionally, it would be worthwhile to conduct a semantic field analysis of proverbs featuring the word *man/moški/mož* to examine how men are positioned relative to categories established in this study. Such an analysis could offer a deeper understanding of the societal values and gender dynamics encoded in language and whether similar mechanisms of stereotyping, idealisation, and critique apply to male figures.

Sources

For the Anglo-American proverb collection

- Doyle, Charles & Mieder, Wolfgang & Shapiro, Fred. 2012. *The dictionary of modern proverbs*. New Haven and London: Yale University Press.
- Litovkina, Anna T. & Dobrovolskij, Oleg. (eds.). 2000. *A proverb a day keeps boredom away*. Pécs-Szekszárd: IPF-Könyvek.
- Litovkina, Anna T. 2018. *Women through anti-proverbs*. London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Mieder, Wolfgang & Kingsbury, Stewart A. & Harder, Kelsie B. (eds.). 1992. *A dictionary of American proverbs*. New York: OUP.
- Speake, Jennifer. 2008. *Oxford dictionary of proverbs*. Oxford: OUP.
- Merriam-Webster. n.d. *Merriam-Webster Dictionary*. (<https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/woman>) (Accessed 2026-04-23.)
- Oxford University Press. n.d. *Oxford Learner's Dictionaries*. (<https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/woman>) (Accessed 2026-04-23.)

For the Slovenian proverb collection

- Babič, Saša. 2021. Stereotipna podoba ženske v slovenskih folklornih obrazcih [Stereotypical image of women in Slovenian folklore forms]. In Žbogar, Alenka (ed.), *Ustvarjalke v slovenskem jeziku, literaturi in kulturi* [Women creators in Slovenian language, literature and culture] Ljubljana: Znanstvena založba Filozofske fakultete. 80–88. doi: [10.4312/SSJLK.57.80-88](https://doi.org/10.4312/SSJLK.57.80-88).
- Meterc, Matej. 2023. *Slovar pregovorov in sorodnih paremioloških izrazov* [The dictionary of proverbs and related paremiological terms]. Ljubljana: Založba ZRC. doi: [10.3986/9789610508533](https://doi.org/10.3986/9789610508533).
- Meterc, Matej. 2020–. *Slovar pregovorov in sorodnih paremioloških izrazov* [The dictionary of proverbs and related paremiological terms]. Ljubljana: ZRC SAZU, Založba ZRC. doi: 10.3986/3023-9664. (Accessed 2026-04-21.)
- eSSKJ: *Slovar slovenskega knjižnega jezika* [The standard Slovenian dictionary 2016–] Spletni rastoči slovar na www.fran.si Ljubljana, 2016–. © 2016–, ZRC SAZU, Inštitut za slovenski jezik Frana Ramovša, Založba ZRC. (Accessed 2026-04-25.). doi: [10.3986/2738-6643](https://doi.org/10.3986/2738-6643).
- Šašelj, Ivan. 1936. Kaj pripovedujejo slovenski pregovori o ženskah [What Slovenian proverbs say about women]. *Etnolog* 8(9): 31–33.

References

- Arora, Sherley. 1984. The perception of proverbiality. *Proverbium* 1: 1–38.
- Babič, Saša. 2011. Paremiologija – na križišču jezikoslovja in slovstvene folkloristike [Paremiology – at the crossroads of linguistics and literary folklore studies]. In Kranjc, Simona (ed.), *Meddisciplinarnost v slovenistiki* [Interdisciplinarity in Slovenian studies]. Ljubljana: Znanstvena založba Filozofske fakultete. 27–31.

- Babič, Saša. 2020. O možeh besedah, regljajočih babah in ostalih (folklornih) stereotipih [About men of their word, chattering women, and other (folkloric) stereotypes]. *Alternator: misliti znanost* 33. doi: [10.3986/alternator.2020.33](https://doi.org/10.3986/alternator.2020.33).
- Baker, Mona. 2018. *In other words. A coursebook on translation*. London: Routledge. doi: [10.4324/9781315619187](https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315619187).
- Bassnett, Susan. 2014. *Translation studies*. London: Routledge.
- Bowen, Glenn A. 2009. Document analysis as a qualitative research method. *Qualitative Research Journal* 9(2): 27–40. doi: [10.3316/QRJ0902027](https://doi.org/10.3316/QRJ0902027).
- Brocato, Linde M. 1996. Cutting commentary. “Celestina”, spectacular discourse, and the treacherous gloss. *Celestinesca* 20(1/2): 103–28.
- Brown, Janet E. & Wright-Harp, Wilhelmina Y. 2011. Cultural and generational factors influencing proverb recognition. *Communication Science and Disorders* 38: 26–35.
- Brunvand, Jan Harold. (ed.). 1996. *American folklore. An encyclopedia*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- Burger, Harald & Buhofer, Annelies & Sialm, Ambros. 2012. *Handbuch der Phraseologie [Handbook of phraseology]*. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter.
- Chesterman, Andrew. 2016. *Memes of translation. The spread of ideas in translation theory*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Classic FM. n.d. What are the lyrics to ‘La donna è mobile’ and what do they mean? (<https://www.classicfm.com/composers/verdi/la-donna-e-mobile-aria-lyrics-meaning/>) (Accessed 2025-05-25.)
- Creswell, John W. & Plano Clark, Vicky L. 2017. *Designing and conducting mixed methods research* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Cruse, Alan. 2011. *Meaning in language. An introduction to semantics and pragmatics*. Oxford: OUP.
- Dobrovól’skij, Dmitrij. 1992. Phraseological universals. Theoretical and applied aspects. In Kefer, Michael & Van der Auwera, Johan (eds.), *Meaning and grammar. Cross-linguistic perspectives*. Berlin: Walter de Gruyter. 279–302.
- Doyle, Charles Clay. 2007. A good man is hard to find. The proverb. *Flannery O’Connor Review* 5: 5–22.
- Early, Joseph E. 2024. Thomas Aquinas’s “misbegotten” concept of women. *Priscilla Papers* 38(4): 5–9.
- Espinal, M. Teresa & Mateu, Jaume. 2019. Idioms and phraseology. *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Linguistics*. Oxford: OUP. doi: [10.1093/acrefore/9780199384655.013.51](https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780199384655.013.51).
- Finegan, Edward. 2008. *Language. Its structure and use*. Boston: Thomson Wadsworth.
- Furlong, Áine & Bernaus, Mercè. 2017. CLIL as a plurilingual approach or language of real life and language as a carrier of culture. *Research Papers in Language Teaching and Learning* 8(1): 34–43.
- Harmon, Lucyna. 2021. Idiom as a translation technique. A theoretical postulate. *Cadernos de Tradução* 41(1): 125–47. doi: [10.5007/2175-7968.2021.e71778](https://doi.org/10.5007/2175-7968.2021.e71778).
- Hussein, Jeylan W. 2005. The social and ethno-cultural construction of masculinity and femininity in African proverbs. *African Study Monographs* 26(2): 59–87.

- Jezikovna svetovalnica. n.d. Je ženska – človek ali oseba [Is woman a person or a human being?]. ZRC SAZU. (<https://svetovalnica.zrc-sazu.si/topic/2733/je-%C5%BEenska-%C4%8Dlovek-ali-oseba>) (Accessed 2025-05-25.)
- Kara, Gökçen. 2021. Gender in Turkish proverbs. *International Social Mentality and Researcher Thinkers Journal* 7(49): 2049–54. doi: [10.31576/SMRYJ.1025](https://doi.org/10.31576/SMRYJ.1025).
- Keber, Janez. 2011. *Slovar slovenskih frazemov* [Dictionary of Slovenian idioms]. Ljubljana: ZRC SAZU.
- Kerschen, Lois. 1998. *American proverbs about women: A reference guide*. Westport, CT: Greenwood Publishing House.
- Kochman-Haładaj, Bożena. 2012. (Negative) perception of women in proverbs across cultures of the changing world. In Ferencik, Milan & Bednarova-Gibova, Klaudia (eds.), *Language, Literature and Culture in the Changing Transatlantic World II*. Prešov: Filozofická fakulta Prešovskej univerzity. 317–38.
- Kochman-Haładaj, Bożena. 2015. On positively tinted women proverbs (and quotations) in English and Polish language material. *Lingaya's International Refereed Journal of English Language & Literature (LIRJELL)* 2(1): 22–42.
- Kochman-Haładaj, Bożena. 2020. The vexing problem of gender stereotyping in world proverbs. *SKASE Journal of Theoretical Linguistics* 17(1): 1–14.
- Kochman-Haładaj, Bożena. 2022. Superiority of women over men in proverbs from around the world. In Szerszunowicz, Joanna (ed.), *Reproducible language units from an interdisciplinary perspective*. Białystok: University of Białystok Publishing House. 511–21.
- Kordeš, Urban & Smrdu, Maja 2015. *Osnove kvalitativnega raziskovanja* [Fundamentals of qualitative research]. University of Primorska Press.
- Kržišnik, Erika. 2008. Viri za kulturološko interpretacijo frazeoloških enot [Sources for the cultural interpretation of phraseological units]. *Jezik in slovstvo*, 53(1): 33–47.
- Kutukdjian, Georges & Corbett, John. (eds.). 2009. *The UNESCO World Report No. 2. Investing in cultural diversity and intercultural dialogue*. Paris: UNESCO.
- Lauhakangas, Outi. 2001. *The Matti Kuusi international type system of proverbs*. Helsinki: Suomalainen Tiedeakatemia.
- Levstik, Fran. [1858] 2012. *Popotovanje iz Litije do Čateža* [Journey from Litija to Čatež]. Ljubljana: Genija.
- Lewandowska, Anna & Antos, Gerd. 2015. *Cognitive aspects of proverbs*. In Hrisztova-Gotthardt, Hrisztalina & Aleksa Varga, Melita (eds.), *Introduction to paremiology. A comprehensive guide to proverb studies*. Warsaw: De Gruyter Open. 162–82.
- Litovkina, Anna T. 2011. The nature of women as revealed through Anglo-American anti-proverbs. *Proverbium* 28: 87–120.
- Litovkina, Anna T. 2014. Mothers-in-law, spinsters and widows as revealed through Anglo-American anti-proverbs. Baran, Anneli & Laineste, Liisi & Voolaid, Piret (eds.), *Scala Naturae. Festschrift in Honour of Arvo Krikmann*. Tartu: Eesti Kirjandusmuuseumi Teaduskirjastus, 171–92.

- Litovkina, Anna T. 2018. Women in American proverbs. In Litovkina, Anna T. (ed.), *Women through anti-proverbs*. London: Palgrave Macmillan. 3–24. doi: [10.1007/978-3-319-91198-4_1](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-91198-4_1).
- Madmarova, Gulipa & Rozykova, Mavliuda & Abytova, Gulsana & Imasheva, Gulmira & Kadyrova, Gulmira & Murzakulova, Kanymzhan & Kydykeeva, Ainura & Samargul, Aitieva & Surkeeva, Dinara & Abdullaeva, Zhypargul. 2021. Reflection of people's ethical ideas in proverbs and sayings. *Open Journal of Modern Linguistics* 11(3): 440–47. doi: [10.4236/ojml.2021.113033](https://doi.org/10.4236/ojml.2021.113033).
- Mandziuk, Justyna. 2016. A proverb a day keeps boredom away. Anti-proverbs, twisted proverbs, perverbs and other animals. *New Horizons in English Studies* 1(1): 21–31. doi: [10.17951/nh.2016.1.21](https://doi.org/10.17951/nh.2016.1.21).
- Martin, Carol Lynn, & Dinella, Lisa M. 2001. Gender-related development. In Smelser, Neil J. & Baltes, Paul B. (eds.), *International Encyclopedia of the Social & Behavioral Sciences*. Oxford: Pergamon. 6020–27.
- Masimova, Lala. 2018. Concept of phraseological units. Functional, structural, and semantic classification of phraseological units. *World Science* 6(34): 11–14. doi: [10.31435/RSGLOBAL_WS/12062018/5885](https://doi.org/10.31435/RSGLOBAL_WS/12062018/5885).
- McCluskey, Colleen. 2007. An unequal relationship between equals. Thomas Aquinas on marriage. *History of Philosophy Quarterly* 24(1): 1–18.
- Meterc, Matej. 2014. Primerjava paremiologije v slovenskem in slovaškem jeziku na osnovi paremiološkega optimuma [Comparison of paremiology in Slovenian and Slovak based on the paremiological optimum]. Ljubljana: University of Ljubljana. (Doctoral dissertation.)
- Mieder, Wolfgang & Litovkina, Anna T. 1999. *Twisted wisdom. Modern anti-proverbs*. Burlington: The University of Vermont.
- Mieder, Wolfgang. 1993. *Proverbs are never out of season. Popular wisdom in the modern age*. Oxford: OUP
- Mieder, Wolfgang. 1997. Modern paremiology in retrospect and prospect. *Paremia* 6: 399–416.
- Mieder, Wolfgang. 2004. *Proverbs. A handbook*. Westport, CT: Greenwood Press.
- Mieder, Wolfgang. 2010. American proverbs. An international, national, and global phenomenon. *Western Folklore* 69(1): 35–54.
- Mieder, Wolfgang. 2015. *Wise words. Essays on the proverb*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- Muradullayevna, Rustamova Malika. 2022. Phraseology as an object of linguistic and cultural studies. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science and Engineering Technology* 10(11): 892–94. doi: [10.22214/ijraset.2022.47502](https://doi.org/10.22214/ijraset.2022.47502).
- Newton, Jeremy. 1974. *Two eighteenth-century English adaptations of the Celestina*. London: Queen Mary University of London. (Doctoral dissertation.)
- Nippold, Marilyn A. & Martin, Stephanie A. & Erskine, Barbara J. 1988. Proverb comprehension in context: A developmental study with children and adolescents. *Journal of Speech and Hearing Research* 31(1): 19–28. doi: [10.1044/jshr.3101.19](https://doi.org/10.1044/jshr.3101.19).
- Nord, Christiane. 2018. *Translating as a purposeful activity. Functionalist approaches explained*. London: Routledge.

- Norrick, Neal R. 1985. *How proverbs mean. Semantic studies in English proverbs*. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Norrick, Neal R. 2015. *Subject area, terminology, proverb definitions, proverb features*. In Hrisztova-Gotthardt, Hrisztalina & Aleksa Varga, Melita (eds.), *Introduction to paremiology. A comprehensive guide to proverb studies*. Warsaw: De Gruyter Open. 7–27.
- Petri, Thomas. 2016. *Aquinas and the theology of the body*. Washington: CUA.
- Petrova, Roumyana. 2002. Gender aspects of English proverbs. *Proverbium. Yearbook of international proverb scholarship* 19: 337–48.
- Petrova, Roumyana. 2014. Contrastive study of proverbs. In Hrisztova-Gotthardt, Hrisztalina & Aleksa Varga, Melita (eds.), *Introduction to paremiology. A comprehensive guide to proverb studies*. Warsaw: De Gruyter Open. 224–61. doi: [10.2478/9783110410167](https://doi.org/10.2478/9783110410167).
- Račić, Anđelka. 2023. The women in the family/society throughout history. *Megatrend revija* 20(1): 107–20. doi: [10.5937/MegRev2301107R](https://doi.org/10.5937/MegRev2301107R).
- Ramšak, Mojca. 2004. Včasih znam tudi molčati, čeprav se zdi to malo verjetno: pripombe k mizoginim stereotipom o ženskem opravljanju [Sometimes I can keep quiet, even if it seems unlikely: comments on misogynistic stereotypes about women's gossip]. *Etnolog* 14(65): 121–38.
- Rasul, Sarwet. 2015. Gender and power relationships in the language of proverbs. Image of a woman. *FWU Journal of Social Sciences* 9(2): 53–62.
- Ronesi, Lynne. 2000. Mightier than the sword. A look at proverbial prejudice. *Proverbium. Yearbook of International Proverb Scholarship* 17: 329–47.
- Schipper, Mineke & Schipper, Wilhelmina Janneke Josepha. 2003. *Never marry a woman with big feet. Women in proverbs from around the world*. Yale University Press.
- Sendi, Rihard. 2017. Homeownership in Slovenia. Searching for an alternative theory on its excessive growth. *Urbani izziv* 28: 135–46. doi: [10.5379/urbani-izziv-en-2017-28-01-005](https://doi.org/10.5379/urbani-izziv-en-2017-28-01-005).
- Shtoltsel, Yulianna Y. 2018. The notion and criteria for classification of phraseological units. *Advanced Linguistics* 2: 9–13. doi: [10.20535/2617-5339.2018.2.158375](https://doi.org/10.20535/2617-5339.2018.2.158375).
- Storm, Hiroko. 1992. Women in Japanese proverbs. *Asian Folklore Studies* 51: 167–82. doi: [10.2307/1178330](https://doi.org/10.2307/1178330).
- Syzdykov, Kanat. 2014. Contrastive studies on proverbs. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences* 136: 318–21. doi: [10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.05.336](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.05.336).
- Taylor, Archer. 1957. No house is big enough for two women. *Western Folklore* 16(2): 121–24.
- Tymoczko, Maria. 2007. *Enlarging translation, empowering translators*. Manchester: St. Jerome Publishing.
- Venuti, Lawrence. 2018. *The translator's invisibility. A history of translation*. London: Routledge. doi: [10.4324/9781315098746](https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315098746).
- Vogrinc, Janez. 2008. *Kvalitativno izobraževanje na pedagoškem področju* [Qualitative training in teaching]. Ljubljana: University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Education.
- Taylor, Archer. [1931] 1962. *The proverb*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Taylor, Archer. 1985. *A proverb and an index to "The Proverb"*. Bern: Peter Lang

Toporišič, Jože. 1974. K izrazju in tipologiji slovenske frazeologije [On the terminology and typology of Slovenian phraseology]. *Jezik in slovstvo* 19(8): 273–79.

Webster, Sheila K. 1982. Women, sex, and marriage in Moroccan proverbs. *International Journal of Middle East Studies* 14(2): 173–84.

Melita Lemut Bajec
University of Ljubljana
Faculty of Education
Kardeljeva ploščad 16, 1000 Ljubljana
Slovenia
e-mail: melita.lemutbajec@pef.uni-lj.si

Klara Šumenjak
University of Primorska
Faculty of Humanities
Titov trg 5, 6 000 Koper
Slovenia
e-mail: klara.sumenjak@fhs.upr.si

Adapting *Ad Hoc* Concepts in Screen Productions

Ali Sukayna, The University of Jordan

Marwan Jarrah, The University of Jordan

Amer Al-Adwan, Hamad Bin Khalifa University

Abstract

This paper examines how ad hoc concepts are rendered in the English subtitles of colloquial Jordanian Arabic in the Netflix film The Alleys (2021). Ad hoc concepts, shaped through narrowing, broadening, or both, result from pragmatic modifications of lexical items. The study analyses selected concepts and figurative expressions, revealing that many were adapted rather than translated literally to ensure clarity and contextual relevance. Two main types emerge: Those shaped by narrative events and those grounded in Jordanian sociocultural contexts, encompassing figurative and non-figurative language. Subtitlers prioritized conveying culture-specific meanings, reflecting the film's setting in an Amman neighborhood where language use is tightly bound to cultural identity. Literal translation would risk miscomprehension for English viewers; instead, contextually tailored renditions preserved both meaning and nuance, underscoring the subtitler's role in balancing linguistic accuracy with cultural accessibility.

Keywords: Ad hoc concepts, explicatures, relevance theory, subtitling

1. Introduction

The domain of audiovisual translation has experienced notable growth in recent years (Pérez-Escudero 2018; Bogucki 2020; Wang & Daghigh 2024), driven by globalization and the rapid rise of video streaming platforms, which have amplified demand for translated audiovisual content (Ali et al. 2024b).¹ As global audiences consume more translated material, translation techniques have become increasingly critical to ensuring accessibility and comprehension across linguistic and cultural boundaries.

Among these methods, subtitling stands out as the most widely adopted and a key driver of recent advancements (Díaz Cintas 2013), enabling access to diverse works for broad audiences (Díaz Cintas & Remael 2014). In the Arab world, subtitling dominates English–Arabic translation (Gamal 2019; Qasim & Yahiaoui 2019), underscoring the need for high-quality translations that convey meaning without imposing excessive cognitive effort on viewers. For subtitles to be effective, they must be clear and comprehensible (Bogucki 2020). One way to enhance clarity is through pragmatic processes that refine the intended message, producing explicatures (Murtisari 2013; Jarrah & Al-Jarrah 2023), interpretations derived from integrating linguistic expressions with contextual clues (Sperber & Wilson 1995; Wilson 2016). Explicatures give audiences the elements needed to infer intended meanings without fully stating them (Carston 2004).

This study focuses on one pragmatic process of generating explicatures: *Ad hoc* concept construction, adjusting the meaning of expressions to align with context (Yus 2006;

¹ We are grateful to two anonymous reviewers for their careful reading of the manuscript and for their detailed and constructive comments. Their suggestions led to substantial improvements in the clarity of the argumentation and the presentation of the empirical results. Any remaining shortcomings are, of course, our own.

Huang 2014). Such adjustments may narrow or broaden the original meaning, depending on communicative needs. By doing so, subtitlers facilitate explicit interpretation and reduce audience cognitive load. This is particularly relevant when translating figurative language, which is often culture-bound and opaque without adaptation.

Consider the following examples from colloquial Jordanian Arabic:

- (1) هاي البنت حلوة
ha:j ʔilbint ʔilwah
(Lit. ‘This girl is sweet!’)

The adjective *ʔilwah* (‘sweet’) may refer to physical beauty or inner qualities. In a context of admiration for appearance, *the girl is luscious* captures the physical sense. If referring to kindness, *the girl is sweet-hearted* is more appropriate. The choice depends on conversational context and intended attributes.

- (2) البنت قطاعة
ʔilbint qatʔa:ʕah
(Lit. ‘The girl is pliers.’)

Here, *qatʔa:ʕah* literally means ‘pliers’ but figuratively conveys studiousness. A literal translation would confuse English audiences unfamiliar with the metaphor. *The girl is a bookworm* preserves the figurative sense and ensures cultural accessibility.

Such examples illustrate how *ad hoc* constructions adapt meaning to fit context and audience expectations, particularly when figurative or culture-specific expressions are involved. Translating these constructions directly often risks incomprehension; contextually adapted renditions preserve both meaning and cultural considerations.

Studying the use of *ad hoc* concepts in subtitling is linguistically and pragmatically significant. In relevance theory, *ad hoc* concepts arise through contextual processes of lexical adjustment such as narrowing, broadening, or a combination of both (Carston 2002; Sperber & Wilson 2012). These processes illustrate how speakers and listeners derive contextually appropriate meanings that may differ from the conventional sense of a lexical item. For translators, particularly subtitlers, interpreting and conveying such context-dependent meanings can be challenging, especially given the temporal and spatial constraints of subtitles (Díaz Cintas & Remael 2014). Examining how *ad hoc* concepts are translated therefore sheds light on how subtitlers balance fidelity to the source-language meaning with accessibility for the target audience, contributing to both theoretical and applied translation studies (Gutt 2000).

Moreover, analyzing whether subtitlers rely solely on narrative context or also consider sociocultural factors, audience expectations, and genre conventions offers insight into translation decision-making. Pragmatic research (e.g. House 2018; Ali et al. 2024a) shows that meaning is rarely encoded in linguistic form alone; it emerges dynamically through context. In subtitling, this entails cultural negotiation, deciding which aspects of the source concept are most relevant for the target audience (Baker 2018). Studying such decisions reveals implicit norms in translation practice and the extent to which cultural transparency is prioritized over lexical fidelity.

If subtitlers consistently employ strategies like explicitation, domestication, or reformulation, these patterns may reflect broader norms in resolving ambiguity across languages (Venuti 2017). This is increasingly important as global audiences rely on subtitled media, where effective handling of *ad hoc* constructions directly impacts intelligibility and reception.

The study also holds practical value for translator training, offering a framework for best practices in subtitling *ad hoc* concepts. By articulating strategies for managing such constructions, it contributes to improved translation quality and more culturally resonant media.

This article argues that translating *ad hoc* concepts, rather than using direct equivalents, more effectively conveys intended meaning, enhancing translation quality and viewer engagement. Accordingly, it addresses two research questions:

1. To what extent do Arabic–English subtitlers employ *ad hoc* concepts?
2. Do they rely solely on the film’s events or also consider broader contextual factors?

The remainder of the article is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews relevance theory and explicature, defining *ad hoc* concepts. Section 3 distinguishes concepts from *ad hoc* concepts. Section 4 details methodology, Section 5 presents findings, and Section 6 discusses results. Section 7 concludes with key insights and future research directions.

2. Relevance theory, explicatures, and *ad hoc* concepts

Relevance theory, developed by Sperber & Wilson (1986 [1995]), posits that human cognition is geared toward maximizing relevance, seeking the greatest contextual effect for the least cognitive effort (Yus 2006; Allott & Textor 2012; Huang 2014; Jarrah et al. 2024). An input, whether an utterance or a memory, is relevant when it interacts with a hearer’s existing knowledge to yield meaningful conclusions (Wilson & Sperber 2004; Carston 2004, 2010). In subtitling, if this alignment is lacking, subtitlers must supply contextual cues to facilitate comprehension.

Meaning is conveyed through explicatures, contextually developed explicit content, and implicatures, inferred meanings (Sperber & Wilson 1995; Carston 2002). Explicatures emerge from linguistic forms that require contextual enrichment, refined through pragmatic processes such as disambiguation, reference resolution (Recanati 2004), free enrichment (Ali et al. 2024b), saturation, and *ad hoc* concept construction (Barsalou 1992). These processes ensure that incomplete or ambiguous utterances are interpreted accurately.

Relevance theory thus frames communication as an inferential process in which linguistic expressions are only one component, with context providing the essential scaffolding for meaning. This interaction between language and context underpins effective subtitling, especially when translating culturally and pragmatically complex material.

Consider the following example, which demonstrates how a linguistic form is transformed into an explicature in translation from Jordanian Arabic into English:

- (3) حكتله انه راح عليه الموعد
 ḥake:tilloh ʔinno: ra:h ʕale:h ʔilmawʕid
 (Lit. ‘I told him that he missed the submission.’)

When combined with contextual information, this can generate the following explicature: *I told Mohammad that he did not meet the submission deadline for the writing course assignment*. This explicature is derived through several pragmatic processes that help clarify the intended meaning. Reference resolution allows the listener to identify *him* as Mohammad, ensuring the correct referent is understood. Disambiguation plays a role in interpreting the verb *missed* as *failed to meet the deadline* rather than any other possible meaning. Additionally, free enrichment refines the meaning of *submission* by specifying that it refers to a particular deadline. Lastly, free enrichment further clarifies the statement by specifying that the *assignment* in question belongs to the Writing course. Together, these processes contribute to a more precise and contextually appropriate interpretation of the utterance.

As previously highlighted, the formation of *ad hoc* meanings, which serves as the primary focus of this study, involves the contextual adaptation of an idea within its logical framework. Barsalou (1992) argues that expressions within this pragmatic domain do not carry fixed definitions that can be assigned according to strict guidelines. Instead, they convey a broad spectrum of interpretations that shift based on the surrounding context, with specific meanings being selected as necessary to fit different circumstances.

Within relevance theory, lexical meanings may undergo contextual adjustment through processes commonly described as narrowing and broadening. Narrowing occurs when the interpreted meaning of a word becomes more specific than its conventional dictionary sense. For example, the word *drink* may be interpreted as *alcoholic drink* in the sentence *He doesn't drink*. In contrast, broadening occurs when the interpreted meaning becomes more general or extended beyond its conventional sense. For instance, the word *mother* in the sentence *She is a mother to the whole team* extends beyond the literal meaning to describe someone who provides care or support. These processes demonstrate how speakers and listeners construct *ad hoc* concepts, adjusting lexical meaning to fit the communicative context.

3. Concepts versus *ad hoc* concepts

The distinction between concepts and *ad hoc* concepts lies in the stability versus contextual flexibility of meaning (Carston 2013). Concepts are stable mental representations storing encyclopedic and logical information (Wilson & Carston 2007). They act as labels for entities, properties, or activities, with fixed denotations that serve as fundamental building blocks of language. These representations also store general knowledge, which supports comprehension in specific contexts.

By contrast, *ad hoc* concepts are contextually adjusted meanings, created when a word's encoded sense is narrowed or broadened to suit a particular communicative situation (Yus 2006; Jarrah & Al-Jarrah 2023). They are pragmatically inferred during interpretation, functioning as temporary mental constructs relevant only to that occasion (Allott & Textor 2012). Their formation depends on contextual cues, available knowledge, and the pursuit of optimal relevance (Wilson & Sperber 2004).

This process can broaden meaning (e.g. using *Hoover* to refer to all vacuum cleaners) or narrow it to a more specific sense. Relevance theory further links *ad hoc* concepts to metaphor, hyperbole, and other non-literal uses, viewing them as manifestations of the same underlying mechanism: adjusting conceptual content to achieve maximal contextual effect with minimal cognitive effort.

An example of the distinction between concepts and *ad hoc* concepts is comparing *ad hoc* concepts to shopping lists. A shopping list for a one-time event is created for a specific purpose and then discarded afterward, much like an *ad hoc* concept that is used only in a specific context and doesn't endure (Allott & Textor 2012). Consider Table 1, which includes an example taken from the official Netflix subtitles of the sitcom *Friends* (Season 1). This example illustrates the creation of the *ad hoc* concept *ʔalmaqʕaf* ('canteen') in the subtitle.

Table 1: Example of *ad hoc* concept construction

The Source Utterance	Netflix's Subtitle
Alright, so I'm back in high school, I'm standing in the middle of the cafeteria , and I realize I am totally naked.	حسناً. كنت في الثانوية أف في وسط المقصف حين اكتشفت أنني عار تماماً. ḥasanan kuntu fi: ʔal θa:nawijjah ʔaqifu fi: waʕ ʔalmaqʕaf ḥi:na ʔiktaʕaftu ʔannani: ʕa:rin tama:man (‘ok, I was in high school standing in the middle of the canteen when I realized I am totally naked.’)

In this example, the concept of “cafeteria” mentioned in the source language has been modified into the *ad hoc* concept of “canteen” in the subtitle. The word *cafeteria* typically refers to a place where food and beverages are served in a public setting, and it carries a specific meaning in many contexts. However, the subtitler has chosen to translate it as *ʔalmaqʕaf* ('canteen') instead of the more direct equivalent *kafiterja*: ('cafeteria'). This decision was made based on the specific context in which the concept *cafeteria* was used, namely, within a school environment. In the Arab world, especially in public schools, the concept *canteen* is more commonly used to refer to the food service areas, as opposed to *cafeteria*, which might imply a different, more formal or commercial setting. Therefore, the subtitler's adjustment ensures that the translation is both contextually appropriate and culturally relevant for the target audience.

Ad hoc concepts therefore refer to contextually adjusted meanings that arise during communication when a speaker pragmatically modifies a lexical concept to fit a specific discourse situation. This modification involves processes such as narrowing (restricting meaning), broadening (extending meaning), or a combination of both (Wilson & Carston 2007). Unlike fixed lexical meanings, *ad hoc* concepts are constructed dynamically based on contextual cues, speaker intentions, and hearer inferences. They play a crucial role in resolving ambiguity and enriching utterance interpretation, making them essential to theories of relevance theory and lexical pragmatics (Sperber & Wilson 1995; Carston 2002).

The primary purpose of this research is to examine how *ad hoc* concepts are rendered in the English subtitles of Arabic utterances, focusing on the interplay between linguistic meaning and contextual adaptation in translation. Specifically, this study investigates the extent to which subtitlers modify conceptual meanings when translating from colloquial Jordanian Arabic into English, analyzing how pragmatic adjustments such as narrowing, broadening, or a combination of both, shape the final translation. Given that *ad hoc* concepts emerge dynamically within discourse, their translation poses a unique challenge, requiring subtitlers to balance linguistic fidelity with contextual intelligibility. By exploring how these modifications occur, this research sheds light on the strategies used to manage linguistic ambiguity in

audiovisual translation, a field where meaning must often be compressed and adapted due to spatial and temporal constraints.

To achieve this, the study examines data drawn from the film *The Alleys* (2021), a Jordanian production available on Netflix, analyzing instances where *ad hoc* concepts and figurative expressions appear in the Arabic dialogue and how they are rendered in the English subtitles. This film provides a rich linguistic and cultural context, as it authentically represents spoken Jordanian Arabic in a socially and culturally embedded setting. By focusing on subtitling, a translation mode that requires conciseness while maintaining communicative intent, this research not only identifies how meaning is pragmatically reconstructed but also evaluates the extent to which cultural and contextual factors influence translation choices.

4. Methods

As mentioned earlier, this study examines Arabic utterances in the film *The Alleys* (2021) and explores the *ad hoc* concepts created by the subtitler to convey these utterances in context. The selected film is presented in the Jordanian dialect, and the data were collected by watching the original movie on Netflix with its English subtitles. Through repeated viewings, the researchers manually identified instances of *ad hoc* concepts by comparing the original Arabic expressions with their English translations, which had been adjusted *ad hoc*. Additionally, the definition of *ad hoc* concepts provided by Sperber & Wilson (1995) served as the reference point for identifying relevant examples.

To enhance the organization and effectiveness of the analysis, the identified *ad hoc* terms were categorized into two main types: *ad hoc* concepts shaped by the course of events within the film and those influenced by the Jordanian sociocultural context. All examples are presented in tables, displaying the original Arabic utterance with its phonetic transcription, and its English subtitle to illustrate how the subtitler adapted the meaning.

The film *The Alleys*, which became available on Netflix in 2021, stars Ali, a young man from a rough neighborhood in Amman, who deceives wealthy guests while trying to be with his lover, Lana. Their relationship is opposed by Lana's mother, Aseel, who turns to a gang leader, Abbas, leading to violence and revenge. Ali steals Abbas's money and flees with Lana, but she rejects his dishonesty, and Aseel, in a fit of rage, fatally stabs him. As she attempts to cover up the crime, new conflicts arise involving blackmail and stolen money.

The film was selected due to the significant number of *ad hoc* translations in its subtitles. This is largely because the main characters come from a poor, working-class background and frequently use colloquial Jordanian expressions. These informal and culturally specific terms often require creative translation strategies to retain their meaning and essence in the subtitles.

5. Findings

The study's findings indicate the identification of 82 instances of *ad hoc* concepts in the English subtitles. As previously noted, for the sake of clarity in discussion, these instances have been categorized into two distinct types: *ad hoc* concepts shaped by the course of events within the film and those influenced by the Jordanian sociocultural context. Each category will be examined separately. Table 2 shows the number of the identified examples on each category.

Table 2: The number of the identified examples on each category

<i>Ad hoc</i> concepts type	The number of examples detected	The percentage
<i>Ad hoc</i> concepts shaped by the course of events	32	39%
<i>Ad hoc</i> concepts influenced by the Jordanian sociocultural context	50	61%

The table provides a quantitative breakdown of the identified *ad hoc* concepts, categorizing them into two main types: those shaped by the course of events and those influenced by the Jordanian sociocultural context. The distribution of examples highlights a notable imbalance, with 61% of the instances falling under the sociocultural category, while only 39% are linked to event-driven modifications. This suggests that subtitlers often engage in significant conceptual adjustments due to cultural influences rather than merely adapting meanings based on the unfolding narrative. The dominance of sociocultural *ad hoc* concepts underscores the complexities of translating culturally embedded expressions. Unlike event-driven modifications, which rely on immediate narrative context, sociocultural adaptations demand a deeper understanding of local customs, social norms, and linguistic conventions. This finding highlights the importance of cultural competence in subtitling, as failure to account for these influences may result in loss of meaning or misinterpretation. Additionally, the data suggests that subtitlers prioritize audience comprehension over literal accuracy, reinforcing the view that translation is a dynamic, context-sensitive process.

5.1. Ad Hoc concepts shaped by the course of events

The findings of the study indicate that subtitlers frequently employ ad hoc concepts when rendering culturally and contextually loaded expressions. Addressing the second research question, this section examines cases in which such concepts are shaped primarily by the immediate course of events in the film. This category encompasses concepts that the subtitler has modified to align with the narrative progression and contextual demands of the film's events. In other words, the rationale behind adjusting these concepts lies in facilitating audience comprehension by ensuring their meanings resonate with the intended message conveyed in the specific scenes where they appear. Below are selected examples (see Tables 3–7), each accompanied by a contextual explanation and a subsequent discussion to clarify the relevant points.

Table 3: *Ad hoc* concept creation for *mrattab*

The Source Utterance	The Subtitle
كل مرة بتشوف عندي زبون مرتب بتوخذه مني kul marra bitʃu:f ʕindi zbu:n mrattab btu:xðoh minni: (Lit. 'Every time she sees that I have a neat customer, she takes him from me.')	Every time she sees me with a rich customer, she swoops in.

In this example, the conversation takes place between two women working at a nightclub. One of them is complaining to the other about a third woman who appears to attract her wealthier patrons. The Arabic adjective *mrattab* carries different connotations depending on context, with its conventional English equivalent being *neat*. For instance, when describing a man, *mrattab* can imply that he is well-groomed and takes care of his appearance; when describing a house, it can suggest that the place is tidy and well-organized. In the nightclub setting, a *mrattab* customer is generally understood to be someone who spends generously, particularly with the women he interacts with. While the exact nature of the interaction is not explicitly stated in the dialogue, the subtitler rendered it as *rich* to convey the sense of a financially rewarding patron. This choice preserves the intended meaning while remaining neutral and accessible to English-speaking viewers.

Table 4: *Ad hoc* concept creation for *ʔaṣṣab*

The Source Utterance	The Subtitle
<p>أنا أخذت أصعب قرار بحياتي ʔana: ʔaxadit ʔaṣṣab qara:r biḥaja:ti: (Lit. ‘I took the hardest decision in my life.’)</p>	I made the most painful decision of my life.

In this scene, Ali’s wife is shocked to learn that her husband is a thief just one day after their marriage. She tells him that running away with him and getting married was the most difficult decision of her life. The film’s events also reveal that Lana, Ali’s wife, had a very close relationship with her mother, who raised her and faced many struggles to provide a decent life for her, especially since her mother is divorced.

Given this background, it seems the subtitler chose not to translate the superlative form *ʔaṣṣab* using its typical English equivalents like *the hardest* or *the toughest*. Instead, the subtitler opted for *the most painful*, which better reflects Lana’s emotional turmoil. This choice conveys the deep personal anguish she feels, having just left her mother to live with Ali. The translation captures the emotional weight of the decision, highlighting the internal conflict Lana experiences in this moment.

Table 5: *Ad hoc* concept creation for *faba:b*

The Source Utterance	The Subtitle
<p>شباب faba:b (Lit. ‘young men’)</p>	Boys

In this scene, Abbas, the undisputed leader of the neighborhood, is seen issuing orders to his men, instructing them to engage in acts of blackmail and intimidation. As he addresses them, he refers to them as *faba:b*.

Linguistically, the Arabic noun *faba:b* is the plural form of *fa:b* and literally means ‘young men.’ In colloquial Arabic, however, the term often functions as a pragmatic form of address used to refer to a group of male associates, subordinates, or companions, and its interpretation is largely determined by context. In this particular scene, Abbas occupies a clear position of authority over the men he is addressing, who carry out his orders without question.

The subtitler renders the term as *boys*, a choice that does not correspond exactly to the literal meaning of *faba:b* but captures the informal and hierarchical tone of Abbas’s address. In English, *boys* is frequently used to refer to a group of male associates in a casual or commanding manner (e.g. Come on, boys), particularly when the speaker assumes a leadership role within the group. Within the context of the scene, this choice helps convey the pragmatic relationship between Abbas and his followers and reflects the dynamic of authority that structures their interaction.

From a relevance-theoretic perspective, the translation can therefore be interpreted as an *ad hoc* adjustment aimed at reproducing the pragmatic force of the source utterance rather than its literal lexical meaning. Instead of focusing strictly on the age-related sense of *young men*, the subtitle prioritizes the interpersonal tone and the group dynamic implied in the original dialogue, enabling the target audience to infer the hierarchical relationship between Abbas and his associates.

Table 6: *Ad hoc* concept creation for *zabbaṭit*

The Source Utterance	The Subtitle
<p>يوميتها زبطت النتائج jumi:tha: zabbaṭit ʔinnata:ʔidʒ (Lit. ‘That day, I fixed the results.’)</p>	I forged my grades.

The protagonist, Ali, is having a candid conversation with his wife. She mentions that she observed how overjoyed he appeared when the high school exam results were revealed. Ali then admits that his happiness was fake; in truth, he had failed the exams but had manipulated the results using Photoshop to give his family a sense of pride.

Ali uses the verb *zabbaṭit*, which in Jordanian Arabic generally means ‘fixed’ or ‘made something right’. In this case, what he really means is that he tampered with his grades to make them look as if he had passed. However, the subtitler recognized that translating this verb literally, such as *I made my grades right*, could mislead English-speaking viewers by implying a positive action. To avoid this ambiguity and make Ali’s confession clear, the subtitler opted for the word *forged*. This translation is not a direct equivalent of *zabbaṭit*, but it captures the true meaning of Ali’s actions within the film’s context. The subtitler ensures that viewers fully understand that Ali intentionally altered his results in a dishonest way, rather than merely fixing an error. This is an example of an *ad hoc* translation choice, where a new term is selected based on the surrounding events to ensure the intended message is conveyed accurately.

Table 7: *Ad hoc* concept creation for *thandisi:hom*

The Source Utterance	The Subtitle
<p>بدي اياكي تزيبهم و تهنديهم biḍdi: ʔija:ki: tzabṭi:hom withandisi:hom (Lit. ‘I want you to fix them and arrange them.’)</p>	I want you to doll them up and make them pretty.

In this scene, a customer arrives at a women's beauty salon with a group of girls and asks the hairdresser to enhance their appearance. In Arabic, the noun *handasa* directly translates to *engineering* in English. However, in Jordanian colloquial speech, the verb *handasa* carries a different meaning as it refers to skillfully arranging or refining something to make it as good as possible. For example, in the phrase *handasit ʔilqasdah* ('I engineered the gathering'), the meaning is that the gathering was planned and organized in an ideal way. Similarly, *handasit ʔilsufrāh* implies that the dining table was neatly arranged and decorated. Keeping this in mind, the subtitler chose to translate *handasi:hum* as *make them pretty* rather than opting for a literal translation like *engineer them*, which would sound unnatural in English. This *ad hoc* translation aligns with the specific context of a beauty salon. The subtitler ensures that the intended meaning is conveyed clearly and effortlessly to English-speaking viewers.

Building upon this point, it is essential to recognize that *ad hoc* concepts shaped by the course of events exemplify the subtitler's role as a mediator of meaning, aligning lexical items with the narrative flow and contextual nuances of the film. Such adjustments reflect the inherent fluidity of language, where meaning is not static but shaped by context and interaction, as emphasized in relevance theory (Sperber & Wilson 1995). When a subtitler modifies the concepts to match the unfolding events, he engages in what Gutt (2000) describes as a form of contextual adaptation, ensuring that the target audience's understanding is both accessible and coherent. This type of adjustment underscores the subtitler's pragmatics-driven decision-making, balancing the need for linguistic accuracy with the necessity of ensuring that the audience grasps the intended message in the context of the film's unfolding narrative.

Moreover, the adaptation of *ad hoc* concepts in line with the film's events highlights the dynamic and interpretive nature of translation, where meaning is constructed not merely by lexical equivalence but through a process of pragmatic enrichment (Carston 2002). The subtitler, in essence, plays the role of an interpreter of the story, navigating the intersections between language, context, and audience expectation, which reflects the broader understanding of communication as inherently context-dependent (Shaw 1987). Thus, the translation of *ad hoc* concepts shaped by events is not only an act of linguistic transference but a nuanced process of cultural and contextual negotiation that contributes to the overall communicative success of the subtitled film. Subtitlers thus facilitate the bridge between two linguistic worlds while preserving the integrity of the original message.

A comparison of the verbs in Tables 6 and 7 demonstrates how the same Jordanian Arabic verb *zabbat* ('fix') can take on different pragmatic meanings depending on context. In Table 6, *zabbatet* refers to Ali's act of tampering with his exam results, which is morally and contextually negative; the subtitler chose *forged* to convey the dishonest action accurately to English-speaking viewers. In contrast, in Table 7, *zabti:hom* ('fix them') retains a positive and skillful nuance, referring to enhancing the appearance of a group of women in a beauty salon. Here, the subtitler rendered it as *doll them up* or *make them pretty*, capturing the practical, aesthetic action rather than a literal translation like *fix them*, which would not convey the intended meaning. These examples highlight the importance of context in determining *ad hoc* translations: the same verb may require radically different English renderings depending on whether the action is evaluatively positive or negative and on the pragmatic cues within the scene.

Having explored how *ad hoc* concepts are shaped by the progression of the film's events, the next section shifts focus to another significant category: *ad hoc* concepts influenced by the Jordanian sociocultural context. These concepts reflect the deeper, culturally embedded meanings that subtitlers must navigate to ensure that the audience fully understands not only

the narrative but also the cultural nuances integral to the story. This section delves into how cultural references, social norms, and local practices shape the translation process, emphasizing the subtitler's role in adapting these concepts to a broader, often non-localized, audience.

5.2. Ad hoc concepts influenced by the Jordanian sociocultural context

While the previous section demonstrated how *ad hoc* concepts can be shaped by the immediate events of the film, the examples in this section illustrate that subtitlers may also rely on broader contextual factors. The instances in this category illustrate that the subtitler intentionally generated *ad hoc* interpretations influenced by Jordanian culture. Certain cultural expressions prompt the subtitler to devise contextually appropriate *ad hoc* renderings, which correspond to these cultural nuances. Note here that our assumption that the subtitler is guided by cultural factors in these cases does not imply that the context of the movie's events is irrelevant. Rather, it indicates that both cultural influences and situational context interact in shaping the translation choices. These examples are further categorized into two groups: non-figurative cultural *ad hoc* concepts and figurative cultural *ad hoc* concepts. As indicated in Table 2 above, this category comprises a total of 50 examples, with 44 being non-figurative and the remaining 6 classified as figurative.

5.2.1. Non-figurative cultural ad hoc concepts

Non-figurative cultural *ad hoc* concepts refer to constructions that the subtitler has specifically crafted to align with Jordanian cultural expressions. These translations aim to make it easier for the audience to understand the meaning with a minimal effort by providing translations *ad hoc* to align with the Jordanian expressions. The goal is to ensure that the viewers can grasp the intended meaning with no confusion, reflecting the cultural context in a way that feels natural for non-Jordanian audience. Consider Table 8.

Table 8: *Ad hoc* concept creation for *ʔil-ʔadʔdʔah*

The Source Utterance	The Subtitle
<p>الحجة مقرزيتي ʔil-ʔadʔdʔah mqazzizi:tɪ: (Lit. 'The old woman disgusted me.')</p>	My mom is bugging me.

In this example, one of Abbas's men is trying to secure a loan, explaining that his mother is constantly nagging him for money. The term *ʔil-ʔadʔdʔah* in Jordanian Arabic generally refers to an elderly woman, but in this specific context it idiomatically refers to the speaker's mother. Understanding the cultural context, the subtitler adapted the term for the English-speaking audience, rendering it as *mom* rather than a literal translation, to ensure clarity and accessibility. This choice reflects the subtitler's sensitivity to Jordanian expressions and everyday language use, conveying the intended pragmatic meaning while maintaining the informal and familiar tone appropriate for the scene.

The conversation from which the utterance in Table 9 was extracted took place in a women's salon, where one woman was attempting to persuade another to consider a particular girl as a potential bride for her son. While showing a picture of the girl, the groom-to-be's mother responded with *ha:j qawjjeh ʔana baʔrifha* which, when translated literally, means 'She is strong, I know her.'

Table 9: *Ad hoc* concept creation for *qawjjeh*

The Source Utterance	The Subtitle
هاي قوية أنا بعرفها <i>ha:j qawjjeh ʔana baʕrifha</i> (Lit. ‘She is strong, I know her.’)	I know her, she is too opinionated.

The Arabic adjective *qawjj* (‘strong’) is highly versatile and can be used to describe people, objects, or even abstract stances in various contexts. For instance, it can refer to a person’s physical strength, such as someone who works out at the gym. It can also describe the durability of an object, like a shelf that can support heavy weights. Additionally, it may be used to characterize a woman as having a strong personality. Nonetheless, in the Jordanian sociocultural context, when a mother searching for a bride for her son rejects a candidate by describing her as *qawjjeh*; the intended meaning is not related to physical strength or financial independence. Instead, it conveys that the woman has a strong personality, firm opinions, and a level of assertiveness that may be perceived as undesirable in a traditional marital setting. Recognizing this cultural nuance, the subtitler opted for an *ad hoc* translation, rendering *qawjjeh* as *opinionated*. This choice reflects an *ad hoc* linguistic adaptation, tailored specifically to the Jordanian context of the bride selection, ensuring that the intended meaning is conveyed naturally to English-speaking viewers.

In this scene, the barber was complimenting a customer on his appearance, admiring how well-groomed and elegant he looked. Following the compliment, the barber asked him whether he wanted to “do it again.” Consider Table 10.

Table 10: *Ad hoc* concept creation for *tʔanni*:

The Source Utterance	The Subtitle
بدك تتني <i>biddak tʔanni</i> : (Lit. ‘Do you want to take two?’)	Are you looking for a second wife?

In colloquial Jordanian Arabic, the verb *ʔiʔanni*: generally means to do something a second time. For instance, if someone finishes a sandwich, they might be asked *biddak tʔanni:?*, meaning ‘Do you want another one?’. However, in this particular context, the barber was not simply referring to repeating an action in a general sense, he was making a humorous reference to the idea of taking a second wife. In Jordanian culture, when a married man suddenly starts paying extra attention to his appearance, dressing sharply, grooming himself meticulously, and making noticeable efforts to look his best, those around him often tease him by suggesting that he may be considering a second marriage. Since Islam permits polygamy under certain conditions, this kind of lighthearted remark is a common cultural joke. The customer’s refined appearance, combined with the barber’s playful tone, provided clear contextual clues that helped the subtitler craft a translation that aligns with the intended humor and cultural connotations.

The translation of non-figurative cultural *ad hoc* concepts underscores the fundamental role of cultural competence in subtitling, aligning closely with the principles of relevance theory (Sperber & Wilson 1995). According to this framework, communication is guided by

the principle of optimal relevance, where the speaker (or in this case, the subtitler) must provide an utterance that yields maximum cognitive effects with minimal processing effort. In the context of subtitling, a literal translation of culturally embedded expressions may result in cognitive overload for the target audience, as they would need to infer unfamiliar cultural references without sufficient contextual cues. Instead, by strategically selecting a translation that conveys the cultural essence of the original expression, the subtitler enhances accessibility, ensuring that the intended meaning is immediately inferable without unnecessary cognitive strain. This aligns with Gutt's (1991) concept of indirect translation, which prioritizes communicative efficiency over rigid lexical fidelity, thereby facilitating an enriched interpretative experience for the audience.

Furthermore, the adaptation of non-figurative cultural *ad hoc* concepts exemplifies the inferential nature of meaning construction, a central tenet in pragmatic theory. Unlike direct lexical substitution, which assumes stable cross-linguistic equivalence, the rendering of culturally bound expressions demands pragmatic enrichment (Carston 2002). This process involves the context-driven modulation of meaning, where subtitlers strategically modify conceptual representations to ensure cultural relevance and contextual fit. Without such an adaptation, the audience would be forced to engage in extensive inferencing, potentially leading to misinterpretation or cognitive fatigue. As Mey (2001) asserts, meaning is not an inherent property of words but an outcome of situated language use, shaped by socio-cultural frameworks. Thus, subtitlers function as pragmatic mediators, dynamically balancing linguistic economy, cultural authenticity, and audience accessibility to optimize the communicative efficacy of the translated text.

5.2.2. Figurative *ad hoc* concepts

According to the relevance theory, figurative uses of the language are *ad hoc* constructions as they are considered as a kind of broadening the meaning intended (Carston 2002; Wilson & Carston 2007). Figurative language is a type of descriptive language used to convey meaning in a way that differs from its literal meaning. This includes figurative similes, metaphors, hyperbole, and allusions among others. Consider Table 11.

Table 11: *Ad hoc* concept creation for *ʃa:jɪfni: 'qa:ʕdah ʕala: bank*

The Source Utterance	The Subtitle
<p style="text-align: right;">شايّفني قاعدة عينك؟</p> <p>ʃa:jɪfni: 'qa:ʕdah ʕabank (Lit. 'Do you see me sitting on a bank?')</p>	<p>Do I look like a bank teller to you?</p>

In this example, Hanadi, Abbas's assistant, refuses to give one of Abbas's men a loan by saying *ʃa:jɪfni: 'qa:ʕdah ʕala: bank?* which literally translates as 'Do you see me sitting on a bank?'. The utterance functions as a figurative expression rather than a literal statement. In Jordanian colloquial usage, the expression evokes the idea that the speaker is being treated as if they had unlimited access to money and could provide it whenever requested. Thus, the pragmatic meaning of the utterance is not simply that the speaker is wealthy, but that she rejects the assumption that she should supply money on demand.

The subtitler rendered the line as *Do I look like a bank teller to you?*. Although this translation departs from the literal imagery of the Arabic expression, it preserves the underlying implicature that the speaker is not responsible for dispensing money whenever others request it. The reference to a bank teller foregrounds the role of someone expected to provide cash upon request, thereby recreating the pragmatic effect of the original utterance within a culturally accessible frame for the target audience. From a relevance-theoretic perspective, the translation can therefore be viewed as an *ad hoc* construction that seeks to reproduce the communicative intention of the source utterance rather than its literal metaphor.

As in the Arabic dialogue, the subtitler does not explicitly state the implicature ('I don't have money' or 'I will not give you money'). Instead, the translation preserves the inferential nature of the original expression, allowing viewers to derive the intended meaning through contextual interpretation. In this way, the subtitle maintains the pragmatic structure of the source utterance while adapting its figurative imagery to the expectations of the target audience.

In Jordan, *bari:zah* refers to a coin valued at 10% of a Jordanian Dinar. As a result, this term is primarily associated with money in the Jordanian context. Yet, in colloquial Jordanian Arabic, it has also developed figurative meanings. It is sometimes used metaphorically to describe someone as insignificant or unimportant. This comparison stems from the fact that *bari:zah* is a low-value coin, making it a fitting metaphor for worthlessness. Now consider Table 12.

Table 12: *Ad hoc* concept creation for *ʔiqḷaḷḷak halbari:zah*

The Source Utterance	The English Subtitle
<p>معلم اصرفلك هالبريزة mʕallim ʔiṣriflak halbari:zah (Lit. 'Boss, get rid of this coin.)</p>	<p>Check out this fool.</p>

In the context of this example, Ali's best friend visited the bar Ali frequently attended. Since it was his first time there, he ordered orange juice. This unusual request led the bar worker to ask his boss to remove him, referring to him as *bari:zah*. Recognizing the cultural significance of this figurative expression, the subtitler used the translation *fool*, as it conveys the idea that Ali's friend was out of place for ordering juice in a bar.

Table 13 includes an utterance from a conversation between Ali and his best friend, who was trying to persuade him to accept living in their modest neighborhood in east Amman and to take over his grandfather's small supermarket.

Table 13: *Ad hoc* concept creation for *ʔinta ʕa:jif bira:sak*

The Source Utterance	The Subtitle
<p>انت عايش براسك و بس ʔinta ʕa:jif bira:sak wbas (Lit. 'You're living in your head, and that's it.)</p>	<p>You have your head in the clouds.</p>

When Ali rejected the idea, his friend responded with *ʔinta ʕa:jif bira:sak wi bas*, which literally translates into English as ‘you live only in your head.’ This phrase, common in Jordanian culture, is figurative; no one literally lives in their head. The meaning behind this expression is that Ali is detached from reality, living in his own world and disconnected from the practical concerns of others, with plans and ideas that exist only in his imagination.

Figurative *ad hoc* concepts, as defined by Wilson & Carston (2007) and Carston (2010: 154–56), arise from pragmatic processes of broadening or narrowing lexical meaning to fit a communicative context. When such concepts carry strong cultural connotations, translation demands more than contextual inference, it requires sensitivity to the meta-cultural framework in which they are embedded. For example, the Jordanian Arabic phrase *ʔinta ʕa:jif bira:sak wi bas* (‘you live only in your head’) conveys not only detachment from reality but also a culturally grounded critique of neglecting practicality and social duty. Rendering it as *you have your head in the clouds* captures the cognitive detachment but not the full socio-cultural force. In relevance theory terms (Sperber & Wilson 1995), optimal translation maximizes contextual effects while minimizing processing effort. Here, cultural competence, not film context alone, is essential for reconstructing an equivalent conceptualization, underscoring the translator’s role as both pragmatic interpreter and cultural mediator.

6. Discussion

The findings of this study highlight the pivotal role that *ad hoc* concept formation plays in subtitling, particularly in rendering Arabic utterances into English. The analysis shows that subtitlers do far more than replace one word with another; they engage in pragmatic reasoning that is finely attuned to cultural and contextual signals. Carston (2010) argues that *ad hoc* concepts emerge through broadening and narrowing processes, allowing speakers to communicate meanings that are only partially encoded in linguistic form. For subtitlers, the challenge is to reconstruct these pragmatically enriched meanings in a way that maintains optimal relevance (Sperber & Wilson 1995) while ensuring that the audience can access them without undue cognitive effort. This balance, between semantic fidelity and pragmatic equivalence, requires deep cultural competence alongside linguistic skill.

A key contribution of this research is its demonstration that context, both micro and macro, is indispensable in subtitling *ad hoc* concepts. At the micro level, subtitlers must consider the immediate discourse, speaker intentions, and the inferential pathways the audience is likely to follow (Gutt 2000). At the macro level, they must work within broader sociohistorical and cultural frameworks. As the data reveal, certain *ad hoc* concepts are culture-bound, demanding culturally resonant equivalents rather than literal renderings. This aligns with audiovisual translation (AVT) scholarship (Gambier 2009; Pérez-González 2014; Chaume 2018; Díaz Cintas & Remael 2020;), which views subtitling as a form of intercultural mediation, where pragmatic and cultural competence are as vital as linguistic accuracy.

Two primary types of *ad hoc* concepts emerge in Arabic–English subtitling. Non-figurative cultural *ad hoc* concepts involve culturally marked terms whose meanings are shaped by context. Here, subtitlers must decide whether to domesticate or foreignize (Venuti 1995), balancing cultural retention with audience accessibility. Figurative *ad hoc* concepts, by contrast, involve metaphors and idioms anchored in local cultural presuppositions. Their translation demands not only linguistic skill but also the ability to map

metaphorical meaning onto a functionally equivalent expression in English (Kövecses 2005). When these pragmatic and cultural layers are ignored, meaning loss is almost inevitable, leading to either distortion or an overload of interpretive effort for the viewer.

Theoretically, this study advances pragmatic equivalence as a central concern in subtitling. While AVT research has long discussed formal and dynamic equivalence (Nida 1964), our findings show that pragmatic equivalence, faithfulness to intended meaning as reconstructed through context, is indispensable (Baker 2018; Díaz Cintas & Remael 2020). It also strengthens the case for integrating pragmatics into translator training, especially for subtitling. Following Gutt's (2000) view of translation as an inferential process, subtitlers must be trained to identify *ad hoc* conceptual shifts and choose strategies that best achieve relevance for the target audience.

Beyond theory, the study has clear professional implications. As global streaming platforms like Netflix expand access to cross-cultural content, demand for high-quality subtitling continues to grow. Yet, as Díaz Cintas and Anderman (2008: 84–86) note, subtitlers often work under significant time and space constraints, which frequently require the condensation or omission of parts of the original dialogue. Our findings reaffirm that subtitlers are not just linguistic converters; they are cultural mediators. Finally, the research underscores a caution regarding technology in subtitling. While machine translation and AI-assisted tools are increasingly common, they lack the inferential capacity to handle context-dependent *ad hoc* concepts, relying instead on statistical patterns (Toral & Way 2015). For this reason, human subtitlers remain essential, particularly when pragmatic sensitivity, cultural depth, and relevance-driven decision-making are at stake.

7. Conclusions and recommendations

This study has demonstrated that the translation of *ad hoc* concepts in subtitling is a highly pragmatic process, requiring a deep engagement with both linguistic and cultural contexts. Drawing on insights from relevance theory (Sperber & Wilson 1995) and pragmatic inference (Levinson 2000), the findings highlight that subtitlers do not merely transfer lexical meanings but must engage in interpretive adjustments that maximize contextual effects while minimizing the audience's cognitive effort. In translating *ad hoc* concepts, subtitlers must navigate between broadening, narrowing, and conceptual shifts (Carston 2002), ensuring that the pragmatic force of an utterance is preserved across languages. This study illustrates that subtitling operates on a hierarchical structure of meaning construction, wherein micro-contextual cues interact with macro-cultural knowledge. In the case of *The Alleys* (2021), Jordanian cultural markers significantly influenced translation decisions, demonstrating that subtitlers must often prioritize meta-filmic cultural mediation over direct linguistic correspondence.

The pedagogical implications of these findings reinforce the necessity of incorporating pragmatics into audiovisual translation (AVT) training programs. As pragmatic competence is central to effective subtitling, curricula should integrate theoretical models from pragmatics, particularly relevance theory, to enhance translators' ability to handle context-dependent meaning negotiation. This aligns with Gutt's (2000) argument that translation is a form of interlinguistic communication that depends on inferential processes rather than code-matching equivalence. Additionally, the study calls for an interdisciplinary approach that bridges translation studies with discourse analysis, cognitive pragmatics, and media studies, ensuring

that subtitlers are equipped to manage the intricate balance between linguistic form, communicative intent, and cultural representation.

In the era of global streaming platforms, where audiovisual content reaches culturally diverse audiences, pragmatic challenges in subtitling have become more pressing than ever. Future research should extend the current inquiry by examining how subtitlers across different languages and genres handle *ad hoc* conceptual translation, investigating the extent to which multimodal constraints influence pragmatic adaptation. Furthermore, given the increasing role of AI in subtitling, it is crucial to assess whether machine translation systems can effectively process context-sensitive *ad hoc* concepts or if human intervention remains indispensable. By addressing these issues, scholars and practitioners can ensure that subtitling remains an efficient and culturally attuned medium of cross-linguistic communication, fostering more nuanced and effective intercultural exchange in an increasingly interconnected world.

Funding

No funding was received.

Conflict of interest

On behalf of all authors, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest.

References

- Ali, Sukayna & Jarrah, Marwan & Al-Jabri, Hanan. 2024a. When the context has the upper hand: The translation of religious expressions. *SKASE Journal of Translation and Interpretation* 17(2): 4–28.
- Ali, Sukayna & Rahman, Wan Rose Eliza Abdul & Chow, Yee Fan. 2024b. An analysis of explicatures in English-Arabic subtitles. The case of *Friends* on Netflix. *International Journal of Arabic-English Studies* 24(2): 457–82. doi: [10.33806/ijaes.v24i2.625](https://doi.org/10.33806/ijaes.v24i2.625).
- Allott, Nicholas & Textor, Mark. 2012. Lexical pragmatic adjustment and the nature of ad hoc concepts. *International Review of Pragmatics* 4(2): 185–208. doi: [10.1163/18773109-00040204](https://doi.org/10.1163/18773109-00040204).
- Baker, Mona. 2018. *In other words. A coursebook on translation*. London: Routledge.
- Barsalou, Lawrence. 1992. Frames, concepts, and conceptual fields. In Kittay, Eva & Lehrer, Adrienne (eds.), *Frames, fields, and contrasts. New essays in semantic and lexical organization*. Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum. 21–74.
- Bogucki, Łukasz. 2020. *A relevance-theoretic approach to decision-making in subtitling*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan. doi: 10.1007/978-3-030-51803-5.
- Carston, Robyn. 2002. Linguistic meaning, communicated meaning and cognitive pragmatics. *Mind & Language* 17(1–2): 127–48.
- Carston, Robyn. 2004. Relevance theory and the saying/implicating distinction. In Horn, Laurence R. & Ward, Gregory (eds.), *The handbook of pragmatics*. Oxford: Blackwell. 633–56.

- Carston, Robyn. 2010. Lexical pragmatics, ad hoc concepts and metaphor. A relevance theory perspective. *Rivista di Linguistica / Italian Journal of Linguistics* 22(1): 153–80.
- Carston, Robyn. 2013. Word meaning, what is said and explicature. In Penco, Carlo & Domaneschi, Filippo (eds.), *What is said and what is not. The semantics/pragmatics interface*. Stanford, CA: CSLI Publications. 175–203.
- Chaume, Frederic. 2018. An overview of audiovisual translation. Four methodological turns in AVT. *Journal of Audiovisual Translation* 1(1): 40–63.
- Díaz Cintas, Jorge. 2013. The technology turn in subtitling. *Translation and Meaning* 9: 119–32.
- Díaz Cintas, Jorge & Anderman, Gunilla (eds.). 2008. *Audiovisual translation. Language transfer on screen*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Díaz Cintas, Jorge & Remael, Aline. 2014. *Audiovisual translation: Subtitling*. London: Routledge.
- Díaz Cintas, Jorge & Remael, Aline. 2020. *Subtitling: Concepts and practices*. London: Routledge.
- Gamal, Muhammad. 2019. AVT studies in the Arab world. The road ahead. In Hanna, Sameh & El-Farahaty, Hanem & Khalifa, Abdel-Wahab (eds.), *The Routledge handbook of Arabic translation*. London: Routledge. 205–20.
- Gambier, Yves. 2009. Challenges in audiovisual translation. In Gambier, Yves & van Doorslaer, Luc (eds.), *The metalanguage of translation*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins. 17–25.
- Gutt, Ernst-August. 1991. *Translation and relevance. Cognition and context*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Gutt, Ernst-August. 2000. Translation as interlingual interpretive use. In Venuti, Lawrence (ed.), *The translation studies reader*. London: Routledge. 376–96.
- House, Juliane. 2018. Translation studies and pragmatics. In Capone, Alessandro & Mey, Jacob L. & Carapezza, Marco (eds.), *Pragmatics and its interfaces*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins. 143–62.
- Huang, Yan. 2014. *Pragmatics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Jarrah, Marwan & Ali, Sukayna & Aljabali, Yousef & Al-Jabri, Hanan. 2024. On the social meanings of avoiding fully-articulated explicatures and the role of pragmatics in utterance explication. *Lodz Papers in Pragmatics* 21(1): 143–67. doi: [10.1515/lpp-2024-0001](https://doi.org/10.1515/lpp-2024-0001).
- Jarrah, Marwan & Al-Jarrah, Rami. 2023. Translating explicatures between Arabic and English. Completing logical forms and calculating pragmatic competence and metalinguistic knowledge. *Babel* 69(2): 188–215. doi: [10.1075/babel.00319.alj](https://doi.org/10.1075/babel.00319.alj).
- Kövecses, Zoltán. 2005. *Metaphor in culture. Universality and variation*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Levinson, Stephen C. 2000. *Presumptive meanings. The theory of generalized conversational implicature*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Mey, Jacob L. 2001. *Pragmatics. An introduction*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Murtisari, Elisabet Titik. 2013. A relevance-based framework for explicitation and implicitation in translation. An alternative typology. *trans-kom* 6(2): 315–44.
- Nida, Eugene A. 1964. *Toward a science of translating. With special reference to principles and procedures involved in Bible translating*. Leiden: Brill.

- Pérez-Escudero, Fernando. 2018. A bibliometric analysis of doctoral dissertations in the subdiscipline of AVT. In Sanderson, John & Botella-Tejera, Carla (eds.), *Focusing on AVT research*. Valencia: Universitat de València. 159–90.
- Pérez-González, Luis. 2014. *Audiovisual translation: Theories, methods and issues*. London: Routledge.
- Qasim, Ahmed & Yahiaoui, Rashid. 2019. The role of subtitling and dubbing in Arabic vocabulary acquisition. A contrastive study. *Arab World English Journal for Translation & Literary Studies* 3(1): 74–86.
- Recanati, François. 2004. Pragmatics and semantics. In Horn, Laurence R. & Ward, Gregory (eds.), *The handbook of pragmatics*. Oxford: Blackwell. 442–62.
- Shaw, R. Daniel. 1987. The translation context. Cultural factors in translation. *Translation Review* 23(1): 25–29.
- Sperber, Dan & Wilson, Deirdre. 1986. *Relevance. Communication and cognition*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Sperber, Dan & Wilson, Deirdre. 1995. *Relevance: Communication and cognition* (2nd ed.). Oxford: Blackwell.
- Sperber, Dan & Wilson, Deirdre. 2012. The mapping between the mental and the public lexicon. In Wilson, Deirdre & Sperber, Dan (eds.), *Meaning and relevance*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. 31–47.
- Toral, Antonio & Way, Andy. 2015. Translating literary text between related languages using SMT. In *Proceedings of the Fourth Workshop on Computational Linguistics for Literature*. Denver, CO. 123–32.
- Venuti, Lawrence. 1995. Translation, authorship, copyright. *The Translator* 1(1): 1–24.
- Venuti, Lawrence. 2017. *The translator's invisibility. A history of translation* (3rd ed.). London: Routledge.
- Wang, Yating & Daghig, Ali Jalil. 2024. Two decades of audiovisual translation studies. A bibliometric literature review. *SAGE Open* 14(3). doi: [10.1177/21582440241274575](https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241274575).
- Wilson, Deirdre. 2016. Relevance theory. In Huang, Yan (ed.), *The Oxford handbook of pragmatics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. 79–100.
- Wilson, Deirdre & Carston, Robyn. 2007. A unitary approach to lexical pragmatics. In Burton-Roberts, Noel (ed.), *Pragmatics*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan. 230–60.
- Wilson, Deirdre & Sperber, Dan. 2004. Relevance theory. In Horn, Laurence R. & Ward, Gregory (eds.), *The handbook of pragmatics*. Oxford: Blackwell. 607–32.
- Yus, Francisco. 2006. Relevance theory. In Brown, Keith (ed.), *Encyclopedia of language and linguistics* (2nd ed.). Amsterdam: Elsevier. 512–19.

Sukayna Ali

*Department of English Language and Literature
School of Foreign Languages
The University of Jordan
e-mail: sukayna.ali@ju.edu.jo*

Marwan Jarrah (The corresponding author)

*Department of English Language and Literature
School of Foreign Languages
The University of Jordan
e-mail: m.jarrah@ju.edu.jo*

Amer AL-Adwan

*Department of Language, Culture and Communication
Hamad Bin Khalifa University, Doha, Qatar
e-mail: aadwan@hbku.edu.qa*